

Deliverable D2.1

Map of Railway needs in 2030

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1. Executive Summary

The Work Package 2 (WP2) of LEADER 2030, and precisely the deliverable D2.1, "Map of Railway Needs in 2030," is a cornerstone of the LEADER 2030 Exploratory Research Project under the EU-RAIL MAWP 2022. This document provides essential intelligence to support the implementation of all Flagship Projects within the EU-Rail initiative, aligning with the strategic objectives outlined in the ERJU Master Plan and Multi-Annual Work Program.

Objective and Scope

The primary objective of D2.1 is to comprehensively map railway innovations expected by 2030, identifying necessary technologies, raw materials, and supply chain requirements across various tiers (OEM, Tier 1, 2, 3). The study integrates findings from Deliverable D1.3, "Supply Alerts for the Future," to assess potential disruptions and their impact on EU-RAIL innovations. Additionally, the report highlights subsystems and components that will become obsolete or significantly reduced due to technological advancements, signaling key areas of industry transformation.

WP2 is instrumental in ensuring that Europe's rail ecosystem remains resilient, sustainable, and competitive. Through a structured analysis of the Flagship Areas (FAs) and their respective Flagship Projects (FPs), WP2 provides insights into how OEMs and suppliers must adapt to evolving digitalization, automation, and green energy trends. These shifts necessitate greater standardization, interoperability, and a strategic move toward sustainable material sourcing, ensuring the railway industry is future-ready.

Key Innovations and Technologies

WP2 identifies several transformative innovations essential for the future of European rail:

- **Network Management & Mobility (FP1 - MOTIONAL):** Advanced traffic management systems, real-time data analytics, and digital platforms enhance operational efficiency and network capacity.
- **Digital & Autonomous Train Operations (FP2 - R2DATO):** Automatic Train Operation (ATO), AI-driven control systems, and advanced sensor technologies improve safety, reliability, and cost efficiency.
- **Intelligent & Integrated Asset Management (FP3 - IAM4RAIL):** Predictive maintenance systems, Digital-Twins, and IoT-based sensors optimize asset lifecycle and reduce maintenance costs.
- **Sustainable & Green Rail Systems (FP4 - RAIL4EARTH):** Energy-efficient propulsion, sustainable materials, and emissions reduction technologies drive sustainability efforts.
- **Competitive Digital Green Rail Freight (FP5 - TRANS4M-R):** Digital Automatic Couplers (DAC), intelligent freight systems, and smart grid integration enhance efficiency and sustainability for seamless rail freight.
- **Regional & Capillary Rail Services (FP6 - FUTURE):** Modular vehicles, cost-efficient infrastructure, and customer-centric digital services improve accessibility and affordability.

- **New Approaches for Guided Transport (FP7 - Pods4Rail):** Automated multimodal transport systems and ultra-high-speed trains introduce innovative mobility solutions.

WP2 underscores the needed increasing role of SMEs in emerging areas such as cybersecurity, AI-driven automation, and modular rolling stock. The mapping exercise identifies key raw materials, including metals and rare earth elements, crucial for these innovations. Additionally, it assesses supply chain resilience and alternative sourcing strategies to mitigate risks associated with material dependencies and geopolitical uncertainties.

Obsolescence, Disruptions, and Criticalities in the Rail Supply Chain

The shift towards digital, automated, and sustainable rail systems under EU-RAIL will phase out legacy components while increasing reliance on critical raw materials (including the Heavy Rare Earth Elements -HREE- and Light Rare Earth Elements -LREE-).

- **Obsolescence & Disruptions**

By 2030, manual coupling, non-digital signaling, condition monitoring, diesel propulsion, and conventional HVAC should be largely replaced by Digital Automatic Couplers (DAC), AI-driven systems, electrification, and energy-efficient technologies. However, supply chain risks—such as semiconductor shortages, rare earth dependencies, and cybersecurity vulnerabilities—could also slow deployment.

- **Critical Raw Materials & Risks**

The rail sector will increasingly depend on materials like Gallium (Ga, Neodymium (Nd) and Dysprosium (Dy) for high-efficiency communication, lithium (Li) for batteries, and silicon (Si) for AI-driven automation. Copper and Steel needs increasing as well across the technology innovation of the flagship project.

While the LEADER 2030 roadmap extends to 2030, consultation interviews advocate for an increased use of Commercial-Off-The-Shelf (COTS) products. As a result, some criticalities *may be perceived* by the consulted stakeholders as moderate or low by 2030, also because only part of EU-RAIL innovations will reach the market by then. The truth is that not everything can be COTS, both *by* and *beyond* 2030, and criticalities will remain strategically important, as shown by the increased effort of the European Commission in ensuring Europe's Strategic Autonomy – which can prove a harder goal with the current evolution of geopolitics. Therefore, **ensuring long-term supply chain resilience, industrial autonomy, and adaptability to future technological shifts remains a priority for Europe's rail ecosystem.**

2. Abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation / Acronym	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
Automatic Train Operation (ATO)	Automatic Train Operation: A technology used to automate the operation of trains.
Autonomous Train	A train moving with the help of an ATO system which provides more or less automatic driving according to the highest level of automation (GoA4), and thus running unattended.
Automatic Train Protection (ATP)	A train operated autonomously to the extent that it has no drivers on-board.
DAC	Digital Automatic Coupling
Driverless	A train operated autonomously to the extent that it has no drivers on-board.
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
EU-RAIL / ERJU	Europe's Rail Joint Undertaking
European Rail Traffic Management System (ERTMS)	The system of standards for management and interoperation of signalling for railways by the European Union.
European Train Control System (ETCS)	The signalling and control component of the ERTMS. It is a replacement for legacy train protection systems and designed to replace the many incompatible safety systems currently used by European railways.
FA	Flagship Area
FP	Flagship Project
FRMCS	Future Railway Mobile Communication System
Grade of Automation (GoA)	The degree of automation applied for a given train or network. The grade goes from GoA1 up to GoA4 in which the train is automatically controlled without any staff on board.
GSM-R	Global System for Mobile Communications - Railway
IoT	Internet of Things
LEADER 2030	"Learning for European Autonomy to Deliver Europe's Rail in 2030"
LiDAR	Light Detection And Ranging
LRR	Long-Range Radar
ML	Machine Learning
Mobility-as-a-Service (Maas)	Mobility as a Service, is a transportation model that integrates various modes of transportation, such as public transit, ride-hailing, car-sharing, and bike-sharing,

	into a single service. It aims to provide travellers with convenient and cost-effective mobility options, enabled by technology platforms and data analytics, that can be accessed and paid for through a single digital interface. MaaS seeks to enhance the efficiency and sustainability of transportation systems while improving the travel experience for users.
Modal share	The share of people (%) – or mass in freight - using a particular mode of transport within the overall transport usage.
Modal shift	A change between modes to usually encompass an increase in the proportion of trips made using sustainable modes.
ODS	Obstacle Detection System
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
Railway Undertaking (RU)	A public or private undertaking licensed according to this Directive, the principal business of which is to provide services for the transport of goods and/or passengers by rail with a requirement that the undertaking ensure traction; this also includes undertakings that provide traction only
SaaS	Software As A Service
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
SRR	Short-Range Radar
TCO	Total Cost of Ownership
Trans-European Transport Network (TEN-T)	The TEN-T is a planned network of roads, railways, airports and water infrastructure in the European Union. The TEN-T network is part of a wider system of Trans-European Networks (TENs), including a telecommunications network (eTEN) and a proposed energy network (TEN-E or TEN-Energy).
TSI	Technical Specification for Interoperability
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
Unattended Train Operation (UTO)	A train operation where the starting and stopping of trains, as well as operation of train doors and handling of emergencies are fully automated without any regulatory requirement of staff present in the trains.
VR	Virtual Reality

3. Background

The present document constitutes the Deliverable D2.1 “Map of Railway needs in 2030” in the framework of the Exploratory Research Project LEADER 2030 as described in the EU-RAIL AWP 2022. Ultimately, it aims to contribute with intelligence information to the execution of all Flagship Projects.

4. Objective/Aim

The purpose of the “Map of Railway needs in 2030” is to summarise in a descriptive report, including synthesis matrixes, key information extracted from the Europe’s Rail Master Plan and Multi-Annual Work Programme.

Therefore, the LEADER 2030 project, through Work Package 2 “Map of Railway Needs for 2030”, aims to analyse the Flagship Areas and Projects outlined in the ERJU Master Plan and Multi-Annual Work Plan. This project is uniquely positioned as the only Europe’s Rail initiative addressing all flagship areas collectively, LEADER 2030 seeks to support and enlighten the EU Rail initiative’s efforts towards suppliers and specifically the Small and Medium Enterprises (SME). Its role is to guide and clarify pathways for transforming the European railway system into a sustainable, efficient, and digitally connected network by 2030.

The report here after will specifically define:

(needs part)

- The list of railway innovations to be introduced by 2030 in Europe through the EU-RAIL programme (detailed list of products and components)
- The technologies such innovations will require (including advanced raw materials), with specification of the relevant supply chain level involved (OEM, Tier 1, 2, 3)

(disruptions part)

- If the ‘supplies alerts for the future’ emerging from the Deliverable D1.3 “Supply alerts for the future” (i.e. specific supply disruptions already affecting the Rail Supply Industries with both state-of-the-art and innovative supplies) can harm also the innovations targeted by EU-RAIL
- The list of components/sub-components/solutions that won’t be necessary anymore or in a reduced/different way because of the introduction of the new innovations EU-RAIL is targeting, as this will represent a cause of disruption for the relevant suppliers.

5. ERJU Technological Innovations

Here the objectives are to:

1. Analyse the ERJU Master Plan and Multi-Annual Work Programme
2. Extract, Flagship Area by Flagship Area, the intelligence from the ERJU Master Plan and Multi-Annual Work Programme that will enhance Flagship Projects
3. Map, for each Flagship Project, the products/components (physical/immaterial) representing the results of innovation activities to 2030
4. Assess if new needs include state-of-the-art needs already subject to past/ongoing disruptions
5. Map components/sub-components that will become obsolete or minimally necessary due to railway transformation targeted for 2030
6. Identify the technology implementation timing and the foreseen criticalities (Column P & R)
7. Provide recommendations to suppliers, with special attention to SMEs.

5.1. Analysis of the ERJU Master Plan and Multi-Annual Work Programme

The ERJU (European Rail Joint Undertaking) Master Plan is quite expansive, it is encompassing operational, environmental, and strategic goals for a resilient, competitive, and sustainable rail system. When it comes to the ERJU Multi-Annual Work Programme (MAWP), it outlines a strategic framework over multiple years to achieve the objectives of ERJU. Its focus is on scaling innovations that support high interoperability standards, improved service quality, reduced costs, and sustainability. This plan includes steps to meet evolving customer needs, boost industry competitiveness, integrate green technology, and ensure resilience to climate impacts, driving forward the EU's policy goals for a greener and more connected rail system. The MAWP aims to transform the railway sector by 2030 through various innovative initiatives. The key focus areas include enhancing digital and automated train operations, improving energy efficiency, integrating advanced materials, and fostering multimodal transport solutions for a unified operational framework.

5.2. Intelligence from the ERJU Master Plan and Multi-Annual Work Programme to Enhance Flagship Projects

The ERJU MAWP outlines several key Flagship Areas crucial to advancing the European railway system's innovation, efficiency, and sustainability. These flagship areas are designed to support the Single European Railway Area (SERA)'s objectives and align with broader European Union policy goals, such as the European Green Deal and the Digital Decade initiative. Below are the primary Flagship Areas identified, along with their objectives and potential impacts. Currently, seven flagship areas have been identified, each of which generates a corresponding flagship project. The following sections provide a detailed analysis of each area, drawing insights from ERJU and ERJU MAWP analyses. For each flagship area, we outline the relevant technologies, as well as the associated functionalities and sub-functionalities necessary to meet the railway

sector's 2030 objectives.

5.2.1. Flagship Area 1: Network Management Planning and Control & Mobility Management in a Multimodal Environment

The Flagship Area 1 (FA1) concerns 'Network Management, Planning, and Control & Mobility' and its respective **Flagship Project 1** (FP1) is named '**MOTIONAL - Mobility Management in a Multimodal Environment and Digital Enablers**'.

Before diving into the FP1 primary objective, here are -according to the ERJU Multi-Annual Work Program (MAWP), *chapter 7.1.2.1. Operational solutions outcome* - the main expected outcomes for the Flagship Area 1 are:

- **Improving strategic and tactical planning of the rail network**
- **Increasing the resilience of a connected 'real time' rail network**
- **Integrated rail traffic within door-to-door mobility.**

Consequently, the primary **objective** of Flagship Project 1 is to enhance railway network planning and control while integrating mobility management across multiple modes of transport. This aims to create a more efficient, adaptable, and interoperable railway system by leveraging advanced digital solutions.

Therefore, among the **key innovations** driven by this Flagship Project is the European Rail Traffic Management System (ERTMS) and the **ERTMS Level 3** has been identified as the core technology to achieve the 2030 future rail objectives. Lower ERTMS levels could have been analysed and detailed, still, the ERTMS Level 3 represents the most advanced standard for digital rail traffic management, providing a transformative approach to network control, capacity planning, and intermodal integration.

Therefore we focused in this analysis on providing the **functionalities** and **sub-functionalities** enabled by ERTMS Level 3. These are described in the chapter 5.2.3.1.

5.2.2. Flagship Area 2: Digital & Automated up to Autonomous Train Operations

The Flagship Area 2 (FA2) concerns ‘Digital & Automated up to Autonomous Train Operations’ and its corresponding **Flagship Project 2** (FP2) is named “**R2DATO - Rail to Digital Automated up to Autonomous Train Operation**”.

Before diving into the FP2 primary objective, here are -according to the ERJU Multi-Annual Work Program (MAWP), *chapter 7.2.2.1. Operational solutions outcome* - the main expected outcomes for the Flagship Area 2 are:

- **Next-generation ATC**
 - automated train preparation
 - automatic stabling
 - automatic maintenance inspection, and remote control
 - Automatic Train Protection (ATP)
 - Automatic Train Operation (ATO)
 - migration strategies
 - rail optimisation techniques

Consequently, the primary **objective** of Flagship Project 2 is to develop and implement technologies for digital, automated, and fully autonomous train operations.

This objective involves development of **key innovations** around the advanced **Automatic Train Control (ATC)**. Therefore, Flagship Project 2 encompasses Automatic Train Protection (ATP), Automatic Train Supervision (ATS), and Automatic Train Operations (ATO) integrated with ERTMS/ETCS standards for hybrid-level autonomy (HL3) and Level 3 (L3) moving block operations. The ERTMS Level 3 and enhanced ATC functionalities, are supported by cutting-edge communication technologies like 5G, FRMCS, and Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X), to serve as the core technological foundation for this initiative.

With more details, the **functionalities and sub-functionalities** enabled by ERTMS Level 3 and ATC are described in the chapter 5.2.3.2.

5.2.3. Flagship Area 3: Intelligent & Integrated Asset Management

The Flagship Area 3 (FA3), titled *Intelligent & Integrated Asset Management*, sees its initiative embodied in the **Flagship Project 3 (FP3) - IAM4RAIL - A Holistic and Integrated Asset Management for Europe's Rail System**

Before diving into the FP3 primary objective, here are -according to the ERJU Multi-Annual Work Program (MAWP), *chapter 7.3.2.1. Operational solutions outcome* - the main expected outcomes for the Flagship Area 3 are:

- **Information sharing across the supply chain and TMS**
- **Unmanned and non-invasive monitoring and inspections**
- **Advanced and holistic asset decisions**
- **Advanced and holistic design and certification of assets**
- **Remotely controlled and unmanned interventions.**

Consequently, the primary **objective** of Flagship Project 3 is to advance comprehensive asset management systems that optimize the lifecycle, reliability, and performance of railway assets.

The **key innovation** supporting this objective is the **Integrated Asset Management System (IAMS)**, which applies to both rail infrastructure and rolling stock. IAMS is designed to enhance maintenance efficiency and manage lifecycle costs effectively through predictive and condition-based monitoring. All these innovations will focus on reducing lifecycle costs and enhancing overall system efficiency through data-driven insights and innovative maintenance strategies. By implementing these intelligent asset management solutions, the project aims to promote sustainable and cost-effective operations within Europe's railway networks.

This Integrated Asset Management System technology introduces advanced **functionalities and sub-functionalities**, described in the chapter 5.2.3.3. and where IoT-based infrastructure sensors, are essential.

5.2.4. Flagship Area 4: A Sustainable and Green Rail System

The Flagship Area 4 (FA4), “A Sustainable and Green Rail System” focuses on driving environmentally friendly and energy-efficient innovations within the European railway sector. The **Flagship Project** under this area, is FP4 “**RAIL4EARTH - Sustainable and Green Rail Systems**”.

Before diving into the FP4 primary objective, here are -according to the ERJU Multi-Annual Work Program (MAWP), *chapter 7.4.2.1. Operational solutions outcome* - the main expected outcomes for the Flagship Area 4 are:

- **Energy management**
 - Integrated and standardised Rail Power Smart Grid (incl. greener energies, control and management of peak of energy consumption).
 - Better energy management at station level (including energy flexibility and resilience of the Electrical Smart Grid).
- **Circularity and resilience**
 - Technologies oriented towards the whole life cycle of the assets and supported by Digital Twin developments.
 - Sector (i.e. infrastructure, rolling stock and buildings) tools or platform for the efficient implementation of circular economy solutions.
 - Guidelines for the design of modular stations (including size and uses).
- **Healthier, safer and more attractive railway system**
 - HVAC at the vehicle level.
 - Passenger flow management integrating variable health and safety measures (including non-toxic materials to fight against the dissemination of pathogens).
 - Industrial standards (design, analyses methods...) for easing the quick adaptation of interiors, supporting a big increase of integration of the secondary raw materials and bio-sourced materials.

Consequently, the primary **objective** of Flagship Project 4 is to significantly reduce the environmental impact of rail operations and infrastructure, thus centred on **Energy Saving & Green Technologies** to promote sustainable and green technologies that enhance energy efficiency, reduce environmental impact, and improve resource use across the rail network. This objective is critical to achieving climate goals, promoting energy independence, and supporting an eco-friendly transport network by 2030.

To achieve these outcomes, Flagship Project 4 encompasses a variety of innovative **technologies** across several **functionalities and sub-functionalities** that are described in the chapter 5.2.3.4.

5.2.5. Flagship Area 5: Sustainable Competitive Digital Green Rail Freight Services

For the Flagship Area 5 (FA5) “Sustainable Competitive Digital Green Rail Freight Services”, the **Flagship Project 5 (FP5)** is titled “**TRANS4M-R - Transforming Europe's Rail Freight**”.

Before diving into the FP5 primary objective, here are -according to the ERJU Multi-Annual Work Program (MAWP), *chapter 7.5.2.1. Operational solutions outcome* - the main expected outcomes for the Flagship Area 5 are:

- **Full Digital Freight Train Operation**
 - Operations for e.g. automated coupling/uncoupling of locos and freight wagons, data/energy system, electronically controlled brake system, train integrity, increased speed via braking performance, automated technical wagon inspection, etc.
 - Freight for e.g., wagons/loading units for multi-modal transport applications.
 - Telematics for monitoring solutions.
 - Yard automation and digitalization.
- **Seamless rail freight**
 - Seamless planning, for e.g. aligned and eased planning of rail freight services via integrated cross-border timetable planning, integrated/connected slot planning and booking functionalities for last mile services.
 - Seamless operations, as dynamic dispatching tools, increased accuracy of predictions (e.g. ETA), standardized European Railway Checkpoints at border crossings, innovative, smart and harmonized process for technical wagon inspections, multi country licensed loco driver, etc.
 - Seamless Management/Selling/Booking thanks to multimodal integration with easy access to (intermodal) rail service, fully digital European customer solutions (services, interfaces for both freight and passenger operations), and seamless & harmonized data exchange of railway checkpoints for smooth European rail freight operation.

Consequently, the primary **objective** of Flagship Project 5 is to enhance the competitiveness and sustainability of rail freight services through digitalization and green technologies.

This project focuses on the **key innovation** of an **Intelligent Train System**, which incorporates advanced functionalities like **Digital Automatic Couplers (DAC)**, including its seamless rail freight part, to enhance the efficiency, sustainability, and competitiveness of rail freight services across Europe.

The primary **functionalities and sub-functionalities** introduced by this key technology are described in this report's chapter 5.2.3.5.

5.2.6. Flagship Area 6: Regional Rail Services/Innovative Rail Services to Revitalize Capillary Lines

For the Flagship Area 6 (FA6) the scope of work is relative to 'Regional Rail Services / Innovative Rail Services to Revitalize Capillary Lines'. The corresponding **Flagship Project 6** (FP6) is named "**FUTURE - Delivering Innovative Rail Services to Revitalize Capillary Lines and Regional Rail Services**".

Before diving into the FP6 primary objective, here are -according to the ERJU Multi-Annual Work Program (MAWP), *chapter 7.6.2.1. Operational solutions outcome* - the main and almost unique expected outcome for the Flagship Area 6 is to reach a:

- **Low-cost technical and operational framework** for low density lines to reduce the cost per kilometre both in terms of CAPEX and OPEX while increasing customer satisfaction as a European solution. That will include:
 - cost efficient components (e.g. wireless and energy self-sufficient infrastructure components)
 - modular railway stations
 - regional lines' tailored zero-emission vehicle concept for passenger and freight (light rail train).

Consequently, the primary **objective** of Flagship Project 6 is to rejuvenate regional rail services and capillary lines by adopting cutting-edge technologies and strategies, aiming to increase accessibility, operational efficiency, and sustainability in regional and rural areas.

This project leverages the **key innovations** and technologies developed in previous flagship areas (1 to 5), with the exception of Digital Automatic Coupler (DAC) as it is freight-specific and therefore not applicable to passenger capillary lines.

The **functions** and **sub-functions** drawn from previous flagship areas and are fully described in this report's chapter 5.2.3.6.

5.2.7. Flagship Area 7: Innovation on New Approaches for Guided Transport Modes

For the Flagship Area 7 (FA7) the scope of work is relative to 'Innovation on new approaches for guided transport modes. The corresponding **Flagship Project 7** (FP7) is titled "**PODS4RAIL**".

Before diving into the FP7 primary objective, here are -according to the ERJU Multi-Annual Work Program (MAWP), *chapter 7.7.2.1. Operational solutions outcome* - the Flagship Area 7 has the particularity that the "general assertion about the operational solutions outcome cannot be made". Still, the innovations developed should concern solutions for:

- **more flexibility through multi-modality**
- **energy-efficient high-speed rail systems**
- **guided systems**

Consequently, the primary **objective** of Flagship Project 7 explores and develops new, flexible, and high-speed guided transport systems. The project's main **objective** is to develop the next generation of railway transport systems as well as guided transport systems based on a fully automated multi-modal mobility system for passengers and goods which is sustainable, interconnected, digital, on-demand, standardised, scalable and suitable for all transport modes."

For this project the **key innovations** need to fulfil the requirement of being an **Open Platform, based on common standards and standardised interfaces, connecting all the transport modes, and be able to provide disruptive Operation and Business Models.**

Therefore, the technologies developed in previous flagship areas (i.e. from 1 to 6) and this time including the Digital Automatic Coupler (DAC), are considered as the starting point of this flagship project. Technologies such as Automated multi-modal mobility systems (e.g., Pods for passenger and freight transport), Ultra-high-speed train systems or Sustainable propulsion technologies (e.g., maglev, vacuum tube technologies) will also be studied in the frame of the **functions and sub-functions** drawn from previous flagships and detailed in this report chapter 5.2.3.7.

5.2.8. Impact and Integration with EU-Rail Initiative

The Flagship Areas collectively aim to transform the European railway system, aligning it with the EU's broader goals of decarbonization, digitalization, and increased resilience. The innovations and solutions developed within these flagship areas will not only enhance the operational efficiency and sustainability of rail transport but also position the European rail industry as a global leader in railway innovation.

These initiatives seek to position Europe as a global leader in railway innovation by leveraging - among others- **advanced technologies such as digital twins, AI-based control systems**, and sustainable propulsion methods like **hydrogen** and **hybrid propulsion**. The flagship areas work toward a **seamless, interoperable rail network** with a **focus on digital automation, integrated asset management, sustainable energy solutions**, and **enhanced passenger services**.

By integrating advanced technologies, the EU-RAIL initiative aims to significantly reduce operational costs, enhance service reliability, and minimize the environmental footprint of rail transport. The focus on multimodal integration and customer-centric innovations ensures rail remains a competitive and attractive mode of transportation for the future. Flagship projects, through advancements in predictive maintenance, traffic management, and multimodal connectivity, reinforce these objectives by driving efficiency, reliability, and sustainability. Moreover, prioritizing customer-focused services and seamless connectivity aligns the rail sector with Europe's evolving societal and mobility needs.

In conclusion, these combined efforts not only support the EU's ambition for a modernized, resilient railway infrastructure but also contributes to solidify the rail value chain up to the smallest supplier contributing to secure the EU Rail as a core component of green, efficient mobility, fully aligned with Europe's decarbonization goals.

5.3. Mapping Innovation Products/Components to 2030

Following the comprehensive analysis of the ERJU flagship areas and the ERJU Multi-Annual Work Plan (MAWP) respective flagship projects in the previous chapter (5.1), this chapter will delve into the specific products and components emerging from each flagship project.

This chapter provides a detailed mapping of innovative solutions, highlighting how each Flagship Project contributes with distinct technological advancements aimed at achieving the 2030 objectives for European rail.

5.3.1. High-Level Expectation

The high-level expectation for LEADER 2030 Work Package 2 “Map of Rail Needs in 2030” is to create a comprehensive, forward-looking inventory of innovation products and components essential for transforming Europe’s rail industry by 2030. This mapping aims to identify not only the key technological advancements but also the specific components and raw materials required to implement these innovations effectively. By doing so, WP2 will provide a strategic foundation to address future sourcing challenges, anticipate critical material demands, and guide investment in sustainable and resilient supply chains. Ultimately, this mapping is intended to ensure that Europe’s rail sector can meet ambitious modernization and decarbonization goals in alignment with LEADER 2030 objectives.

To achieve these objectives, the analysis employs a structured methodology rooted in specific hypotheses and organized into key steps. The "Modalities to Reach It" section details this approach, including the sequential analysis of each flagship project, focus on primary innovations, component extraction, material identification, and a forward-looking assessment of technology implementation and sourcing impact by 2030. This systematic approach ensures a robust and actionable evaluation aligned with LEADER 2030's strategic goals.

5.3.2. Modalities to Reach 2030 Innovation Mapping

To analyse the innovations outlined in the European Rail Joint Undertaking (ERJU) Master Plan and the ERJU Multi-Annual Work Plan (MAWP) in relation to the LEADER 2030 initiative, a structured methodology was applied, supported by specific hypotheses. This approach aimed to systematically break down each flagship project (FP) to reveal core innovations, enabling a comprehensive understanding of future technological requirements. Below is an expanded explanation of the methodology and hypotheses that guided the creation of the analysis and resulting data tables.

Methodology

Sequential Analysis by Flagship Project

The methodology began with a sequential analysis of each Flagship Project (FP). By examining each FP individually, we ensured that any cross-flagship innovations or interdependencies could be clearly identified in later stages. This methodical approach allowed for a focused examination of each FP's unique innovations, products, components, and material needs, facilitating easier identification of potential overlaps and common technologies across FPs.

Desk Research and Focus Group Interviews

Initially, desk research was conducted to analyse the ERJU Master Plan and MAWP, identifying key innovations within each FP. However, to verify and expand upon this information, focus group interviews were conducted with industry experts. These interviews allowed for validation of the desk research findings, while providing additional insights and real-world perspectives.

The desk research and interview findings were then consolidated into comprehensive tables, one for each flagship area (FA) and corresponding flagship project (FP). There is one Table per Flagship, and all Tables are attached to this report.

Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: Focus on the Main Innovation per Flagship Project

The primary hypothesis was to identify and thus focus the main innovation for each FP rather than creating an exhaustive list of all possibly existing innovations and in fact that have been already identified and listed in the ERJU Multi Annual Work Program. This focus allowed for a detailed analysis of the core innovation, examining its functionalities and sub-functionalities to define the essential hardware and software requirements. From this, we identified necessary components and, ultimately, the raw materials—particularly rare earth elements—that would be crucial for achieving these innovations. This hypothesis enabled us to concentrate on the most impactful elements of each FP, optimizing the analysis for clarity and relevance.

Hypothesis 2: Selection of the Latest Stage of Technology for Analysis

Railway technologies often progress incrementally, with different regions or countries adopting innovations at varying stages.

For instance, the European Rail Traffic Management System (ERTMS) began in the early 1990s, initiated by the EU to standardize signalling systems across Europe. Key developments included the 1996 EU directive on rail interoperability and the release of initial specifications in 1999, defining ETCS (European Train Control System) and GSM-R (a dedicated rail communication system). ERTMS operates on three levels, each with increasing technological sophistication and capabilities:

- **Level 1:** Uses trackside equipment to communicate with trains via GSM-R. It overlays existing signalling systems, allowing gradual upgrades.
- **Level 2:** Introduces continuous communication between trains and control centres via GSM-R, eliminating the need for trackside signals, which increases safety and efficiency.
- **Level 3:** (Currently in development) Moves towards a fully automated system with real-time train location updates, further increasing capacity and flexibility by eliminating fixed blocks.

Today, ERTMS deployment varies across Europe, with Level 2 commonly adopted on high-speed lines, while Level 3 is still largely conceptual as the European Union aims to install ERTMS across the TEN-T network by 2030 (core network) and by 2040 (extended and comprehensive networks), as per the latest ERTMS European Deployment Plan (EDP).

Given this staggered implementation, we hypothesised that the latest stage of each FP's innovation would most accurately reflect the technological and material demands expected by 2030. This assumption allowed us to model the requirements based on the most advanced and resource-intensive iteration of each technology.

Hypothesis 3: Emphasis on Hardware over Software

The focus of this analysis was on hardware requirements, as software needs are addressed by other EU initiatives and projects outside the scope of LEADER 2030. While software was acknowledged as an integral component, the analysis centred on the tangible, physical products and materials required to support each FP's core hardware components. Consequently, software was documented for reference, but detailed requirements were not analysed in depth, except when it came to the supportive structure (tangible) to the software.

Hypothesis 4: Focus on Rare Earth Elements (REEs) in Raw Material Extraction

To determine the necessary raw materials, each innovation's functionalities and sub-functionalities were broken down into sub-assemblies. From these subassemblies, the hardware and software components were identified, focusing particularly on rare earth elements (REEs) critical for advanced technologies. Given the increasing importance of REEs in high-tech applications—especially in hardware for automation, communication, and energy-efficient designs—our analysis prioritized identifying the specific rare earth elements (Heavy REE and Light REE) essential to each FP. This hypothesis was critical to understanding the evolving resource demands and ensuring alignment with sustainability goals.

Steps in Analysis

- 1. Identify Innovations:** Each FP's main innovation (and its more advanced version when the case) was identified based on ERJU documentation and industry inputs.
- 2. Break Down Functionalities** For each main innovation, core functionalities and sub functionalities were outlined.
- 3. Detail Products and Components:** From the identified functionalities, relevant products were broken down into sub-assemblies and their respective hardware and software components, isolating hardware for further analysis.
- 4. Extract Raw Materials:** Components were mapped to their required raw materials, focusing on rare earth elements crucial for advanced rail technologies.
- 5. Categorize Needs and Potentially Obsolete Components:** Each FP was analysed for new material requirements compared to previous technologies, as well as components likely to become obsolete.
- 6. Likelihood of Technology Implementation by 2030:** Assessed the probability of each innovation reaching operational status by 2030 based on its projected Technology Readiness Level (TRL), as detailed in ERJU MAWP.
- 7. Criticality of Raw Material Demand on the Sourcing Chain by 2030:** Analysed the criticality of raw materials based on demand trends and the likelihood of related innovations being implemented, identifying potential supply chain risks by 2030.

This comprehensive approach not only mapped the material and technological needs essential to LEADER 2030 objectives but also introduced a forward-looking analysis. By linking technology readiness with material demand, the methodology highlighted critical areas of impact on the sourcing chain. Altogether, this structured approach provided a thorough, actionable framework aligned with LEADER 2030's strategic goals.

5.3.3. Key Innovations and components by Flagship Project

Based on the previously described methodology and followed steps, we came with a final output in a series of tables detailing the innovations focusing on the key one, product requirements, and raw materials for each FA and respective FP. For a fully detailed view by technologies, functionalities, respective subassemblies, components and concerned raw materials, the ideal is to refer directly to the excel table (in annex) for each of the concerned FA and respective FP.

In the following, the key innovations and components are detailed to a certain extent in order to highlight the hardware raw materials required for the rail innovations expected for 2030.

5.3.3.1. Flagship Project 1: MOTIONAL - Mobility management multimodal environment and digital enablers

The **MOTIONAL FP** emphasizes on optimizing multimodal rail mobility management by enhancing **real-time monitoring, network control, and secure data exchange**. The components are structured to improve traffic capacity, ensure security, and enable reliable digital communication.

This innovation structure proposed here below for **FP1** captures the primary **innovations** (functionalities and sub-functionalities) **and hardware components** (based on the sub-assemblies identified) required to achieve high-level traffic control, network security, and secure mobility. The software elements are essential complements to hardware innovations, enabling real-time adjustments, position accuracy, and cybersecurity protocols that align with the objectives of **MOTIONAL**, still the focus here is on the hardware and their related raw materials.

Traffic Management, Capacity Planning and Mobility Orchestration (the 1st main functionalities on FA1 excel sheet – column G)

Here the functionality that is looked for is the **Capacity Planning and Train Detection**. This functionality is integral to maintaining accurate train positioning, enhancing scheduling efficiency, and maximizing rail network capacity. Capacity planning relies on real-time train detection for optimal traffic management and punctuality. Therefore to achieve it we need to have the following sub-functionalities and sub-assemblies:

- **Train Detection for Precise Positioning**, as it focuses on continuous, accurate location monitoring for each train. This ensures trains are positioned precisely within the network, allowing for real-time adjustments and minimized disruptions through reduced infrastructure costs and enhanced operational flexibility.

Here, the **subassemblies** are:

- The **GNSS (Global Navigation Satellite System)** as it incorporates satellite signal devices to provide reliable, high-precision positioning, critical for safety and traffic flow optimization. GNSS also facilitates interoperability across regional networks.

- **Inertial Measurement Units (IMU)** complements GNSS by tracking position and motion, especially useful in GPS-limited areas, ensuring uninterrupted accuracy in train location.

Here, the **Key Hardware Components** are:

- The **Satellite Signal Devices**, as high-precision GNSS devices (e.g. Trimble BD990), are equipped for robust location tracking and essential for safe, coordinated train operations.
- **IMU Sensors** (e.g. Honeywell HG4930) support accurate movement tracking by measuring orientation and acceleration, supplementing GNSS data to maintain real-time positioning.

Here, the **main Raw Materials** are:

- Metals like **Copper (Cu)** and **Gold (Au)** for connectors and signal transmission due to their excellent conductivity and durability.
- Semiconductors based on **Gallium Arsenide (GaAs)**, commonly used in GNSS systems, as it enhances sensor sensitivity and performance.

Here, the **Key Software** part concerns the **Positioning and Fusion Algorithms**. These algorithms process data from GNSS and IMU sensors, merging it to create a comprehensive and highly accurate positional feed that adapts as trains move through diverse terrains.

Beyond Train Detection functionalities -as detailed above- with concerned products, components and raw material, we could also mention the below functionalities for FA1:

- **Train Integrity Monitoring:** to enable continuous monitoring and reporting to confirm that all parts of a train remain intact, enhancing safety and reliability.
- **Moving Block Signalling:** to allow for dynamic, real-time adjustments of separation distances between trains, improving network capacity and operational efficiency.
- **Automatic Train Protection (ATP):** to ensure safe operations by enforcing speed limits and activating automatic braking when necessary, thus enhancing safety.

All of their concerned products, components and raw material are detailed in the FA1 excel sheet in the Annex.

Network and Real-Time Traffic Management (the 2nd main functionalities on FA1 excel sheet – column G)

Here the functionality that is looked for is the **Real-Time Network Control** the flow generated is vital for maintaining efficient and safe traffic across the rail system. This functionality leverages advanced data analytics to detect network demands and adaptively manage train schedules, reducing delays and maximizing track usage. One of the key sub-functionality is the **Enhanced Network Flow and Control** that utilizes real-time data exchange. This functionality manages operational dynamics, adjusting train movement and capacity to meet demand changes quickly.

Here, the **Subassemblies** are:

- The **Radio Block Centre (RBC)**, to manage train movements by providing movement authorizations and ensuring safe separation between trains. RBC facilitates the scalability of Traffic Management Systems (TMS) across a wider network.
- The **Data Communication and Networking**, ensure reliable data transmission for real-time control and management, crucial for maintaining punctuality, forecasting capacity

accurately, and dynamically responding to network demand. These systems include Data Communication Modules that enable seamless data exchange across the network, facilitating real-time communication between control centres and trains to maintain synchronized operations and enhance overall efficiency.

Here, the **Key Hardware Components** are:

- The **High-Frequency Antennas** designed for rapid, high-data-rate communication essential for continuous, high-quality data exchange.

Here, the **main Raw Materials** are:

- Metals like **Copper (Cu)** in wiring. This supports high-quality signal transmission, ensuring reliability.
- Semiconductors based on **Silicon (Si)**, essential in communication modules for high-speed data processing.

Here the **Key Software** part concerns the **Real-Time Analytics Software**. This software monitors, analyses, and adjusts network traffic flow, optimizing traffic density and ensuring swift, adaptive responses to operational shifts.

Secure Overall Mobility (the 3rd main functionality on the FA1 excel sheet)

Here the functionality that is looked for is the **Security Management in Mobility Systems**. Indeed, security management within mobility systems is essential to prevent unauthorized access, ensure data privacy, and protect the integrity of rail network operations. This functionality is focused on securing data exchanges and protecting operational systems against cyber threats. Therefore the sub-functionality of **Data and System Security** is key in increasing digitalization environments making rail systems vulnerable to cybersecurity risks. Securing data exchanges and operational systems is crucial to maintaining both system integrity and public trust.

Here, the **subassemblies** are:

- The **Robust Cybersecurity Modules**, these are embedded within network infrastructure to detect and mitigate security threats in real-time, ensuring uninterrupted safe operations.

Here, the **Key Hardware Components** are:

- The **Firewalls and Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS)** as they protect network entry points, monitor network traffic, and respond to potential threats. Intrusion detection systems identify unauthorized activities, enhancing overall security.

Here, the **main Raw Materials** are:

- Metals like **Copper (Cu)** and **Aluminium (Al)** for wiring and shielding within security hardware.
- Semiconductors based on **Silicon (Si)** for processors that enable encryption, firewall management, and threat detection functions.

Here the **Key Software** part concerns the **Cybersecurity Protocols and Threat Detection Algorithms**. These algorithms monitor data flows, detect suspicious activities, and initiate defensive measures to safeguard sensitive operational data and maintain system integrity.

5.3.3.2. Flagship Project 2: R2DATO - Rail to Digital automated up to autonomous train operation

The **R2DATO FP** focuses on transitioning the rail system to higher levels of digital automation, enabling increasingly autonomous train operations. This requires **advanced systems for train control, intelligent automation, and seamless communication**. The components and innovations proposed here aim to ensure enhanced safety, reliability, and efficiency while preparing the rail system for full automation.

This innovation structure captures the primary functionalities and hardware components (based on the sub-assemblies identified) needed to achieve automation goals. This comprehensive breakdown highlights **R2DATO FP2's** focus on autonomous train operations, emphasizing **automation, intelligent decision-making, seamless connectivity, and safety**. As a reminder, while software is indispensable, this analysis stresses hardware requirements and their associated raw materials. As well, **R2DATO FP2** integrating parts of the **MOTIONAL FP1** such as Train detection, Train Integrity Monitoring, Moving Block Signalling or Advanced train Protection (ATP), we focus here on the new elements brought by this Flagship Project.

Advanced Signalling, Control and Automation (the 1st main functionality on the FA2 excel sheet)

Here the functionality that is looked for is the **Progressive Automation of Train Operations**. This functionality involves transitioning from driver-assisted systems to fully autonomous train operations. It supports increasing levels of automation, from supervised systems to fully automated (GoA 4). As a natural consequence, the **Automatic Train Supervision and Control** sub-functionality is required and this involves the use of *Automatic Train Supervision (ATS)* to enable efficient scheduling and routing while *Automatic Train Control (ATC)* systems ensure safe and accurate train movements. These systems are vital for reducing human error and improving operational efficiency. All these advanced functionalities are relying as well on **AI-Driven Train Optimization** since artificial intelligence enables trains to optimize their operations by learning from historical data and current conditions. This reduces energy consumption, improves scheduling, and enhances operational reliability. The derived sub-functionality is the **Predictive and Adaptive Automation**. Predictive models anticipate network conditions and adapt train operations dynamically, minimizing disruptions and improving punctuality

Here, the **subassemblies** are:

- The **Train Detection**, to ensure accurate train positioning without trackside equipment, a critical feature for precise and autonomous operations.
- The **Train Integrity Monitoring**, to provide continuous monitoring and integrity reporting to confirm that all parts of the train remain intact, improving safety and reliability.
- The **Moving Block Signalling**, to facilitate real-time dynamic adjustments for safe separation between trains, significantly boosting network capacity and operational efficiency.
- The **Automatic Train Protection (ATP)**, to enforce speed restrictions and automatic braking when necessary to maintain safe operations.

- The **Advanced Train Control and Monitoring Systems (TCMS)**, to enhance train performance and safety by optimizing on-board systems for efficient, predictive maintenance and improved automation.
- The **Autonomous Operations (ATO at GoA4)**, to allow fully autonomous train operations with precise control over speed, stopping, and departure. Advanced sensor technologies (such as LiDAR and radar) are a must here and these include the
 - The **AI Processing Units**, which represent advanced computing units embedded onboard to process real-time data and make automated decisions.
 - The **Machine Learning Modules**, that continuously improve train operation algorithms by analysing operational data.

Here, the **Key Hardware Components** are:

- The **Onboard Control Modules** to process real-time data for automated operation, integrating inputs from sensors and external systems.
- The **AI Chips and Accelerators** as they are high-performance processors designed for deep learning and real-time decision-making.
- The **Onboard Edge Computing Devices** to enable decentralized processing of data close to its source, reducing latency.

Here, the **main Raw Materials** are:

- Metals like **Copper (Cu)** for wiring and connections, **Steel (Fe)** for structural components in sensors and controllers, **Aluminium (Al)** for lightweight cooling enclosures.
- Semiconductors based on **Silicon (Si)** for microprocessors, essential in ATP systems and onboard modules, or semiconductors based **Advanced Silicon (Si)** for AI processors, Graphene for next-generation computing chips
- Plastics and Polymers like **Polycarbonate** for casing and insulation, protecting sensitive electronic components.

Here the **Key Software** part concerns the **ATS/ATC Algorithms and the AI-Based Optimization Models**. The algorithms monitor and control train movements, ensuring safe and efficient autonomous operations while the models are trained on historical data for adaptive scheduling and energy optimization.

Seamless Communication and Connectivity (among the 2nd main functionality on the FA2 excel sheet)

Here the functionality that is looked for is the **Continuous Train-to-Ground Communication** as Reliable communication systems are critical for real-time data exchange between trains and control centres. This ensures synchronized operations, improves safety, and supports automation. The resultant main sub-functionality is the **Next-Generation Communication Systems**. These future-ready systems like 5G and FRMCS (Future Railway Mobile Communication System) enable higher data rates and more reliable connections, supporting autonomous operations.

Here, the **subassemblies** are:

- The **5G and Future Railway Mobile Communication System (FRMCS)**, to enable real-time, high-speed communication across train and trackside systems, ensuring interoperability and responsive decision-making. Indeed, AI-driven control systems are essential here.

- The **Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) Communication**, to support wireless interaction between the train and external entities (e.g. cars, buses, trams, e-scooters, and more), enhancing situational awareness and supporting autonomous operations. AI-driven control systems are essential for maintaining the real-time responsiveness required to support informed and timely decision-making. These **Onboard Communication Modules** handle high-speed data transmission and reception, ensuring uninterrupted connectivity.

Here, the **Key Hardware Components** are:

- The **5G Antennas and Modems** as they deliver high-speed, low-latency communication critical for real-time operations.
- The **Signal Amplifiers** to enhance communication strength over long distances.

Here, the **main Raw Materials** are:

- Metals like **Copper (Cu)** and **Gold (Au)** for signal conductors and high-performance connectors.
- Semiconductors based on **Silicon (Si)** for modems and amplifiers.

Here the **Key Software** part concerns the **Communication Protocols and Signal Processing Algorithms** that enable reliable data transfer and ensure interoperability across diverse network infrastructures.

Secure Overall Cybersecurity (the 3rd main functionality on the FA2 excel sheet)

Here the functionality, that embraces the same needs as for FP 1, can be further detailed regarding the need to ensure **Operational Safety and Cyber Resilience**. Indeed, as automation increases, robust safety and cybersecurity measures are critical to protect both the physical and digital infrastructure of rail systems. Therefore the sub-functionality of **Cyber-Physical Security Systems**, these are integrated systems that protect against both physical risks and cyber threats, ensuring uninterrupted and safe operations.

Here, the **subassemblies** are:

- The **Firewall and Security Gateways** as these protect onboard and network systems from unauthorized access and cyberattacks.
- The **Redundant Safety Systems** to provide backup to maintain safety in case of system failures.

Here, the **Key Hardware Components** are:

- The **Secure Processing Units** to handle encryption, authentication, and threat detection in real-time.
- The **Safety Relays and Backup Modules** that ensure critical safety functions to remain operational even during failures.

Here, the **main Raw Materials** are:

- Metals like **Aluminium (Al)** and **Copper (Cu)** for wiring and shielding.
- Semiconductors based on **Silicon (Si)** for processors handling encryption and authentication.

Here the **Key Software** part concerns the **Cybersecurity Algorithms and Monitoring Systems Algorithms** for threat detection and real-time response, ensuring system integrity.

5.3.3.3. Flagship Project 3: IAM4RAIL - A Holistic and Integrated Asset Management for Europe's Rail System

The **IAM4RAIL** Flagship Project focuses on developing a unified approach to asset management, leveraging predictive analytics, automation, and smart infrastructure. Its key innovations aim to optimize the life cycle of rail assets, minimize costs, and improve operational efficiency. These innovations are critical for achieving a holistic, efficient, and predictive approach to asset management across Europe's rail systems, therefore they are happening around **Predictive Maintenance and Monitoring Systems**, the **Smart Infrastructure for Rail Systems**, the **Asset Life Cycle Optimization** and the **Enhanced Data Integration and Interoperability**. This framework ensures operational reliability, cost-effectiveness, and infrastructure longevity.

Advanced Asset Management for Infrastructure and Rolling Stock (The 1st main functionalities on FA3 excel sheet)

Here the functionalities on achieving full integration of operations and maintenance through systems such as the Train Management System (TMS) and Condition-Based Monitoring (CBM). These technologies aim to enhance the **Operational Efficiency** by leveraging data insights, enabling comprehensive **performance assessment** of rail systems and processes, and conducting **real-time monitoring of asset conditions**. This integrated approach ensures improved operational performance and resource efficiency.

Here, the **subassemblies** are:

- The **Operational Efficiency**, to improve the efficiency of rail operations by providing actionable insights derived from comprehensive data analytics. Real-time Data Collection devices from various sources including digital signalling units, sensors and communication networks
- The **Performance Analysis**, to evaluate the performance of rail systems and processes to identify areas for improvement.
- The **Condition-Based Monitoring (CBM)**, to monitor asset conditions in real time, enabling timely interventions based on asset health.

Here, the **Key Hardware Components** are:

- The **IoT sensors** to monitor real-time operations through devices integrated into the train and the infrastructure (e.g. trackside sensors, axle counters, etc).
- The **Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs - drones)** for long-range monitoring and mapping (e.g. the fixed-wing drone like eBee X from senseFly); or multicopter Drones (DJI Matrice 300 RTK) for close-up inspections and detailed surveys that measure operating temperatures to prevent overheating.
- The **Edge Devices** to monitor tunnels movements as for local data processing devices (e.g. NVIDIA Jetson Nano, Raspberry Pi 4, Intel NUC) that use Magnetic induced microwires before entering and in the tunnels

Here, the **main Raw Materials** are:

- Metals like **Copper (Cu)** for sensor wiring, connectors and heat dissipation needs, **Gold (Au)** for high-quality connectors, **Aluminium (Al)** for sensor housing.

- Semiconductors based on **Silicon (Si)** for IoT device chips and processors.

Here the **Key Software** part concerns the **Data Aggregation and Processing Software** to aggregate sensor data and perform integrity checks based on AI and ML.

Efficient Predictive Maintenance and Operations (the 2nd main functionalities on FA3 excel sheet)

Here the functionalities that are looked for are revolving around **Data-driven Decision Making**. The purpose here is to reach real-time condition monitoring and enhance asset reliability as well as to reduce unplanned maintenance. Therefore the sub-functionality is mainly articulated around the **Predictive Maintenance, Lifecycle Management, and Resource Optimization**

Here, the **subassemblies** are:

- The **Predictive Maintenance**, to anticipate equipment failures before they occur, reducing unplanned downtime and optimizing maintenance schedules, thus relying on Condition Monitoring for continuous monitoring of asset (e.g. for tunnels, crossing, bridges, etc.).
- The **Lifecycle Management**, to track the condition and performance of assets over time, facilitating strategic planning for asset renewal and replacement thanks to Maintenance Scheduling.
- The **Resource Optimization**, to ensure efficient allocation of maintenance resources and budget, minimizing operational costs through Inventory Management where spare parts and tools for maintenance activities are managed.

Here, the **Key Hardware Components** are:

- The **Sensors and IoT Devices** to monitor asset conditions like wear, temperature, and vibrations. For example, temperature sensors prevent overheating, while vibration sensors (e.g., Bosch MEMS) detect wear and abnormalities, enabling proactive maintenance and enhanced reliability.
- The **Communication Modules using fibre optics** (if not 4G/5G networks) to transmit data from sensors to central servers, and cloud servers, local storage devices for data storage.

Here, the **main Raw Materials** are:

- Metals like **Copper (Cu)** for sensor wiring, connectors and heat dissipation needs, **Gold (Au)** for high-quality connectors, **Aluminium (Al)** for sensor housing.
- Semiconductors based on **Silicon (Si)** for IoT device chips and processors.

Here the **Key Software** part concerns mainly the development of **AI algorithms** for general health monitoring, including anomaly detection for bogies and trainset components. Additionally, it involves integrating checkpoint data by fusing various inputs into a unified collection point for streamlined analysis and decision-making.

Real-Time Simulation and Monitoring with Digital Twins

Here the functionalities that are sought are relative to the enhancement of interoperability standards to ensure seamless operation across different railway systems and thus the need to use digital twin technology to reach a **real-time simulation** and **monitoring** of railway assets. The purpose is to achieve a continuous monitoring of tracks, bridges, and other critical infrastructure for safety and performance optimization thanks to **Predictive Analysis** and **Structural Health**

Monitoring (SHM). This integrated approach (rail and infrastructure) ensures improved operational performance and resource efficiency.

Here, the **subassemblies** are:

- The **Simulation**, to create virtual models of rail assets, enabling testing and analysis without impacting real-world operations. This would be possible thanks to the creation of detailed digital replicas of physical assets such as Station and track asset Management creation.
- The **Real-Time Monitoring**, to provide a live data feed from physical assets to their digital counterparts, allowing for immediate response to emerging issues.
- The **Predictive Analysis**, to use scenario-based analysis to predict the impact of different conditions on rail operations, supporting proactive decision-making.

Here, the **Key Hardware Components** are:

- **Smart Sensors** (e.g., HBM Strain Gauges) to provide real-time structural condition data.
- **IoT devices** (sensors and gateways) to monitor real-time operations through devices integrated into the train and the infrastructure (e.g. *Accelerometers* from STMicroelectronics -LIS3DSH- to monitor dynamic loads and vibrations)
- **Networking Hardware** (incl. Saas, PaaS, DaaS)
- **Edge Computing Devices** (incl. energy harvesting systems)

Here, the **main Raw Materials** are:

- Metals like **Copper (Cu)** for wiring, **Gold (Au)** for high-quality connectors, **Aluminium (Al)** for sensor housing, and **titanium (Ti)** for structural components where lightweight strength or corrosion resistance is crucial (ideal for extreme -dust and debris- or demanding environments like the one of rail as Electromagnetic Interference -EMI- can often happen).
- Semiconductors based on **Silicon (Si)** for sensor processing, and **Gallium Arsenide (GaAs)**

Here the **Key Software** part concerns the **SHM Data Visualization Platforms** to display real-time health metrics of infrastructure to operators using *Data Analytics Software, Simulation and Modelling Software, Cloud Computing Platforms* -incl. Saas, PaaS, DaaS-, *AI & ML Frameworks* and *Integration Platforms*.

Secure Overall Cybersecurity (the 4th main functionality on the FA3 excel sheet)

Here the functionality, that embraces the same needs as for FP 1 and FP2, can be further detailed regarding the need to ensure *Operational Safety* and all what is induced by it. Therefore the sub-functionalities (on top of the ones described on 5.2.3.1 for FP2 and 5.2.3.2 for FP2) are relative to **threat detection** and the management response to any incident.

Here, the **subassemblies** are (on top of the ones described on 5.2.3.1 for FA1 and 5.2.3.2 for FA2):

- The **Threat Detection**, to identify potential cybersecurity threats in real time, safeguarding critical infrastructure
- The **Risk Management**, to assess and mitigates cybersecurity risks to protect against disruptions.
- The **Incident Response**, to ensure a rapid and effective response to cybersecurity incidents, maintaining operational continuity and protecting data integrity.

Here, the **Key Hardware Components** are:

- The ***Cryptographic Modules*** to be used as hardware security modules -HSMs- (e.g. Thales nShield or Gemalto SafeNet for secure key management and encryption)
- The ***Network Sensors*** to ensure network management (e.g. devices from Snort or Suricata).

Here, the **main Raw Materials** are:

- Metals like ***Aluminium (Al)*** and ***Copper (Cu)*** for wiring and shielding.
- Semiconductors based on ***Silicon (Si)*** for processors handling encryption and authentication.

Here the **Key Software** part concerns the ***Encryption Algorithms*** (for *AES -Advanced Encryption Standard- and RSA -Rivest Shamir Adleman- for data protection*) **and** ***IDS Software*** to detect and respond to potential security threats in the network.

5.3.3.4. Flagship Project 4: RAIL4EARTH - Sustainable and Green Rail Systems

The **RAIL4EARTH** innovations pave the way for a sustainable and resilient rail system by integrating renewable energy, optimizing resource use, and adapting to climate change emphasizes on creating sustainable, energy-efficient, and environmentally friendly rail systems. It prioritizes reducing the carbon footprint of rail operations, promoting the use of **Alternative Energy and Propulsion Systems, Renewable Energy Sources (RES)**, and **optimizing energy efficiency in infrastructure and rolling stock**.

The innovation framework outlined below (though limited compared to the excel sheet for FP4) encompasses all potential energy sources, including renewable alternatives, to ensure a robust and sustainable operation across all facets—from infrastructure to rolling stock. It also integrates circular economy innovations, enhancing the resilience of trains to climate challenges and optimizing energy efficiency.

Alternative Energy & Propulsion Systems (the 1st main functionality on FA4 excel sheet)

Here the functionality that is looked for is the **Energy Recovery and Optimization** to optimize energy usage by recovering energy during operations and minimizing waste. As an illustration, the main sub-functionalities are the **Battery-Electric Multiple Units (BEMU), Hydrogen Fuel Cells, Hybrid Propulsion Systems**.

Here, the **subassemblies** are:

- The **Electrical energy** to power the train over short to medium distances without the need for continuous external power supply (e.g., overhead wires or third rails)
- The **Hydrogen amount** to be stored in a given volume to extend the operational range of the train between refuelling stops.
- The **Seamless Energy Management** i.e. coordinate the use of energy from batteries, hydrogen fuel cells, and conventional power sources and enable regenerative braking systems

Here, the **Key Hardware Components** are:

- **Battery racks interfaces** to efficiently change batteries during the train's life by maintainers
- **Efficient battery management systems (BMS)** to monitor battery health and status in real-time
- **Hydrogen fuel cells** to offer reliable operation under varying load conditions
- **Integrated powertrains** combining battery, hydrogen, and conventional systems version, with Braking energy recovery systems
- **Power electronics** for efficient energy conversion

Here, the **main Raw Materials** are:

- Metals like cobalt, nickel, manganese, **Copper (Cu)** for motor windings, **Aluminium (Al)** for capacitors, **Lithium (Li)** for batteries.
- Semiconductors based on **Silicon (Si)** for motor controllers and **Silicon Carbide (SiC)** power electronics, **Gallium Nitride (GaN)** transistors.

Here, the **Key Software** part concerns the **Battery management software for real-time monitoring and optimization** to manage energy flow between braking systems and storage units, or **Energy Management Systems** for optimizing the hybrid powertrain.

Renewable Energy Sources (RES) (2nd main functionalities on FA4 excel sheet)

Here the functionality that is looked for is the **Energy Supply Optimization** as this functionality aims to leverage renewable energy sources (including the alternative ones) to power rail systems and reduce dependency on fossil fuels. Thus, the Renewable Energy Integration appears as the main sub functionality.

Here, the **subassemblies** are (among others detailed in the excel sheet but not only):

- The **Smart Renewable Energy-Powered Stations** to utilize renewable energy sources to power rail infrastructure, promoting sustainable operations and reduced carbon footprint.
- The **Energy Storage Systems (ESS)** to focus on efficient energy storage solutions that ensure a stable energy supply, maximizing the use of renewable sources and balancing energy demands.
- The **Green Electrification** to include the efforts to reduce dependency on fossil fuels by electrifying more rail lines and integrating renewable sources into the power grid for trains and infrastructure (including systems for Energy Loss Reduction, or Fault Detection Management).

Here, the **Key Hardware Components** are:

- **Solar panels** (e.g., Photovoltaic Panels like First Solar Series 6) and **wind turbines** to generate electricity to offer scalability for different capacity needs.
- **Lithium-Ion Battery Storage Units** to store excess energy for later use.

Here, the **main Raw Materials** are:

- **Metals like Silicon (Si)** for photovoltaic cells, **Copper (Cu)** for wiring, **Lithium (Li)** for energy storage, or **Neodymium (Nd a LREE)** in the case of sensitive magnetic sensors that are used for wind turbine magnets.
- **Plastics and Polymers like Polyethylene** for protective panel coatings.

Here, the **Key Software** part concerns the **Energy Management Systems** and the elements to monitor and optimize renewable energy production thanks to the usage of **Predictive analytics Software** for balancing supply and demand with grid integration.

Smart and Efficient Operations (3rd main functionalities on FA4 excel sheet)

Here the functionality that is looked for is the **Eco-Friendly Construction and Maintenance** to reduce the environmental impact of rail infrastructure by using sustainable materials and practices. The sub functionalities are **Operational Efficiency and Predictive Analytics**, the **Noise and Vibration Mitigation Technologies** and the **Enhanced Energy Efficiency in Electro-Systems**.

Here, the **subassemblies** are:

- The **Proactive Equipment Maintenance** to predict and address maintenance needs before failures occur, reducing downtime and extending the lifespan of rail components
- The **Noise & Vibration** to minimize the noise reduction at source (i.e. generated by train movement), benefiting both passengers and communities near rail lines.
- The **Powerful and efficient propulsion** to reduce energy consumption and operational costs

- The **Climate control** oriented to ensure optimal temperature and air quality inside trains, enhancing passenger comfort

Here, the **Key Hardware Components** are:

- The **Predictive maintenance systems** to anticipate equipment failures before they occur, reducing unplanned downtime and optimizing maintenance schedules
- **Low-noise track and wheel designs** like high-temperature Tolerant Rail Alloys to reduce track deformation risks and thus noise and vibration.
- **Advanced HVAC (Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning) systems** to improve energy efficiency in rail systems, reducing overall power consumption and provide passengers with a comfortable environment by maintaining optimal temperature, ventilation, and air quality within the train.

Here, the **main Raw Materials** are:

- Metals like **Steel (Fe)** and **Copper (Cu)** for sensor housings, motors and wiring, **High-grade steel (Fe)** for rails and **alloyed steel (Fe)** for wheels, and **Aluminum (Al)** for heat exchangers.
- Semiconductors like **Digital Signal Processing (DSP)** chips for sensors and microprocessors, or semiconductors based on **Silicon Carbide (SiC)** and **Gallium Nitride (GaN)** for power electronics and Control electronics for temperature regulation.
- **Plastics and Polymers** like **Composite Materials** for sound insulation materials, and vibration damping materials.

Here, the **Key Software** part concerns all kind of **algorithms for Machine Learning, AI-driven optimization or predictive ones**. The purpose being to optimize energy use and adapt consumption while maintaining performance, as this functionality contributes to overall energy savings and reduced operational costs.

Rail Usage Attractiveness (4th main functionalities on FA4 excel sheet)

Here the functionality that is looked for is the enhanced usage of Low-Carbon Construction Materials. It is also important to achieve **Resilient Infrastructure Design** to develop rail systems that can withstand extreme weather conditions and adapt to climate change thanks to Climate-Adapted Rail Components.

Here, the **subassemblies** are:

- The **Digital Ticketing and Real-Time Information Systems** to modernize ticketing with digital solutions providing passengers with real-time travel information that improves the user experience and facilitates efficient, convenient travel.
- The **Accessibility Innovations** referring to enhancements in accessibility to make rail transport more inclusive, supporting a wider range of passengers, including those with disabilities.
- The **Comfort and Well-being Enhancements** that include all innovations focused on passenger comfort and well-being as designed to increase rail usage by creating a more appealing, passenger-centred travel environment. These include the usage of sustainable materials for rail infrastructure beyond the rolling stock.

Here, the **main Raw Materials** are:

- Metals for the contactless payment systems such **Copper (Cu)** antennae for RFID chips and wiring, **Aluminum (Al)** housings of electronic components, and for the circular economy practices of train car materials Scrap **Steel (Fe)**, **Aluminum (Al)** for reuse.
- Semiconductors with **Silicon** for microprocessors and RFID chips core material using **Gallium (Ga) and Germanium** for the advanced semiconductors.
- Plastics and Polymers like **recycled Polyethylene** for secondary products.

Here, the **Key Software** part concerns the **Payment processing systems** for digital transactions, **Integrated systems** for managing audio-visual aids and **Intelligent interior management** or **Material Recovery Tracking Systems** to monitor recycling and upcycling efficiency using AI algorithms.

5.3.3.5. Flagship Project 5: TRANS4M-R - Transforming Europe's Rail Freight

The **TRANS4M-R, FP 5** focuses on modernizing rail freight by enhancing digitalization, automation, and operational efficiency. Its primary goals include increasing rail freight capacity, streamlining intermodal logistics, and reducing environmental impact through sustainable practices and advanced technologies. These converge into 3 main functionalities for **TRANS4M-R, FP 5**, this being **Full Digital Freight Train Operations (FDFTO)**, **Seamless Rail Freight** and the **Innovative Freight Assets**.

These innovation structure captures the primary functionalities and hardware components (based on the sub-assemblies identified) needed to achieve automation and seamless operations goals. This comprehensive breakdown highlights **TRANS4M-R, FP 5's** focus on a sustainable, competitive, digital green rail freight services, emphasizing on **Digital Automatic Coupler (DAC)**, **Energy and Communication**, **Digitalization of Train Functions**, and **Automated Yard Operations** as sub-functionalities of the for the full digitalization of freight operations.

When it come to the Seamless Rail Freight, the required sub-functionalities are **Seamless and Intermodal Connectivity**.

Finally, when it comes to the Innovative Freight Assets functionality, the main sub-functionalities are coming down to the **Sustainable Freight Practices** such as Hydrogen Transport Container, Self-Propelled Wagon or Energy Efficiency Strategy for Freight.

Full Digital Freight Train Operations (FDFTO) (1st main functionality on the FA5 excel sheet)

Here the functionality that is looked for is to provide real-time tracking and monitoring of freight movements to improve efficiency and reliability. This functionality involves ultimately transitioning from driver-assisted systems to fully autonomous train operations. It supports increasing levels of automation, from supervised systems to fully automated (GoA 4). As a natural consequence, the **Digital Automatic Coupler (DAC)** and the **Train Functions**, among others, are mandatory sub-functionalities. These systems are vital for reducing human error and improving operational efficiency.

Here, the **subassemblies** related to the functionalities are:

- The **Digital Automatic Coupler (DAC)** to streamline the coupling process, reduce manual intervention, and enhance operational efficiency.
- The **Energy and Communication Systems** (incl. Train Integrity) to ensure reliable real-time monitoring and communication that will support efficient and safe freight operations.
- The **Train Functions** (e.g., Automated Brake Test) to automate essential train functions, reducing delays and increasing safety.
- The **Automated Yard Operations** to optimize yard management, increasing throughput and reducing bottlenecks in rail freight logistics.

Here, the **Key Hardware Components** related to the sub-assemblies are:

- The **Automatic Coupler Systems**, i.e. mechanized components for coupling/uncoupling trains.
- The **Sensors and Actuators** for detecting coupling conditions and actuating the process.

- The **Power Supply Systems**, i.e. including transformers, voltage converters and circuit breakers for 400V operations
- The **Communication Modules** with transceivers, antennas and data processors to secure data transmission across the train.
- The **Integrity Monitoring Sensors** through Strain Gauges, Accelerometers, or Data Loggers that ensure the train's physical integrity.
- The **Brake Actuators and Pressure or Position Sensors** for automatic brake testing and monitoring.
- The **Diagnostic Modules** thanks to Data Acquisition Systems and Display Units devices that analyse brake performance data.
- The **Automated Shunting Locomotives** equipped with automation, i.e. propulsion and control systems, for yard operations
- The **CCTV and Surveillance Systems** to cameras and monitoring displays to monitor and manage yard activities thanks.
- The **Sensors for Track and Train Positioning** thanks to GPS Modules and Position Sensors that detect and manage the position of trains.

Here, the **main Raw Materials** are (for the exhaustive list please refer to the FA5 excel detailed sheet):

- Metals like **Stainless Steel (Fe)** for corrosion resistance, **Aluminum (Al)** for lightweight components or sensors housing, **Copper (Cu)** for wiring and connections, **Gold (Au)** for high-quality connectors.
- Semiconductors based on **Silicon (Si)** for MEMS, GPS chips, image sensors or display drivers and sensors.
- Plastics and Polymers like **Polycarbonate** and **Polyurethane** for housing, **Polyethylene (PE)** for seals and **Liquid Crystal Display (LCD)** panels.

Here the **Key Software** part concerns the **Brake Control Systems Software** that automates and monitors brake testing, the **Energy Management Systems Software** for optimizing energy use and distribution, and the **Yard Management Systems Software** to control and automate yard operations. These software on top of AI and ML algorithms are here to monitor and optimize all operations and logistic freight needs.

Seamless Rail Freight (2nd main functionalities on FA5 excel sheet)

Here the functionality that is looked for is to grant the operations with **Seamless Planning and Dispatching** to integrate advanced planning tools that will streamline dispatching, reduce delays, and improve overall scheduling efficiency. Likewise the other functionality that is required is the **Intermodal Integration and Prediction** as it will enhance connectivity with other transport modes and leverage predictive analytics to optimize cargo transfers and minimize delays.

Here, the **subassemblies** are:

- The **Servers and Data Centers** to host planning and dispatching software.
- The **Communication Networks** to achieve real-time data exchange between systems.

- The **Intermodal Transfer Equipment** with cranes and automated systems for moving freight between transport modes.
- The **Tracking and Monitoring Devices** (e.g. IoT) to track cargo across different modes of transport.

Here, the **Key Hardware Components** are:

- The **Server Racks**, the **Processors**, and **Cooling Systems**.
- The **Routers & Switches**.
- The **Hydraulic Systems**, the **Control Systems**, the **GPS Modules**, the **RFID Tags** and various **Components** (e.g. the IoT sensors).

Here, the **main Raw Materials** are:

- Metals like **Steel (Fe)** for structural components in sensors and controllers and **Aluminum (Al)** for lightweight frames, **Copper (Cu)** for wiring, **Gold (Au)** for high-performance connectors.
- Semiconductors based on **Silicon (Si)** for network processors.
- Plastics and Polymers like **Polycarbonate** for housing and insulation.

Here the **Key Software** part concerns the **Logistics Planning Software** as it will provide platforms that optimize train scheduling and routing, in junction to **Intermodal Logistic platforms** which will integrate and optimize the flow of goods across transport modes.

Innovative Freight Assets (3rd main functionalities on FA5 excel sheet)

Here the functionalities that is looked for is the carbon reduction in freight operations via the **Hydrogen Transport Container** and the **Self-Propelled Wagon** that will minimize the environmental impact of rail freight by adopting greener technologies and practices. Also another functionality looked for is the **Energy Efficiency Strategy for Freight** as will reduce energy consumption and enhance efficiency through innovative recovery systems.

Here, the **subassemblies** are:

- The **Hydrogen Storage Tanks** to enable eco-friendly freight solutions by supporting hydrogen-based transportation methods.
- *The **Safety Valves and Sensors** to monitor and ensure a safe containment of hydrogen.*
- *The **Onboard Propulsion Systems**, either with electric or hybrid engines for self-propulsion.*
- The **Sensors for Navigation and Control** with devices for managing wagon movement autonomously.
- The **Energy Recovery Systems** that will use devices for regenerative braking systems to capture and reuse energy.
- The **Energy Storage Units** using batteries or capacitors to store recovered energy.

Here, the **Key Hardware Components** are:

- The **Tank Shell**, the **Liners**, the **Insulation**, and the **Valves**.
- The **Electric Motors**, the **Gear Systems**, the **Battery Storage**, the **Battery cells**, the **Battery Management System**, the **Inertial Measurement Units (IMUs)**, and the **GPS Modules**.
- The **Regenerative Braking Units**, the **Battery Cells**, the **Capacitors** (if used), the **Battery Management System (BMS)**, and the **Cooling System** (for high-capacity storage).

Here, the **main Raw Materials** are:

- Metals like **Aluminum (Al)** or **Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastics (CFRP)** for lightweight, high-strength tanks, **Copper (Cu)** for wiring and electrical connections, **Steel (Fe)** for the motor core and **Lithium (Li)** for batteries, **Nickel (Ni)** for cathodes.
- Semiconductors based on **Silicon (Si)** for battery management systems, microcontrollers and sensors, for pressure and hydrogen detection sensors, or for MEMS gyroscopes and accelerometers.
- Plastics and Polymers like **Polyethylene (PE)** for chemical resistance, **Polycarbonate** for housing.

Here the **Key Software** parts concern the **Predictive Maintenance Tools Software** that uses energy data to predict and optimize maintenance needs and the **Energy Optimization Algorithms Software** that optimizes energy use across the train's systems.

5.3.3.6. Flagship Project 6: FUTURE - Delivering innovative rail services to revitalise capillary lines and regional rail services

NOTE:

For this Flagship Project 6 as well as for the next one, i.e. Flagship Project 7, they are both using the output or starting from the output of the previous flagships, i.e.:

- from Flagship Project 1 to Flagship Project 5 for Flagship Project 6, as it concerns the capillary lines and not the freight operations, so no DAC but still concerned by the “last mile shunting operations”

For that reason, in this chapter and the next one, the focus of the Flagship Project is mentioned as well as the main functionalities, while the sub-assemblies, the hardware, the raw material and finally the key software's are not as repeating what is written in the previous chapters.

The **FUTURE, FP6** focuses on modernizing regional and capillary rail services to address gaps in connectivity, improve operational efficiency, and deliver sustainable, innovative rail systems. This entails leveraging **advanced traffic management, train detection, and sustainable technologies** to ensure regional rail services align with broader EU ambitions. Therefore, ERJU MAWP clearly mentions that this Flagship used the enablers and output of the previous flagship. Here the extracts:

- Flagship 1 states that Flagship 6 **“specifies the requirements for regional railways and uses the enablers developed in FA [FP] 1 adapting a simplified TMS and on-demand passengers services requesting flexible timetabling”**.
- Likewise for Flagship 2, this Flagship 6 **“specifies the requirements for regional railways and uses the enablers developed in FA [FP] 2 adapting cost-effective CCS and ATO solutions for functions such as highly accurate fail-safe train positioning, train integrity, train length detection as well as cost-effective communication. Both, FA [FP] 1 and FA [FP] 2 provide the operational backbone for FA [FP] 6”**.
- When it comes to Flagship 3, it precises that **“FA [FP] 6 uses the enablers developed in FA3 (e.g. infrastructure inspection systems to be installed in commercial vehicles, autonomous inspection vehicles, algorithms to predict asset degradation, robotic solutions to perform maintenance tasks and new manufacturing and repairing techniques based on additive manufacturing) taking into account the scope and objectives of FA [FP] 6 to minimise asset life-cycle costs and decrease OPEX”**.
- Regarding Flagship 4, it is stated that the flagship 6 **“uses the enablers developed in FA [FP] 4 where relevant, including alternative low carbon, low weight and energy efficient systems to achieve cost efficient decarbonization and resilience”**.
- Finally, in the flagship 5 and 7, it is stated that **“Multimodal shared-mobility solution - DAC as an essential prerequisite for single staffed last mile shunting operations and a better integration in multimodal transport chains- developed in FA [FP] 7 and FA [FP] 5 can be used in FA [FP] 6 to increase the attractiveness of regional railways for customers and generate additional revenue streams.”**

Therefore the functionalities, sub-assemblies and related hardware, raw materials and software are as per the previously described Flagship Projects, see below (and excel FP6 related sheet for

full details):

- **Traffic Management and Mobility Orchestration** (as per FP1 above)
- **Real-Time Forecasting and Capacity Management** (as per FP1 above)
- **Secured Mobility** (as per FP1, FP2 and FP3 above)
- **Advanced Signalling, Control, and Automation** (as per FP2 above)
- **Advanced Train Communications and Decision Support** (as per FP2 above)
- **Advanced Asset Management for Infrastructure and Rolling Stock** (as per FP3 above)
- **Efficient Predictive Maintenance and Operations** (as per FP3 above)
- **Real-Time Simulation and Monitoring with Digital Twins** (as per FP3 above)
- **Alternative Energy & Propulsion Systems** (as per FP4 above)
- **Renewable Energy Sources (RES)** (as per FP4 above)
- **Smart and Efficient Operations** (as per FP4 above)
- **Rail Usage Attractiveness Enhancement** (as per FP4 above)
- **Full Digital Freight Train Operations** (as per FP5 and except the DAC features)
- **Seamless Rail Freight** (as per FP5 for 'last mile' shunting operations)
- **Innovative Freight Assets** (as per FP5).

5.3.3.7. Flagship Project 7: Pods4Rail - Development of New Mobility Solutions with Modular Pods

REMINDER:

For this Flagship Project 7, like it was for the previous one i.e. Flagship Project 6, the starting point happens once the output of the previous flagships i.e.:

- from Flagship Project 1 to Flagship Project 5, fully i.e. including the DAC part, for the Flagship Project 7 as it will concern all kinds of transportation for passenger and freight purposes.

For that reason, in this chapter the focus of the Flagship Project is mentioned as well as the main functionalities while the sub-assemblies, the hardware, the raw material and finally the key software's are not as repeating what is written in the previous chapters.

The **PODS4RAIL**, FP7, focuses on introducing modular pods as an innovative rail mobility solution, enhancing flexibility, efficiency, and sustainability. The project aims to deliver **advanced rolling stock innovations** tailored for **specific operational needs**, with a **modular design** allowing **seamless adaptation across passenger and freight services**.

In the ERJU MAWP, a clear extract regarding - Flagship Area 7 on p.193 & 194- reminds that the **"The vision of the FA [P7] is to develop the next generation of railway transport systems as well as guided transport systems based on a fully automated multi-modal mobility system for passengers and goods which is sustainable, interconnected, digital, on-demand, standardised, scalable and suitable for all transport modes."** Therefore "Any innovation in FA [P] 7 needs to fulfil the requirement of being an **Open Platform, based on common standards and standardised interfaces, connecting all the transport modes**, and be **able to provide disruptive Operation and Business Models**."

Therefore, the functionalities, sub-assemblies and related hardware, raw materials and software are as per the previously described Flagship Projects, see below (and excel FP7 related sheet for full details):

- **Traffic Management and Mobility Orchestration** (as per FP1 above)
- **Real-Time Forecasting and Capacity Management** (as per FP1 above)
- **Secured Mobility** (as per FP1, FP2 and FP3 above)
- **Advanced Signalling, Control, and Automation** (as per FP2 above)
- **Advanced Train Communications and Decision Support** (as per FP2 above)
- **Advanced Asset Management for Infrastructure and Rolling Stock** (as per FP3 above)
- **Efficient Predictive Maintenance and Operations** (as per FP3 above)
- **Real-Time Simulation and Monitoring with Digital Twins** (as per FP3 above)
- **Alternative Energy & Propulsion Systems** (as per FP4 above)
- **Renewable Energy Sources (RES)** (as per FP4 above)
- **Smart and Efficient Operations** (as per FP4 above)
- **Rail Usage Attractiveness Enhancement** (as per FP4 above)
- **Full Digital Freight Train Operations** (as per FP5)
- **Seamless Rail Freight** (as per FP5)
- **Innovative Freight Assets** incl. smart grids integration of energy storage solutions (as per FP5).

5.3.4. Overview of FPs and Key technologies, and needed Components and Raw materials

To summarize what is detailed in the previous paragraphs, the following two figures are presented. They were used during InnoTrans 2024 to present the supply impact of the new Rail Innovations promoted by Europe's Rail.

Figure 1 | High-level overview of Key technologies, Components and Raw Materials needed to deliver the Rail Innovations within FP1 to FP5 (source: LEADER 2030 presentation at InnoTrans 2024)

Figure 2 | High-level overview of Key technologies, Components and Raw Materials needed to deliver the Rail Innovations within FP6 to FP7 (source: LEADER 2030 presentation at InnoTrans 2024)

Source: J. Rainbault research and analysis for RAILENIUM | June 2024 to date

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5.4. Technologies to be Introduced Based on the new needs assessment (disruptions in HW/SW and Raw Materials) *(column L)*

This section is here to outline the new technologies to be introduced across the seven Flagship Projects (FPs) of LEADER 2030, emphasizing the disruptions identified in hardware and software requirements and their induced raw materials needs. The identified new needs are derived from the detailed assessment of functionalities, sub-functionalities, sub-assemblies, and related components and raw materials treated in the previous chapter and sections.

Thus, in this section we will outline the raw materials disruptions and link it to the excel sheet “overall” section of each Flagship Project (bottom part of each Flagship Project table) as well as to the summary presentation done at InnoTrans 2024 to the Head of LEADER 2030, Veronica Elena BOCCI, and the then contemporary ERA Head, Mr Josef DOPPLEBAUER.

5.4.1.FP1: MOTIONAL - Mobility Management Multimodal Environment and Digital Enablers - Technology Disruptions

For the FP 1 we see the introduction of new technologies materializing in the transition to AI-driven traffic and capacity management, in the adoption of predictive analytics for multimodal integration and also in advanced real-time data communication systems (5G, FRMCS), all aiming for Train Integrity, ATP, Data Communication and Networking, and Robust cybersecurity Measures (e.g. encryption, authentication. All main disruptions are referred the below as Hardware and Software:

- **Hardware:**
 - Introduction of **GNSS devices** with high-precision satellite signal components and Inertial Measurement Units (IMU) for enhanced train positioning,
 - **EoT, IoT** and **Network sensors** and **Magnets**, and **ETCS** Computers,
 - **High-frequency antennas** and **FRMCS** communication for real-time data communication and advanced firewalls for cybersecurity all operating on **High Performance Servers**.
- **Software:**
 - **Positioning algorithms** that integrate GNSS and IMU data, real-time analytics for network flow optimization, and threat detection algorithms.
 - **HMI** based on open operating systems (to allow a system network operation to all operators as induced by the ERTMS interoperability essence)
 - **Decision Making software** supporting decision making (train detection, ATP, Integrity, com°, etc.) based on:
 - Data fusion software
 - Centralised databases
 - Software defining priority rules
 - Harmonised methods for capacity planning
 - testing algorithms for constant trials of the system

- **Verification and security issues** software for (Data Com° & Networking, Cybersecurity measures).

This has a direct impact on the **Raw Materials Disruptions** and emerges as such:

- Shift to **Gallium Arsenide (GaAs)** for GNSS sensitivity improvement and **Gallium Nitride (GaN)** in advanced semiconductors.
- More widespread incorporation of **Neodymium (Nd)** and **Lithium (Li)**, for improved sensor performance
- Increased reliance on **Copper (Cu)** and **Gold (Au)** for connectors and supportive Data Centers infrastructure
- Higher dependence on **Silicon (Si)** in processors and in power electronics for efficient power conversion and management as having higher thermal conductivity, greater efficiency, and handling higher voltages than traditional silicon semiconductors.

5.4.2.FP2: R2DATO - Rail to Digital Automated Train Operations - Technology Disruptions

For the FP2 we see higher demands for more sophisticated and robust communication and processing capabilities compared to older rail technologies. Therefore the introduction of new technologies would concern the shift to autonomous operations with GoA4 automation, it will concern the advanced train localization (as GNSS seen in FP1 already), and the extensive use of use of AI for decision-making in real-time traffic (including to non-rail vehicles via V2X communication). All these will mainly materializes in the below Hardware and Software:

- **Hardware:**
 - Implementation of **AI-driven train control systems**,
 - **LIDAR**, and **Radar sensors** for autonomous operations,
 - **Advanced MEMS** accelerometers and **Smart Valve actuators**
 - along with **edge computing devices (e.g. ETCS, BIU)** for real-time decision-making.Furthermore, the market will continue to demand high-precision sensors, advanced energy storage systems, GSM-R equipment, and AI-based control systems, despite recent supply disruptions. These components should be marked with a "supply alert" to ensure continuous monitoring and proactive measures to secure their availability
- **Software:**
 - **AI-powered** GoA4 (Grade of Automation Level 4) algorithms,
 - **predictive maintenance systems**,
 - and **digital twins** for operational simulation.

This has a direct impact on the **Raw Materials Disruptions** and emerges as such:

- Expanded use of **Rare Earth Elements (REEs)** for sensors and actuators such **Neodymium (Nd)**

- Increased reliance on **Copper (Cu)**, **Steel (Fe)** and **Gold (Au)** for connectors and supportive Data Centres infrastructure
- Increased demand for **Gallium Arsenide (GaAs)** and for advanced semiconductors thus increased demand of **Gallium Nitride (GaN)**.

5.4.3.IAM4RAIL - Holistic and Integrated Asset Management for Europe's Rail System - Technology Disruptions

For the FP3 we see the introduction of new technologies as Real-time Operations, Predictive maintenance and Condition Based Monitoring, all using Digital Twins and IoT sensors, as well as more computing and edge devices processing for real-time analytics. Here below are the concerned main Hardware and Software:

- **Hardware:**
 - **Advanced Signalling** (e.g. Digital signals, control units) for real-time train control
 - Deployment of **IoT-enabled sensors** for predictive maintenance and centralized asset management hubs with high-speed processing capabilities,
 - **Edge Computing Devices** such as local data processing devices using **Magnetic induced microwires** before and in the tunnels to monitor tunnels movements
- **Software:**
 - **Integrated asset management platforms** using **digital twin platforms**
 - **AI-driven analytics** such as **AI algorithms for general health conditions to bogies and certain components part of the trainsets**
 - **check point data integration** such as **collection / data fusion of information in a single point of various inputs, with IoT frameworks.**

This has a direct impact on the **Raw Materials Disruptions** and emerges as such:

- Expanded use of **lightweight alloys** for IoT devices.
- Adoption of **advanced Silicon (Si)** and **Platinum (Pt)** components for sensor reliability and increased reliance on **Copper (Cu)**, and Heavy Rare Earth Elements such as **Terbium (Tb)** and **Dysprosium (Dy)**.
- Increased demand for **Gallium Arsenide (GaAs)** and for advanced semiconductors thus increased demand of **Gallium Nitride (GaN)**.

5.4.4.FP4: RAIL4EARTH - Sustainable and Green Rail Systems

For the FP4 we see the introduction of new technologies for the transition to green energy sources (e.g. hydrogen, solar) and energy recovery systems (regenerative braking) materializing in the below Hardware and Software:

- **Hardware:**
 - **Battery Electric Multiple Units (BEMUs), Fuel cells** and **hydrogen tanks** to replace diesel engines
 - Implementation of **regenerative braking systems**,
 - Introduction of **energy-efficient traction systems**, and **Smart Renewable Energy-Powered Stations**
 - **Advanced insulation materials** for energy-efficient rolling stock
 - Installation of **onboard battery storage** (e.g. large-scale battery storage system).
- **Software:**
 - **Energy management systems** integrated with real-time monitoring for optimal efficiency (e.g. Intelligent climate control and lighting).

This has a direct impact on the **Raw Materials Disruptions** and emerges as such:

- Increased use of **Lithium (Li), Gallium (Ga)** for battery technologies and their semiconductors, **Copper (Cu)**.
- Higher demand for **Light** and **Heavy Rare Earth Elements**, such as **Neodymium (Nd), Yttrium (Y), Europium (Eu), Terbium (Tb)**, including for the use of **magnets** in regenerative systems.

5.4.5.FP5: TRANS4M-R - Transforming Europe's Rail Freight

For the FP5 we see the introduction of new technologies to allow the automation and electrification in freight handling and also the implementation of digital logistics platforms for enhanced supply chain management (i.e. from DAC to Energy and Communication via the Train functions). All of which will be materializing mainly in the below Hardware and Software:

- **Hardware:**
 - **Automated freight handling systems** such as automation hardware, coupling/decoupling sensors:
 - **Digital couplers** for automated train coupling/decoupling.
 - **Electric and pneumatic connectors** integrated into DAC systems.
 - **IoT Sensors and actuators** for coupling status detection and control
 - **Proximity sensors** to detect coupling distance.
 - **Force sensors** to monitor coupling strength and alignment.
 - **Optical sensors** for alignment verification during coupling
 - **Modular freight carriages,**
 - **Advanced sensors and RFID** tagging.
The advanced sensors demand is expected to remain high due to their critical role in DAC systems for safe and efficient coupling/decoupling operations.
- **Software:**
 - **Digital freight management platforms** for communication modules,
 - **Predictive logistics algorithms.**

This has a direct impact on the **Raw Materials Disruptions** and emerges as such:

- Increased reliance on **Aluminum (Al)** and **Aluminum Bauxite (Ai)** for lightweight freight carriages and **Silicon (Si)** for IoT devices
- Expanded use of **Copper (Cu)** in RFID and connectivity modules, and **Steel (Fe)**.

5.4.6.FP6: FUTURE - Delivering Innovative Rail Services for Capillary Lines and Regional Rail Services

For the FP6, and on top of the previous mentioned new technologies (except the DAC related ones), we see the introduction of new technologies related to lightweight trains with modular designs and decentralized energy systems (e.g. solar and wind integration). This is materializing mainly in the below Hardware and Software (on top of the previously mentioned ones):

- **Hardware:**
 - **Modular rail systems** for low-density networks,
 - **Compact power units,**
 - Lightweight rolling stock using **lightweight composite-based train shells**
- **Software:**
 - Regional **network optimization algorithms**
 - **Demand-responsive scheduling platforms.**

This has a direct impact on the **Raw Materials Disruptions** and emerges as such:

- Shift to lightweight materials like **Titanium (Ti)** and **Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymers (CFRP)**
- Expanded use of **advanced composite materials** for durability and efficiency
- **Lithium (Li)** for modular energy storage systems.

5.4.7.FP7: PODS4RAIL - Development of New Mobility Solutions with Modular Pods

For the FP7, and on top of the previous mentioned new technologies, we see the introduction of new technologies induced by the development of modular and adaptable pods for both passenger and freight services, and the introduction of robotic systems for automated pod handling. Though the technologies are fully relying on the output of the previous Flagships, still we should expect the below Hardware and Software:

- **Hardware:**
 - *Modular pod systems with integrated power units*
 - *autonomous navigation technologies*
- **Software:**
 - *Self-adaptive navigation algorithms*
 - *Passenger experience optimization platforms.*

This has a direct impact on the **Raw Materials Disruptions** and emerges as such:

- Increased demand for lightweight alloys like **Aluminum-Lithium (Al-Li)**
- Use of **advanced polymers and composites** for pod structures.

5.4.8. Short Summary Table of Technology and Material Disruptions

FP	Technology Disruptions (Hardware)	Software Disruptions	Key Material Disruptions
<i>FP1</i>	GNSS, IMU, High-Frequency Antennas, Firewalls	Positioning, Analytics, Cybersecurity	GaAs, Cu, Au, Si
<i>FP2</i>	AI Systems, LIDAR, RADAR, Edge Computing	AI GoA4, Predictive Maintenance, Digital Twins	REEs, GaN, Reduced Steel
<i>FP3</i>	IoT Sensors, Centralized Hubs	AI Analytics, IoT Frameworks	Lightweight Alloys, Si, Pt
<i>FP4</i>	Regenerative Braking, Traction Systems, Batteries	Energy Management Systems	Li, Co, Rare Earth Magnets
<i>FP5</i>	Automated Systems, Modular Carriages, RFID	Freight Management, Predictive Logistics	Al, Cu, Reduced Iron
<i>FP6</i>	Modular Rail Systems, Compact Units	Optimization Algorithms, Scheduling Platforms	Ti, CFRP, Reduced Cast Iron
<i>FP7</i>	Modular Pods, Autonomous Navigation Systems	Self-Adaptive Navigation, Experience Platforms	Al-Li, Advanced Polymers

5.5. Obsolete and phasing out Components due to the railway transformation targeted for 2030 (column M)

The transition towards a fully digitalized, automated, and sustainable railway network by 2030 entails significant changes in the hardware, software, and raw materials used in railway infrastructure. As new technologies emerge, certain traditional components and raw materials will become obsolete or phased out due to inefficiencies, lack of compatibility with modern systems, or environmental concerns. This section highlights the key hardware and raw materials that will be phased out across the seven Flagship Projects (FPs) under the LEADER 2030 initiative.

5.5.1.FP1: MOTIONAL - Mobility Management Multimodal Environment and Digital Enablers – Obsolescence

Building on the previously outlined introduction of new technologies, FP1 will significantly impact the rail industry by driving the gradual phasing out of the following hardware and raw materials:

- **Hardware:**
 - **The legacy Train Detection Systems:**
 - **Traditional track circuits and axle counters** are being replaced by advanced GNSS and IMU-based positioning systems, reducing reliance on physical trackside equipment and thus
 - the decrease of **fixed block sections** used in traditional signalling systems,
 - the diminution of **track circuit-based detection** systems
 - the drop of **Manual Train Control systems**
 - the reduction of **Non-Integrated Braking systems**.
 - **The Analog Communication Systems:**
 - **GSM-R will be phased out** in favour of FRMCS and IP-based communication protocols, thus:
 - the reduction of **Basic radio communication**,
 - **The Static Scheduling Tools:**
 - **Manual and semi-automated timetable management systems** are being replaced by AI-driven dynamic scheduling solutions
- **Raw Materials:**
 - **Steel (Fe)** in Track circuits and all mechanical equipment, **basic Copper (Cu)** wiring (as replaced by Fiber Optics), and **Copper-Based Track Circuits**, due to the shift towards wireless train detection systems, copper-intensive trackside infrastructure is becoming redundant
 - Old semiconductor types, for e.g.:
 - **Bipolar Junction Transistors (BJTs)** used in older control systems, amplifiers, and switching devices
 - **Silicon (Si) Rectifiers** and **Diodes**, used for basic power regulation, signal rectification, and protection circuits

- **Thyristors (Silicon-Controlled Rectifiers)** used in traditional power control and rectification circuits
- **Early Generations MOSFETs (Metal-Oxide-Semiconductor Field-Effect Transistors)** utilized in early electronic control units and basic switching application.

5.5.2.FP2: R2DATO - Rail to Digital automated up to autonomous train operation – Obsolescence

Building on the previously outlined introduction of new technologies, FP2 will significantly impact the rail industry by driving the gradual phasing out of the following raw materials, though the decreases in 'former' raw material usage are generally offset by the overall increase in the more advanced and efficient materials, therefore most of the raw materials here are seeing a stable usage.

- **Hardware:**
 - **The Manual Driving Interfaces**
 - **Traditional control panels** and **manual throttle systems** will be phased out as ATO (GoA4) becomes the standard.
 - **Conventional Braking Systems**
 - the reduction of **Non-Integrated Braking systems**, i.e. **Mechanical-only braking mechanisms**, are being replaced by sensor-integrated, AI-optimized braking solutions.
 - **Standalone Driver-Centric Systems:**
 - Systems that rely on **human operation** such as traditional components for **manual control systems** are being replaced with fully automated and AI-assisted control platforms.
 - **Mechanical Relays** which may have used various metals and plastics, might be replaced by solid-state relays and advanced electronic switches, reducing the overall usage of these materials.
- **Raw Materials:**
 - **Steel-Heavy Control Panels** as the removal of human-operated driving cabins will reduce the need for **large metal-based interfaces**
 - Metals in general we will see a decrease in metals usage as wireless communication (Wi-Fi 6) becomes more prevalent, reducing the need for extensive physical cabling
 - Semiconductors, older semiconductor technologies will decrease as more advanced silicon-based chips are used
 - Plastics and Polymers used in the legacy enclosures and casings will decrease with the increased integration and miniaturization of components.

5.5.3.FP3: IAM4RAIL - A Holistic and Integrated Asset Management for Europe's Rail System – Obsolescence

Building on the previously outlined introduction of new technologies, FP3 will significantly impact the rail industry by driving the gradual phasing out of the following Technologies, Hardware and Raw Materials.

- **Technologies and Hardware:**
 - **Legacy Monitoring Sensors**
 - **Wired vibration and stress monitoring sensors** are being replaced with wireless IoT-enabled predictive maintenance systems.
 - **On-Site Maintenance Diagnostics:**
 - **Manual inspection procedures** are becoming obsolete in favour of AI-powered predictive analytics.
 - **Paper-Based Asset Tracking Systems**
 - Digital twin and blockchain-enabled asset management systems are replacing **traditional paper-based documentation**.
- **Raw Materials:**

Will see a reduced dependence on heavy metals previously used in legacy infrastructure

 - **Plastic in Analog Monitoring Systems**
 - With the shift towards digital and sensor-based diagnostics, **plastic casings used in outdated monitoring equipment** will decline.

5.5.4.FP4: RAIL4EARTH - Sustainable and Green Rail Systems – Obsolescence

Building on the previously outlined introduction of new technologies, FP4 will significantly impact the rail industry by driving the gradual phasing out of the following Technologies, Hardware and Raw Materials.

- **Technologies and Hardware:**
 - **Diesel Locomotives**
 - The shift to battery-electric and hydrogen-powered trains is making **diesel-based propulsion systems** obsolete.
 - **High-Emission Track Lubricants**
 - Eco-friendly alternatives are replacing **petroleum-based lubricants** (e.g. fuel-based system components),
 - **Non-Energy Efficient HVAC Systems**
 - **Older heating, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC) systems** are being phased out in favour of energy-efficient smart HVAC solutions
- **Raw Materials**
 - In the case of the Heavy Diesel Engine Components, the **Cast iron and Steel (Fe) used in traditional diesel locomotives** will decline with the transition to lightweight electric motors.

5.5.5.FP5: TRANS4M-R - Transforming Europe's Rail Freight – Obsolescence

Building on the previously outlined introduction of new technologies, FP5 will significantly impact the rail industry by driving the gradual phasing out of the following Technologies, Hardware and Raw Materials.

- **Methods and Hardware:**
 - **Traditional Wagon Coupling Systems**
 - ***Mechanical coupling systems*** are being phased out in favour of automatic digital coupling (DAC) technology reducing labour costs and human error
 - Phase-out of **Manual Brake Testing Systems** as Automated brake testing will be integrated into DAC systems
 - **Conventional Freight Tracking Methods**
 - ***RFID-based freight monitoring*** is being replaced by real-time IoT and AI-driven logistics management
 - **Non-Modular Freight Wagons**
 - ***Fixed-configuration freight cars*** are becoming obsolete with the introduction of modular and flexible wagon concepts
 - ***Non-digital maintenance tools, conventional energy storage systems, and non-eco-friendly materials*** will become obsolete
 - ***Legacy Data Storage Systems*** as they will be replaced by cloud-based and quantum computing solutions for data storage and processing.
- **Raw Materials**
 - ***Steel-Based Coupling Equipment in older mechanical systems will see traditional Steel (Fe) components*** reducing with the shift to lightweight composite materials and automated digital coupling systems
 - Reduction of **Cast iron** in internal combustion engines
 - Diminution of ***Basic polymers like PVC and older insulation materials.***

5.5.6.FP6: FUTURE - Delivering innovative rail services to revitalise capillary lines and regional rail services – Obsolescence

Building on the previously outlined introduction of new technologies, and the referred technologies, methods, hardware and raw materials that will be phase out, FP6 will notably impact the rail industry by driving the gradual phasing out of the following Hardware and Components.

- **Hardware and Components:**

- The replacement of Replace traditional steel carriages, i.e. Diesel Multiple Units (DMUs) such as **Regional diesel trains** will be phased out in favour of battery-electric and hydrogen fuel cell-powered trains.
- Traditional Signalling Infrastructure such as **Trackside signalling** will be reduced with the implementation of virtual balises and digital ETCS Level 3 systems,
- Manual Ticketing Systems using **Paper-based ticketing** will become obsolete due to the widespread adoption of digital and biometric-based fare collection.

5.5.7.FP7: Pods4Rail - Development of New Mobility Solutions with Modular Pods – Obsolescence

Building on the previously outlined introduction of new technologies, and the previously referred technologies, methods, hardware and raw materials that will be phase out, FP7 will significantly impact the rail industry by driving the gradual phasing out of the following Hardware and Components.

- **Hardware and Components:**

- With the shift towards flexible, on-demand mobility solutions will make **traditional fixed-schedule rail services** obsolete in some areas.
- Conventional railcars with **heavy steel chassis** are being phased out in favour of lightweight composite-based pod systems when it will come to Heavyweight Rail Vehicles,
- **Conventional manual driving mechanisms** will no longer be relevant with fully automated and guided modular pods for Mechanical Steering & Control.

- **Raw Materials**

- Lightweight carbon fibre and composite materials will replace **traditional heavy steel-based railcar structures** when it comes to Heavy Steel in Vehicle Bodies.

The transformation of the railway sector by 2030 will lead to significant shifts in hardware, software, and raw material usage. Many legacy components, from diesel propulsion systems to traditional train detection technologies, are being replaced by advanced digital and AI-driven solutions. As automation, electrification, and digitalization continue to evolve, obsolete materials and systems will be phased out, aligning the railway industry with the sustainability and efficiency goals set for 2030. This transition will also impact supply chains, manufacturing, and maintenance processes, requiring strategic planning for resource allocation and workforce adaptation.

5.6. Technology implementation and foreseen criticalities (Column P & R)

Across the seven Flagship Projects (FP1 to FP7), technology implementation faces varying levels of readiness and criticality. If all technologies are going to be implemented at the same swift pace the market might face bottleneck situation when it would come to the raw materials. In order to assess this criticality several hypotheses have been taken. To conduct the analysis, which results are exhaustively detailed in the excel table (in annex) for each of the concerned FA and respective FP, the below is an expanded explanation of the methodology and hypotheses that guided the analysis and resulting data for both the *Likelihood of technology (HW/SW) implementation in 2030* (i.e. in column “P”) and the *Foreseen criticalities in 2030* (i.e. in column “R”)

5.6.1. Modalities to Reach Criticalities Assessment

To determine the criticalities of the innovations outlined in the European Rail Joint Undertaking (ERJU) Master Plan and the ERJU Multi-Annual Work Plan (MAWP) in relation to the LEADER 2030 initiative, a structured methodology was applied, supported by specific hypotheses. This approach aimed to systematically break down each flagship project (FP) to reveal core innovations criticalities, enabling a comprehensive understanding of future raw material needs. Below is an expanded explanation of the methodology and hypotheses that guided the creation of the analysis and resulting data tables:

Methodology

Sequential Analysis by Flagship Project

By examining each FP individually, we ensured that every single new technology implementation and its related raw material could be considered separately and not overlooked. This methodical approach allowed for a focused examination of each FP’s unique innovations, products, components, and material needs, facilitating easier identification of potential overlaps and common technologies across FPs.

Determination of implementation by technology (column P of each sheet – see attached table in annex)

The technology implementation has initially to be determined in order to identify the potential bottlenecks it might create on the sourcing of a raw material rather than another. To determine this implementation determination, likelihood hypothesis have been taken (described below).

These hypotheses supported the determination of:

- the recognition of what is to be thought critical (i.e. raw material) and what would be less
- a “deadline” for the technology to be implemented by that date.

Determination of criticality by main raw material (column R, of each sheet – see attached table in annex)

The raw material’s sourcing potential bottlenecks will determine the criticality, and this is determined based on two elements:

- the *technologies needs* in terms of raw materials
- the potential *date of implementation* of the concerned technology and thus the need for the related raw materials.

Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: Align with Technology Readiness Levels from ERJU MAWP, March 2022

Here the objective is to assess the likelihood of each innovation to reach operational status by 2030 based on its projected Technology Readiness Level (TRL), as detailed in ERJU MAWP.

Indeed, Railway technologies, like any other technologies, progress incrementally until reaching their operational environment (i.e. being implemented and serving the market). With technology stages, i.e. readiness levels, clearly identify we will be able to cross the information between the raw material criticality and the technology readiness in order to determine the overall foreseen criticalities for the railway sourcing industry up to the SME level eventually.

The Technology Readiness Levels (TRL) are a type of measurement system used to assess the maturity level of a particular technology. Each technology project is evaluated against the parameters for each technology level and is then assigned a TRL rating based on the projects progress. There are nine technology readiness levels. TRL 1 is the lowest and TRL 9 is the highest. Here below a short description of the various levels:

- **TRL 1:** *Basic principles observed*
- **TRL 2:** *Technology concept formulated*
- **TRL 3:** *Experimental proof of concept*
- **TRL 4:** *Technology validated in lab*
- **TRL 5:** *Technology validated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies)*
- **TRL 6:** *Technology demonstrated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies)*
- **TRL 7:** *System prototype demonstration in operational environment*
- **TRL 8:** *System complete and qualified*
- **TRL 9:** *Actual system proven in operational environment (competitive manufacturing in the case of key enabling technologies; or in space)*

For our analysis purpose, we based it on the Europe's Rail Joint Undertaking Multi-Annual Work Programme, Version 2.0, from 1st March 2022, as it will the most accurately reflect the technological and material demands expected by 2030. Therefore we hypothesised that:

- a) the TRL described for each FP's innovation in the ERJU MAWP are the ones to be taken into account
- b) these TRL levels would be the minimum level achieved, as we know that they have been determined and published on March 2022, and since the industry and the press is fully aware of the extended times that have been required for all FP, pushing further all deadlines.

Given this staggered implementation, and ERJU MAWP input for TRL, these assumptions allowed us to model the requirements based on the most advanced and resource-intensive iteration of each technology.

The 3 qualifiers we modelled are the “High likelihood”, “Moderate likelihood” and “Low likelihood” of a technology to be implemented by 2030. These were determined as per the below hypotheses:

<p>“High likelihood”, is considered when the technology has been commercialized by 2030, i.e. TRL level is at “9” by 2027</p>
<p>“Moderate likelihood”, is considered when the technology would have passed the prototype stage (and its potential reiterations) by 2030, i.e. TRL level “7” identified is only foreseen, by the ERJU MAWP of March 2022, for 2027</p>
<p>“Low likelihood”, is considered when the technology is, at best, foreseen to be demonstrated by 2027, i.e. TRL level is at best at “6” by 2027</p>

Hypothesis 2: Align with Critical Raw Material Act List, May 2024.

The identification of what should be considered critical and what would be less, or not, is key to determine the criticality of the raw material needed by the railway sourcing industry. For this task and its subsequent analysis, the hypothesis was taken to follow the identified the critically based on the Critical Raw Material Act (CRMA) published as EU Regulation on 3 May 2024 and entered into force on 23 May 2024.

Hypothesis 3: The determination of the overall foreseen criticality

To determine the overall critically of the raw materials concerned by the implementation of an innovative technology, the 4 qualifiers selected were the “Very High criticality”, “High criticality”, “Moderate criticality” and “Low criticality” and these were determined as per the below hypothesis:

<p>“Very High criticality”, is considered when:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the raw material concerned faces an increased usage and is part of the CRMA list - the technology has a “High likelihood” to happen by 2030
<p>“High criticality”, is considered when:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the raw material concerned faces an increased usage and is part of the CRMA list - the technology has a “Moderate” to “High likelihood” to happen by 2030.
<p>Moderate criticality, is considered in two possibilities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the raw material concerned faces an increased usage and is part of the CRMA list - the technology has a “Moderate” to “Low likelihood” to happen by 2030 <p>or</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the raw material concerned is on a stable usage and is part of the CRMA list - but still the technology has a “High likelihood” to happen by 2030 <p>or</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the raw material concerned is on a stable usage and is not part of the CRMA list - but still the technology has a “Moderate” to “High likelihood” to happen by 2030
<p>Low criticality, is considered when:</p>

- the raw material concerned faces an **increased usage** and is part of the CRMA list
- the technology has a “*Low likelihood*” to happen by 2030
(for example in FP2, for V2X, the TRL is predicted at “8” by 2027 and only for GoA2)
- or
- the raw material concerned is on a **stable usage** and is not part of the CRMA list
- but still the technology has a “*Moderate*” to “*Low likelihood*” to happen by 2030
- or
- the raw material concerned is on a **stable usage** and is part of the CRMA list
- but still the technology has a “*High likelihood*” to happen by 2030

These hypotheses enabled us to concentrate on the most impactful elements of each introduced technology, optimizing the analysis for clarity and relevance.

Steps in Analysis

- 1.** Identify the **trend usage** of the new components / raw materials (column L): For each FP’s main innovation, once the components and its relative raw material were identified an analysis was conducted to identify if the usage was increased or stable.
- 2.** Identify the **TRL level** for each of the innovative technologies (column P): For each FP’s, the main innovation (and its more advanced version when the case) was identified based on ERJU documentation and industry inputs.
- 3.** Determine the **overall foreseen criticality** for the rail supply chain (column R): Here the analysis of the raw materials criticality was based on demand trends and the likelihood of related innovations to be implemented, identifying potential supply chain risks by 2030. For each FP’s main innovation, the raw material usage variation (column L) was crossed with the relevant raw material critically (CRMA), that was then crossed with the TRL level of the concerned technology by 2030 (column P) in order to come up with the overall foreseen criticality for the rail industry.

This comprehensive approach not only mapped the material and technological needs essential to LEADER 2030 objectives but also introduced a forward-looking analysis. By linking technology readiness with material demand, the methodology highlighted critical areas of impact on the sourcing chain.

5.6.2. The criticalities output

Overall, the two meaningful findings from stakeholder consultations confirm a **shift in TRL commercialization timelines—while some flagship technologies may reach TRL9 by 2031, FP6 and FP7 will struggle to exceed TRL7**. To mitigate supply chain risks, a strong reliance on COTS (Commercial-Off-The-Shelf) solutions was recommended by the interviewees, ensuring component availability and resilience against importation, transportation hazards, and stock shortages. This underscores the need for strategic adaptation in procurement and manufacturing, balancing innovation with supply chain stability.

While from the data analysis here is what has been extracted as criticalities for each of the Flagship Projects:

5.6.2.1. FP1: MOTIONAL - Mobility Management Multimodal Environment and Digital Enablers – Criticalities

The FP1 (MOTIONAL) is advancing digital mobility solutions but requires robust data architectures and cybersecurity frameworks.

As a result, the project predominantly encounters "High" to "Very High" criticalities concerning the raw materials required for technologies enabling ERTMS Level 3, specifically through:

- Traffic Management (incl. Train integrity),
- Capacity Planning versus Operations,
- Mobility Orchestration,
- TMS Scalability.

This materializes mainly in very high demands for rare earth elements such as Gallium, Neodymium (a LREE), Lithium, and for the metals demand are high for Copper and Steel (see presentation at InnoTrans 2024 in the Annex).

5.6.2.2. FP2: R2DATO - Rail to Digital automated up to autonomous train operation – Criticalities

The FP2 (R2DATO), which focuses on automation, is heavily dependent on sensor fusion, AI, and resilient communication systems (FRMCS/5G), with integration challenges across legacy infrastructure.

As a result, the project primarily encounters "High" to "Very High" criticalities concerning the raw materials required for technologies enabling ERTMS Level 3, as outlined in the above FP1 description. This is further intensified by the criticalities associated with Advanced Train Control and Monitoring Systems (TCMS) technologies, which rely heavily on communication and AI capabilities.

In contrast, for Autonomous Train Operations (ATO), Advanced Train Communications (ATC), and emerging decision-support technologies, the criticality of raw materials is notably less significant for 2030, with assessments ranging from moderate to low.

This materializes mainly in very high demands for rare earth elements such as Gallium, and for the metals demand are very high for Copper (see presentation at InnoTrans 2024).

5.6.2.3. FP3: IAM4RAIL - A Holistic and Integrated Asset Management for Europe's Rail System – Criticalities

The FP3 (IAM4RAIL) emphasizes predictive maintenance using IoT and Digital Twins, necessitating industry-wide interoperability standards.

For this Flagship Project, all identified technologies and their associated raw materials are categorized as having "high criticality." This includes advanced asset management, predictive maintenance (such as condition-based monitoring), and operations, as well as real-time simulation and monitoring of railway assets.

This materializes mainly in very high demands for rare earth elements such as Gallium, Neodymium (a LREE), Terbium and Dysprosium (were both are HREE). For the metals demands are high for Copper (see presentation at InnoTrans 2024).

5.6.2.4. FP4: RAIL4EARTH - Sustainable and Green Rail Systems – Criticalities

The FP4 (RAIL4EARTH) prioritizes sustainable materials, energy-efficient propulsion, and circular economy strategies, yet scalability and cost efficiency remain key concerns.

Therefore, while energy-related technologies (such as alternative energy and propulsion systems, energy storage systems, and green electrification) are categorized as having a "moderate criticality" level, Smart Renewable Energy-Powered Stations remain at a "high criticality" level.

In contrast, technologies enabling ERTMS Level 3, as described in the FP1 framework, face predominantly "high" to "very high" criticality levels due to the reliance on raw materials required for advanced train control and monitoring systems (TCMS). This includes technologies involving communication and AI capabilities, which further elevate the criticality of the raw materials involved.

Overall, for FP4 technologies, the majority of Technology Readiness Levels (TRL) are projected to fall between '6' and '7' by 2027, meaning they will, at best, have reached the prototype stage.

This materializes mainly in very high demands for rare earth elements such as Lithium, Gallium, in high demands for Yttrium, Europium and Terbium (all HREE), and for the metals demand are high mainly for Copper (see presentation at InnoTrans 2024).

5.6.2.5. FP5: TRANS4M-R - Transforming Europe's Rail Freight – Criticalities

The FP5 (TRANS4M-R) relies on AI-driven freight operations and smart logistics, requiring automated handling systems and resilient freight corridors.

Therefore, technologies associated with Full Digital Freight Train Operations predominantly face “High” to “Very High” criticalities (specifically DAC-related technologies), with the exception of yard-related technologies, which are assessed at a more “Moderate” level of criticality.

For Seamless Rail Freight and Innovative Freight Assets, the criticality level is generally “Moderate,” although “High criticality” is anticipated for raw materials required for semiconductors and batteries.

This materializes mainly in very high demands for rare earth elements such as Lithium and Aluminium Bauxite and for the metals demand are very high for Copper and Steel (see presentation at InnoTrans 2024).

5.6.2.6. FP6: FUTURE - Delivering innovative rail services to revitalise capillary lines and regional rail services – Criticalities

The FP6 (FUTURE) aims to revitalize capillary networks and while it will align with the criticality of the previous flagships it will struggle with funding and feasibility, delaying large-scale adoption.

Therefore, for this flagship, the criticality has been assessed as “Low” (refer to column U in the annexed Excel sheet). This is primarily due to the focus on low-cost solutions rather than high-cost innovations. As a result, the adoption of expensive technologies and associated raw materials is unlikely.

5.6.2.7. FP7: Pods4Rail - Development of New Mobility Solutions with Modular Pods – Criticalities

As mentioned during the interview consultation around FP7 *"Firstly, a technological maturity is more difficult to reach for such innovative systems compared to the evolution of existing systems. In terms of operations and traffic coordination of the innovations in FP7, simulation tools will be most valuable to develop guidelines and to evaluate their performance, as the full systems will not be operational, to have real-world tests. Therefore, a TRL up to 5 can be foreseen."*

The FP7 (PODS4RAIL) explores modular pod-based transport, facing significant technological and regulatory hurdles, making it unlikely to reach TRL 7 by 2030. In fact, the entire flagship has been identified as having very low criticality, as most of the technologies are expected to achieve a TRL between ‘5’ and ‘6’ at best. This indicates that optimistically these technologies will be validated in specific environments and potentially demonstrated by 2031.

5.7. Recommendations to OEMS, suppliers and moreover to SMEs (Column T)

Amongst its engagements, LEADER 2030 aims to support and enhance the EU Rail initiative's engagement with suppliers, particularly Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs). Within this framework, our objective is to provide guidance and clarity on the pathways to transforming the European railway system into a sustainable, efficient, and digitally connected network by 2030, with a specific focus on empowering SMEs.

Based on the achieved analysis from the 'needs part' and the 'disruption part' as required by the objective of this project and its work package (see chapter 4 Objective / Aim), and given the specification of the criticality induced by each technology innovation on the raw material related to it, we will here detail flagship project by flagship project the impact on IMPACT ON OEMS/SUPPLIERS.

Overall, across all flagships, the primary disruptions include:

1. **Digitalization** – OEMs must transition from mechanical and analog systems to **AI-driven, IoT-connected platforms**.
2. **Automation** – A growing need for **self-diagnosing, self-driving, and self-maintaining rail systems**.
3. **Sustainability** – Demand for **hydrogen, battery, and lightweight materials** disrupts traditional rolling stock and propulsion supply chains.
4. **Cybersecurity & Data Analytics** – Increased reliance on **real-time data analytics, cloud computing, and cybersecurity frameworks**.

Based on these disruptions, overall needs have emerged for both OEMs and Suppliers (T1 to 3 and SMEs).

- **OEMs:** Will need to innovate and adapt to new technologies such as DAC systems, intelligent control systems, and eco-friendly materials. They will play a crucial role in developing and integrating these new components.
- **Tiers (including SMEs):** SMEs will be critical in developing specialized components and technologies, such as sensors, AI systems, and energy storage solutions. They will need to collaborate closely with OEMs and leverage funding and research opportunities.

This comprehensive approach will require coordinated efforts from all stakeholders, including OEMs, SMEs, research institutions, and policymakers, to achieve the ambitious targets set for 2030 and beyond. Here below, the impact to OEMs, suppliers and SMEs is detailed in terms of impact, opportunities to SME and overall disruption of each flagship.

5.7.1.FP1: MOTIONAL – Impact on OEM/Suppliers/SMEs (Column T)

Here, the growth of train detection and planning systems will significantly impact OEMs and suppliers, particularly in software development, real-time forecasting, and network responsiveness. The growing need for advanced train integrity monitoring devices will require the design and manufacture of innovative onboard and trackside solutions, urging suppliers to invest in high-precision sensors and fail-proof communication technologies. Also, the rising intricacy of transport networks, mainly in cross-border operations, will drive demand for interoperable components and systems, boosting OEMs to develop standardized interfaces and connectivity solutions.

The intensification of digitalization in traffic management will also create opportunities and challenges. Cybersecurity will become a critical focus, necessitating robust encryption, authentication mechanisms, and threat detection systems tailored to railway infrastructure. Suppliers specializing in control systems will see increased demand for sophisticated signaling and automation components.

Meanwhile, SMEs will find openings in niche markets, mainly in GNSS-based positioning, inertial measurement units, and cybersecurity solutions. The growing reliance on standardized connectors for command, control, and data communication will further open doors for expert manufacturing and integration services, enabling SMEs to offer flexible solutions that align with mobility needs.

In summary, the impact, opportunities and disruptions can be recapped as below:

Impact on OEMs/Suppliers:

- More advanced train detection systems to improve train planning and real-time forecast of transport demand.
- Increased demand for sophisticated signaling and control system components.
- Design and manufacture of advanced train integrity monitoring devices.
- Development of continuous communication networks for improved cooperative planning across borders.
- Development of interoperable components and systems to boost cross-border rail integration.
- Intensification of digitalization and partial automation of manual processes.
- Integration and connection to last-mile (accession lines/shunting/yards/terminals) slot planning via interfaces.
- More robust cybersecurity measures tailored to railway systems.

Opportunities for SMEs:

- Niche areas like GNSS-based train positioning, inertial measurement units, and cybersecurity solutions.
- Increased demand for standardized connectors for communication, command, and control data.

Disruption:

Traditional traffic management hardware suppliers may face obsolescence unless they pivot toward software and data-driven solutions.

5.7.2.FP2: R2DATO – Impact on OEM/Suppliers/SMEs (Column T)

In this flagship, we identified that the push towards higher levels of automation in railway operations will transform the landscape for OEMs and suppliers, demanding new ATO (Automatic Train Operation) solutions capable of real-time decision-making, environmental supervision, and obstacle detection. These developments will require precise positioning systems and AI-driven safety mechanisms, leading to increased collaboration between hardware manufacturers and software developers. The emergence of remote driving and command capabilities for depots, low-traffic lines, and fallback operations will also necessitate the adaptation of control systems to next-generation communication networks.

To support the reliability of these autonomous systems, modeling techniques for verification and validation will gain prominence, pushing suppliers to develop Digital-Twins and simulation frameworks. Moreover, the shift toward unstaffed vehicles will drive demand for enhanced CCTV and sensor-based passenger information systems, integrating AI-powered hazard detection, remote assistance, and predictive maintenance.

SMEs will play a crucial role in developing collaborative connectivity solutions, particularly in FRMCS, V2X, and 5G-enabled cooperative awareness technologies, ensuring seamless real-time communication and operational efficiency.

In summary, the impact, opportunities and disruptions can be recapped as below:

Impact on OEMs/Suppliers:

- Development of new ATO solutions for automated driving and decision-making, integrating AI-based environment supervising systems.
- Implementation of remote driving and command for depots, low-traffic lines, fallback operations, and shunting, adapted to communication systems.
- Advanced modeling techniques for development, verification, and validation solutions.
- New generation of CCTV, sensors, and passenger information systems with AI-driven hazard detection and remote assistance.

Opportunities for SMEs:

- Collaborative connectivity solutions integrating FRMCS, V2X, and 5G to enhance cooperative awareness.

Disruption:

Traditional mechanical control systems will decline in demand, forcing suppliers to adapt to digital, AI-based automation and real-time edge computing.

5.7.3.FP3: IAM4RAIL – Impact on OEM/Suppliers/SMEs (Column T)

Here, with the Flagship Project 3 we witness how the evolution of asset management in rail will lead to a substantial shift towards energy-efficient, self-diagnostic components, enabling seamless interoperability and data exchange between subsystems. Suppliers will need to innovate low-energy consumption components that can autonomously monitor and transmit operational data. Additionally, real-time inspection tools with enhanced accuracy and reduced labor requirements will become essential, creating demand for high-performance sensors and automation solutions.

OEMs and suppliers will also need to respond to increasing expectations for on-demand, fast-delivery spare parts, particularly in small production batches. This shift will encourage the adoption of advanced manufacturing techniques, such as 3D-printing and just-in-time logistics. Robotics applications will continue to gain traction, leading suppliers to explore automation for maintenance and operational support. Moreover, the development of new wireless network backbones will reduce maintenance costs and unlock new digital services for railway operators.

SMEs, in particular, will find opportunities in BIM-based digital twins and predictive maintenance solutions, shaping the next generation of asset management.

In summary, the impact, opportunities and disruptions can be recapped as below:

Impact on OEMs/Suppliers:

- Development of self-diagnostic components with low- or zero-energy consumption.
- Advanced inspection tools for shorter inspection times, increased accuracy, and reduced staff requirements, with real-time interoperable results.
- On-demand, fast-delivery spare parts production in small quantities.
- Exploration of robotic applications for various use cases.
- Development of a new Wireless Network Backbone for trains to reduce maintenance needs and enable new services.

Opportunities for SMEs:

- Increased demand for BIM modeling to support Digital Twin development.

Disruption:

Suppliers of conventional maintenance equipment may need to transition towards sensor-enabled predictive maintenance tools or risk losing market relevance.

5.7.4.FP4: RAIL4EARTH – Impact on OEM/Suppliers/SMEs (Column T)

In the case of the Flagship Project 4, the sustainability will drive significant changes for OEMs and suppliers, with a focus on the development of advanced onboard energy storage systems and standardized recharge interfaces. The push for holistic energy management will require new solutions tailored to specific railway environments, including stations, yards, terminals, and infrastructure components. Suppliers will need to integrate innovative energy storage technologies while ensuring compatibility across different railway networks.

The shift towards sustainable and attractive rail vehicles will also place greater emphasis on design improvements, including accessibility, service optimization, and pandemic-resilient interiors. Additionally, the demand for energy harvesting systems will grow, particularly for optimizing sensor autonomy and reducing reliance on external power sources.

SMEs can contribute significantly to this transformation by developing electro-mechanical components designed for low consumption, low emissions, noise reduction, and vibration control, ensuring that sustainable rail solutions meet both regulatory and operational expectations.

In summary, the impact, opportunities and disruptions can be recapped as below:

Impact on OEMs/Suppliers:

- Development of various onboard energy storage systems and standardized recharge interfaces.
- Holistic energy management systems considering specific rail installations.
- Enhancing vehicle capacity for sustainability, accessibility, and pandemic prevention.
- Design of energy harvesting systems to optimize sensor autonomy.

Opportunities for SMEs:

- Focus on electro-mechanical components for low consumption, emissions, noise, and vibrations.

Disruption:

Traditional diesel engine suppliers must pivot to battery and hydrogen technologies, and new materials will disrupt steel-dominant manufacturing chains.

5.7.5.FP5: TRANS4M-R – Impact on OEM/Suppliers/SMEs (Column T)

In the case of the Flagship Project 5, the impacts are generated as the freight sector will experience a digital revolution, with OEMs and suppliers expected to develop new customer platforms that provide real-time logistics chain management. This transformation will require extensive data integration, AI-powered forecasting, and seamless multimodal solutions, driving the demand for intelligent freight planning and dispatching tools. The need for digitalized and automated rail freight operations will further push suppliers to create interoperable components that enhance operational efficiency across different stakeholders.

A key area of development will be the design and production of multi-functional and modular wagons, enabling flexible freight handling and improved load management.

SMEs will find opportunities in sensor development, actuators, and advanced communication modules, particularly as Digital Automatic Coupler (DAC) technology becomes a critical component of rail freight. The adoption of DAC will require OEMs and suppliers to upgrade production capabilities, investing in precision manufacturing, advanced electronics, and high-performance materials. Additionally, as DAC systems demand continuous maintenance, software updates, and diagnostics, SMEs will have a crucial role in offering specialized aftermarket services, ensuring long-term sustainability and operational efficiency.

In summary, the impact, opportunities and disruptions can be recapped as below:

Impact on OEMs/Suppliers:

- Development of digital customer platforms for real-time logistics management.
- Identification and design of multimodal solutions to facilitate transportation.
- Digitalized and automated rail freight operation tools for seamless coordination among all sector players.
- Design and production of multi-functional and modular wagons.

Opportunities for SMEs:

- Niche areas like sensors, actuators, communication modules, and specialized coupler materials.
- Investment in new manufacturing technologies for Digital Automatic Coupling (DAC) systems.
- Specialized aftermarket services for DAC maintenance, diagnostics, and software updates.

Disruption:

Manual coupling systems and legacy freight management tools face rapid obsolescence, pushing suppliers to invest in automation and connectivity.

5.7.6.FP6: FUTURE – Impact on OEM/Suppliers/SMEs (Column T)

For the Flagship Project 6, the modernization of regional rail services will create a diverse set of opportunities and challenges for OEMs and suppliers, incorporating elements from FP1 through FP5, except for DAC-related innovations (as previously mention and visible on the excel table sheet in annex). Suppliers will need to develop and manufacture advanced train detection systems, automated train control mechanisms, and intelligent network planning solutions to enhance regional rail efficiency. Also, energy storage solutions, real-time freight management platforms, and modular vehicle designs will play a crucial role in revitalizing capillary lines and improving multimodal connectivity.

For SMEs, this transformation presents opportunities in digital connectivity, lightweight vehicle components, and standardized communication interfaces. The focus on automation, energy efficiency, and responsive transport network planning will require suppliers to align with evolving digital standards, ensuring that new rail solutions remain interoperable and adaptable to regional needs.

In summary, the **impact on OEMs/Suppliers** is the summation of FP1 to FP5 impacts except DAC-related technologies. The **opportunities for SMEs** is the summation of FP1 to FP5 impacts except DAC-related technologies. While the **disruption** will concern the small-scale regional rail suppliers must integrate modular and flexible rail solutions or risk being left behind.

5.7.7.FP7: Pods4Rail – Impact on OEM/Suppliers/SMEs (Column T)

The emergence of modular pod-based mobility solutions will integrate various technological advancements from FP1 through FP5, including DAC-related innovations. OEMs and suppliers will be tasked with developing scalable and interoperable pod systems that seamlessly integrate into existing rail infrastructure while offering flexible passenger and freight solutions. The need for energy-efficient, autonomous, and AI-driven pods will drive demand for lightweight materials, high-performance batteries, and intelligent onboard control systems.

Additionally, the push for fully automated rail freight and passenger transport will encourage the development of multimodal solutions that enhance connectivity between rail, road, and urban transit networks.

SMEs will play a pivotal role in designing specialized sensors, actuators, and connectivity modules, ensuring smooth data exchange between pod vehicles and railway control centers. The growing reliance on DAC for modular freight operations will further create opportunities for SMEs to provide aftermarket services, including maintenance, diagnostics, and software updates.

In summary, the **impact on OEMs/Suppliers** is the summation of FP1 to FP5 impacts including DAC-related technologies. The **opportunities for SMEs** are the summation of FP1 to FP5 impacts including DAC-related technologies. While the **disruption** will be faced by traditional rolling stock suppliers who may struggle unless they invest in urban mobility tech and small-scale automation.

5.8. Overall Conclusion for the Work Package 2 of LEADER 2030

LEADER 2030 Work Package 2 (WP2) plays a pivotal role in defining the technological advancements and supply chain transformations that will shape Europe's rail supply industry by 2030 and beyond. With a strong emphasis on resilience, sustainability, autonomy, and competitiveness, WP2 provides a detailed roadmap of emerging innovations, critical raw material dependencies, and potential supply chain disruptions. This effort is essential to future-proof the European rail ecosystem, ensuring its ability to adapt to evolving regulatory, environmental, and operational challenges.

WP2 is directly aligned with the EU's strategic objectives (ERJU MAWP) of digitalization, sustainability, and multimodal efficiency. Through a structured analysis of the Flagship Areas (FAs) and their associated Flagship Projects (FPs), WP2 outlines the essential transformations required across the sector. The findings ultimately highlight how OEMs and suppliers must adapt to a rapidly changing landscape, driven by automation, integrated asset management, and green energy solutions. These shifts demand greater standardization, interoperability, and a shift toward sustainable material sourcing, ensuring that technological evolution is supported by a robust and future-ready supply chain.

A key achievement of WP2 is its comprehensive mapping of railway innovations to be implemented through the EU-RAIL program. The study identifies the essential technologies, components, and raw materials—ranging from metals to rare earth elements—that will be critical for these advancements. Additionally, the analysis highlights components, subsystems, and software solutions that will become obsolete or significantly reduced in importance due to the adoption of next-generation technologies. Beyond just technological needs, WP2 pinpoints potential disruptions and obsolescence risks, providing a clear assessment of the criticality of each innovative technology required across the flagship projects.

Another major insight from WP2 is the shifting dynamics within the supply industry, with a needed growing role for SMEs in niche technology areas such as cybersecurity, predictive maintenance, AI-driven automation, and modular rolling stock components. By identifying key raw material dependencies and alternative sourcing strategies, WP2 directly addresses the pressing challenge of securing Europe's industrial autonomy in rail manufacturing. The increasing focus on energy efficiency, digitalization, and automation underscores the need for stronger collaboration across the rail ecosystem, ensuring that suppliers can effectively meet future market demands.

Ultimately, WP2 provides a strategic foundation for a competitive, autonomous, and sustainable rail supply industry. By fostering innovation, strengthening supply chain resilience, and ensuring alignment with the EU's long-term transport vision, WP2 is hopefully paving the way for the next work packages of LEADER 2030 to contribute to Europe's leading role for the global railway transformation.

5.9. Consultation – Approach & Methodology

To complement the desk research analysis of the innovations outlined in the European Rail Joint Undertaking (ERJU) Master Plan and Multi-Annual Work Plan (MAWP), a direct consultation approach was recommended and implemented. This method involved systematically engaging each Flagship Project Coordinator to obtain first-hand insights into the status, outcomes, and future technological requirements of their projects, including raw material dependencies and supply chain implications.

In addition to these consultations, Railenium proposed extending the outreach to key industry players through targeted interviews. This broader engagement aimed to enhance the overall analysis by integrating industry perspectives on innovation trends, obsolescence risks, and supply chain challenges expected by 2030.

A structured questionnaire was designed to gather in-depth insights from industry stakeholders. The collected responses served to map current and emerging innovations, identifying components at risk of becoming obsolete, and addressing supply chain constraints. Also, these findings contributed to validate the research approach and refine the interpretation of key ERJU documents through the interview focus groups.

Methodology

Systematic Approach of Each Flagship Project and More

The seven (7) Flagship Project Coordinators and four (4) EU projects have been approached to contribute to LEADER 2030 WP2 analysis of the rail industry. Here are the Projects concerned:

Type	Segment	Company (/EU FP project)
EU-FP1	Freight & Mainline	<u>MOTIONAL (ERTMS)</u>
EU-FP2	Freight & Mainline	<u>R2DATO (ATO over ETCS)</u>
EU-FP3	Freight & Mainline	<u>IAM4RAIL (Asset Monitoring)</u>
EU-FP4	Freight & Mainline	<u>Rail4Earth (Green)</u>
EU-FP5	Freight	<u>TRANS4M-R (Freight)</u>
EU-FP6	Freight & Mainline	<u>FUTURE (Capillary lines)</u>
EU-FP7	Mainline	<u>Pods4Rail (Future Mobility)</u>
EU-project	Freight & Mainline	<u>Academics4Rail</u>
EU-project	Freight & Mainline	<u>ESEP4Freight (WebPlatform)</u>
EU-project	Freight & Mainline	<u>InBridge4EU (Bridges)</u>
EU-project	Freight & Mainline	<u>RAIL4CITIES (Stations)</u>

Out of all these contacted project heads only 8 participated to our interview, details of which are in the respective interviews notes. Unfortunately, the Flagship Project 1- MOTIONAL, Flagship Project 2- R2DATO and Flagship Project 4- Rail4Earth could not be interviewed.

Complementary Approach with Rail Industry Main Players

On top of the expected Flagship Project Coordinators consultation, the rail industry main players were approach to provide an operational insight to each flagship target. This allowed to sense how the industry market sensed the technology innovation disruption and its impact to their supply chain. Here are the main players approached:

Type	Segment	Company (/EU FP project)
Leasing	Freight & Mainline	<u>Railpool</u>
OEM	Freight & Mainline	<u>Alstom</u>
OEM	Freight & Mainline	<u>CAF</u>
OEM	Freight & Mainline	<u>SIEMENS</u>
OEM	Freight & Mainline	<u>SKODA Digital</u>
OEM	Mainline	<u>TALGO</u>
OEM	Freight & Mainline	<u>MHI</u>
OEM	Freight & Mainline	<u>THALES / Hitachi</u>
Operator	Mainline	<u>Eurostar</u>
Operator	Freight & Mainline	<u>SBB</u>
Operator	Freight & Mainline	<u>SNCF Réseau</u>
<i>Operator</i>	Mainline	<u>NS</u>
<i>Operator</i>	Freight & Mainline	<u>SNCF</u>
Supplier T0	Freight & Mainline	<u>Wabtec</u>
Supplier T1	Freight & Mainline	<u>Bosch</u>
Supplier T1	Freight & Mainline	<u>DELLNER</u>
Supplier T1	Freight & Mainline	<u>SKF</u>
Supplier T2		<u>RAILNOVA</u>
Supplier T3	Freight & Mainline	<u>CEDA</u>
Supplier T3	Freight & Mainline	<u>The Signalling Company</u>
z-Other	Freight & Mainline	<u>DLR</u>
z-Other	Freight & Mainline	<u>UIC</u>
z-Other	Freight & Mainline	<u>UNIFE</u>

Out of all these contacted Rail industry players, **24 participated to our interviews**, details of which are in the respective interviews notes.

Below, the questionnaire and its section are detailed.

5.9.1. Questionnaire for Mapping Innovation Products/Components to 2030

The questionnaire was divided in 4 sections, each of them serving a specific purpose, details of which are described below

5.9.1.1. Section 1: Overall Presentation

This sections aimed at presenting:

- the LEADER 2030 project, its objective and the ones of the WP2

LEADER 2030 – WP2 Interview guide

PREPARED BY RAILENIUM - JEMYLIA RAIMBAULT | June 2024

LEADER
Learnings for European Autonomy to Deliver Europe's Rail in 2030

Get ready for 2030's Rail industry supply needs

RAILENIUM, the French rail supply industry's Institute for Technology Research, is a key participant, amongst others, in the **LEADER 2030 project**. Supported by Europe's Rail JU, this initiative focuses on "Learnings for European Autonomy to Deliver Europe's Rail in 2030."

RAILENIUM, with its expertise in market-driven innovation projects, has been appointed to lead Work Package 2 (wp2) of LEADER 2030. WP2 goal is to **analyze ERJU technological innovations** and deliver the "Map of Railway Needs in 2030" (deliverable 2). The focus will be on the components and raw materials (Tse1 to Tse-3 level) that will affect supply capacity, including enablers and obstacles, essential for European Rail leadership. This study will involve interviewing ERJU members and project partners, including Flagship project coordinators, operators, infrastructure organizations, OEMs, and suppliers (p1e-13).

The interview guide is thus articulated in three parts.

Part A-Listening to you: aims at understanding the relevant output status of your Flagship area

Part B-Your Innovations: aims at extracting your key innovations to reach the Flagship objectives

Part C-Foreseen issues: aims at identifying what new technology implementation predicts.

What's in for you?
Securing Europe's Rail flagship innovations by developing a more resilient and prepared supply chain, thereby avoiding bottlenecks and disruptions.

RAILENIUM

- agree on the purpose of the Flagship Project, the EU-Rail Project or the rail main player role

Flagship Project XX
Title of the Flagship Project

The main objective is to XXXXXX This overarching goal will be pursued through XXXX

These goals are to be achieved through a
..... This project will also address
*
.....

Let's dive into the output and their need / pressure on the Rail industry supply chain!

LEADER 2030 | WFO - RAILENIUM | RAIL INDUSTRY NEEDS 2030 RAILENIUM

- Identify the interviewee(s)

4

Interviewee details

/Name _____
 /Firstname _____

/Position _____

/Country _____

/Entity's name _____

/Category _____

<input type="checkbox"/> OEM (O)	<input type="checkbox"/> Operator (SO/PO)	<input type="checkbox"/> Supplier (S1-3)
<input type="checkbox"/> Mainline (M)	<input type="checkbox"/> Freight (F)	<input type="checkbox"/> Leasing (L)
<input type="checkbox"/> Industry (I)	<input type="checkbox"/> Association (A)	<input type="checkbox"/> University (U)
<input type="checkbox"/> EU-FA (FA)	<input type="checkbox"/> Rail Organization (R)	<input type="checkbox"/> Other (Ot)

LEADER 2030 | WP2 – SAU2023A | MAP RAILWAYS NEEDS 2030

RAILENIUM

5.9.1.2. Section 2: PART A -Listening to you – Today’s status

This section aimed at understanding the current state of the concerned project or stakeholder towards the forthcoming innovations. The interview’s open questions materialized as below to engage conversation rather than opting for closed questions narrowing the outcome. Here is the illustration of the interview guidelines for **Today’s status**:

LEADER 2030 – RAILENIUM / WP2 – Interview Guidelines for experts/Euroforum 5

LEADER PART A
Learnings for European
Autonomy to Deliver Europe's
Rail in 2030

Listening to you – Today's status

Flagship status

What can you share already?
Any main obstacles?
Any specific opportunity?

ERJU MAWP identified innovations

Do you confirm all of them?
Have you found other ones worth raising?
Do you see less of them?

**“ UNDERSTANDING YOUR ENVIRONMENT
YOUR STATUS, YOUR OUTPUT SO FAR.**

LEADER 2030 | WP2 – RAILENIUM | MAWP RAILWAYS NEEDS 2030

5.9.1.3. Section 3: PART B - Your innovations – Flagship key ones

This section aimed at extracting from the concerned project or stakeholder their key innovations. The interview's open questions materialized as below to engage conversation rather than opting for closed questions narrowing the outcome.

Here is the illustration of the interview guidelines for **Flagship key innovations**:

LEADER 2030 - WIP2 - RAILNIUM | WP2 - Interview Guidelines for digital knowledge 6

LEADER PART B
Learnings for European Autonomy to Deliver Europe's Rail in 2030
Your innovations –Flagship key ones

Modular and standardized vehicle concepts

.....

Cost-efficient infrastructure components
- wireless train detection systems
-
-

.....

Customer-centric digital services

.....

others

.....

**” SENSING WHAT IS KEY
TO ENSURE VIABILITY, DECREASED COSTS.**

LEADER 2030 | WP2 – RAILNIUM | NMP RAILWAYS NEEDS 2030

5.9.1.4. Section 4: PART C - Foreseen issues – up to sourcing

This section aimed at extracting the potential issues up to sourcing needs or disruptions. The interview’s open questions materialized as below to engage conversation rather than opting for closed questions narrowing the outcome.

Here is the illustration of the interview guidelines for **Foreseen issues – up to sourcing**:

LEADER 2030 - RAILENIUM | PART C - Foreseen issues - up to sourcing
7

PART C

Foreseen issues – up to sourcing

- A. Technological integration**
- B. Regulatory compliance**
- C. Adoption/ transition**
- D. Climate issues**
- E. Energy supply**

Other (please specify)

Issues related to

1. Digital Automatic Coupling (DAC)
2. European Train Control System (ETCS)
3. European Rail Traffic Management System (ERTMS)
4. Autonomous Train Operation Systems
5. Multimodal Integration Platforms
6. Track-side signal perception (Camera, ...)
7. Obstacle perception (sensors, LiDAR, ...)
8. Localization of the train (point on the map)
9. Digital map (i.e. signaling boxes, crossing, station, ...)
10. Noise/Alarm perception
11. Advanced Energy Storage Systems
12. Sustainable and Advanced Materials

Issues related to

1. Internet of Things (IoT)
2. Artificial Intelligence (AI)
3. Machine Learning (ML)
4. Augmented Reality (AR)
5. Advanced Robotics
6. Quantum Computing

**IDENTIFYING POTENTIAL ISSUES
TO SECURE THE INNOVATIONS.**

LEADER 2030 | 2022 - RAILENIUM | SMP RAILWAYS NEEDS 2030

6. References

Accenture (2022), *From disruption to reinvention: The future of supply chains in Europe.*

Attinasi M G, Ioannou D, Lebastard L, Morris R (2023), *“Global production and supply chain risks: insights from a survey of leading companies”*, *Economic Bulletin Boxes Issue 7-2023*, European Central Bank.

Attinasi M G, Boeckelmann L, Meunier B (2023), *Unfriendly friends: Trade and relocation effects of the US Inflation Reduction Act*, CEPR.

Bauer M, du Roy O, Sharma V (2023), *“A Forward-Thinking Approach to Open Strategic Autonomy: Navigating EU Trade Dependencies and Risk Mitigation”*, *ECIPE*, November.

Benoit F, Connell García W, Herghelegiu C, Pasimeni P (2021), *“Detecting and Analysing Supply Chain Disruptions”*, *Single Market Economy Papers*, European Commission.

Bernuy-Lopez C (2023), *“Electrolysis technologies and LCOH: current state and prospects for 2030”*, *Hydrogen Tech World*, 13 April.

Bhairavi J (2021), *“Global supply chain dependencies and disruptions · Global supply chains, national resilience, and dependency on China”*, *Project for Peaceful Competition*.

Breton T (2022), *“Neither autarchy nor dependence – more European autonomy”*, *Blog of Commissioner Thierry Breton*, 25 August.

Buysse K, Essers D (2023), *“Critical raw materials : from dependency to open strategic autonomy?”*, *NBB Economic Review*, 2023 N° 13.

Council of the European Union (2023), *Infographic - An EU critical raw materials act for the future of EU supply chains*, November.

European Central Bank (2023), *The EU's Open Strategic Autonomy from a central banking perspective. Challenges to the monetary policy landscape from a changing geopolitical environment.*

European Commission (2020a), *Communication from the Commission ‘New Industrial Strategy for Europe’*, Commission Communication, COM(2020) 102 final.

European Commission (2020b), *A new Circular Economy Action Plan For a cleaner and more competitive Europe*, Commission Communication, COM(2020) 98 final.

7. Appendix

The table compiling all the seven Flagship Projects analysis is recognized to be so huge for each of the Flagship Project that it is handed as a separate document though totally embedded in the deliverable D2.1.

LEADER 2030 Task 2.1 & 2.2 & 2.3 - Desk Search for 'Map of Railway Needs 2030'										Likelihood of technology (H/W/SW) implementation in 2030		Foreseen criticalities in 2030 (Crossing info from L & P column + CMAA list + LEADER 2030 D1.3)		IMPACT ON OEMS/ SUPPLIERS																	
FLAGSHIP AREA	FA TITLE (according to ERU MAWP)	FLAGSHIP PROJECT (according to ERU MAWP)	FP TITLE (according to ERU FP respective website)	MAIN CONCERNED TECHNOLOGY (based on ERU MAWP, FP website)	FUNCTIONALITIES (based on ERU MAWP/Flagship)	SUB-FUNCTIONALITIES (according to ERU FP website and Public Deliverables + ERTMS User Group Documentation + ERA ERTMS + UNIFE Publications)	SUB-FUNCTIONALITIES DEFINING SUB-ASSEMBLIES (detailed technologies) (Full desk search, i.e. beyond ERU FP website and Public Deliverables + ERTMS User Group Documentation + ERA ERTMS + UNIFE Publications)	(Main) COMPONENTS TO INTRODUCE	(Main) RAW MATERIALS	NEW COMPONENTS / RAW MATERIALS USAGE Old vs. New technology adoption in 2030 (i.e. vs. ERTMS 2, ERTMS 3, or none):	OLD COMPONENTS / RAW MATERIALS USAGE Old vs. New technology adoption in 2030 (i.e. vs. ERTMS 2, ERTMS 3, or none):	(Striving) ELEMENTS TO INTRODUCE	- SOFTWARE -			What can this mean to OEMs and Suppliers (with special attention to SMEs) supplying/working in the relevant segment(s) ?															
FA 1	Network management planning and control & Mobility	FP1	MOTIONAL	ERTMS L3	Traffic management, Capacity Planning vs. Operation, Mobility Orchestration, TMS Scalability	Train Reliability	GNSS (Global Navigation Satellite System) for real time train location data using satellite navigation	Satellite signal devices (e.g. Trimble B290 or Leica GS18 T) to receive satellite signals and calculate the train's position with high accuracy	Metals: Copper (Cu), Gold (Au) for connectors, Aluminum (Al) Semiconductors: Silicon (Si), Gallium arsenide (GaAs) Plastics and Polymers: For housing and protective coverings Ceramics: Used in capacitors and other components. Lithium (Li) For battery components if powered	Galium Arsenide (GaAs): More commonly used in high-frequency, high-efficiency satellite communication systems	Old silicon-based GPS modules with basic silicon diodes and early-generation MOSFETs	Positioning Algorithms i.e. using software to process satellite data and determine the train's exact position (e.g. RTK, Real-Time Kinematic corrections for enhanced accuracy)	High likelihood Moderate likelihood Low likelihood	High criticality Moderate criticality Low criticality	More advanced train detection systems to improve train planning and real time forecasts of transport demand																
																High-precision antennas (e.g. NovAtel GNSS Antenna) to ensure better signal reception	Metals: Copper (Cu) for wiring, Aluminum (Al) or Stainless Steel for structural parts Ceramics: For dielectric components Plastics and Polymers: For housing and insulation	= stable as usage of metals, plastics, and ceramics remains consistent with older technologies	= stable as usage of metals, plastics, and ceramics remains consistent with older technologies	= Moderate High (if autonomous Train, TRB)	= Moderate criticality	More advanced train detection systems with software to have responsive transport network planning, routing & capacity management									
																Inertial Measurement Units (IMU) to supplement GNSS by providing detailed motion data	IMU sensors (e.g. Honeywell HG4930 or Northrop Grumman LN-251) to provide data on acceleration and angular rates	Metals: Copper (Cu), Gold (Au) for connectors, Aluminum (Al) Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for MEMS (Micro Electro-Mechanical Systems) Plastics and Polymers: For casing and protective layers Quartz: For resonators in some sensors	= stable as quartz has been used historically in sensor technology	= Basic silicon MEMS (Micro Electro-Mechanical Systems) with less integration	Fusion Algorithms i.e. using software to combine IMU data with GNSS data to improve localization accuracy and stability	= Moderate High (if autonomous Train, TRB)	= Moderate criticality	Develop continuous communication networks to improve cooperative planning with transport multi-actors (cross borders)							
																Odometry Systems for measuring the train's speed and distance traveled to ensure accurate positioning	Wheel sensors (e.g. RBL7D) types sensors that measure wheel rotation) to calculate distance traveled	Metals: Steel (Fe), Copper (Cu) for wiring Plastics and Polymers: For housing and insulation Magnets: Rare earth metals like Neodymium (Nd)	= Neodymium - Nd (RE): Newer, more sensitive magnetic sensors rely on strong rare earth magnets	= Silicon-based GPS modules with basic silicon diodes and early-generation MOSFETs	Odometry Calculation Software to process sensor data and estimate speed & distance, integrating with other localization systems	= High (if autonomous Train, TRB)	= Very High criticality	Develop interoperable components and systems							
																End-of-Train Devices (EOTD) for monitoring the status of the last car and ensures the train's integrity	EOT Sensors (e.g. Alstom End-of-Train Monitor that check the status of the last car and communicates with the train's on-board systems)	Metals: Steel (Fe), Copper (Cu), Aluminum (Al) Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) Magnets: Rare earth metals like Neodymium (Nd)	= Neodymium - Nd: Newer, more sensitive magnetic sensors rely on strong rare earth magnets		Integrity Monitoring Software for applications that process data from EOT devices and ensure that all train segments are connected	= Moderate High (if autonomous Train, TRB)	= High criticality	More robust cybersecurity measures tailored to railway systems							
																Onboard Monitoring Systems using sensors and communication systems to verify train integrity	IoT sensors integrated into the train to monitor physical and operational parameters	Metals: Copper (Cu), Aluminum (Al), Gold (Au) Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) Plastics and Polymers: For casing and protective coverings Ceramics: For capacitors and insulators	= Enhanced Semiconductors: More advanced and specialized semiconductor materials for higher performance (usage of Silicon with smaller process nodes - 28 nanometers to reduce consumption and enhance speed without rare materials)	= Improved Plastics and Polymers: For better durability and protection in varied environmental conditions (Type 77)	Data Aggregation and Processing Software to aggregate sensor data and perform integrity checks based on AI and ML	= High	= High criticality	Integration and manufacture of the last mile (accession lines/shunting/yards/ terminals) slot planning directly via interfaces							
																Virtual Block Sections for replacing fixed block sections with flexible, dynamic blocks	Trackside Communication Units to communicate with on-board systems and manage virtual blocks	Metals: Aluminum (Al), Copper (Cu), Steel (Fe) Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) Plastics and Polymers: For housing and insulation Ceramics: For capacitors and other components	= stable as all materials usage consistent with older technology		Moving Block Algorithms i.e., Dynamic algorithms that calculate safe separation distances and train movement activity on AI-based models	= High	= Moderate criticality	SMEs can focus on niche areas like GNSS-based train positioning, inertial measurement units, and cybersecurity solutions, open interfaces to adapt to mobility demand							
																Continuous Train Control for providing real-time updates on movement authority based on train location and speed.	Onboard Controllers to receive and process real-time movement authorities	Metals: Copper (Cu), Aluminum (Al), Gold (Au) for connectors Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) Plastics and Polymers: For casing and insulation Ceramics: For capacitors and insulators	= stable as all materials usage consistent with older technology		Control Software to manage real-time updates and ensure trains follow movement authorities	= High	= Moderate criticality	SMEs can focus on the wide opportunity provided by the increased demand for standardized connectors for communication							
																ETCS for on-board Equipment for monitoring train speed and comparing it to the permitted speed, applying brakes if needed	ETCS Computers (e.g. Siemens Trainguard or Alstom ETCS equipment that handle train control and safety functions)	Metals: Copper (Cu), Aluminum (Al), Gold (Au) Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) Plastics and Polymers: For housing and insulation Ceramics: For capacitors and insulators	= stable as all materials usage consistent with older technology		ETCS Software Stack to implement the ETCS protocols, including speed monitoring and braking functions	= Moderate High (if autonomous Train, TRB)	= High criticality	SMEs can focus on the wide opportunity provided by increased demand for standardized connectors for command & control data							
																Brake Interface Unit (BIU) for connecting the ETCS onboard system with the train's braking system for automatic intervention	BIU Modules that interface between the ETCS system and the train's braking system	Metals: Copper (Cu), Aluminum (Al), Steel (Fe) Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) Plastics and Polymers: For casing and insulation Ceramics: For capacitors and insulators	= stable as all materials usage consistent with older technology		Brake Control Software to manage braking commands issued by the ETCS system	= Moderate High (if autonomous Train, TRB)	= High criticality								
Secure overall mobility	Real-time punctuality and capacity forecasts, Demand forecast, Nodes & Network capacity	Data Communications and Networking	Radio Block Centre (RBC) for managing train movements, providing movement authorities, and ensuring safe separation between train units	GSM-R (Global System for Mobile Communications - Railway) for ensuring reliable communication for on-board train units and the RBC	GSM-R base stations specific to railway communication (e.g. those from Siemens or Alstom)	Metals: Aluminum (Al), Copper (Cu), Steel (Fe) Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) Plastics and Polymers: For casing and insulation Ceramics: For capacitors and insulators	Onboard GSM-R equipment as train-mounted devices that communicate with trackside GSM-R infrastructure	Metals: Aluminum (Al), Copper (Cu), Gold (Au) for connectors Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) Plastics and Polymers: For housing and insulation Ceramics: For capacitors and other components	Routers and Switches i.e., industrial-grade network equipment for high reliability (e.g. Cisco's ruggedized networking products)	Metals: Copper (Cu), Aluminum (Al), Gold (Au) for connectors Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) Plastics and Polymers: For casing and insulation Ceramics: For capacitors and insulators	Gallium Nitride (GaN): Newer semiconductor for high-efficiency, high-power applications (Type 77)	Advanced Plastics and Polymers: Enhanced materials for better performance and protection (Type 77)	GSM-R Protocol Stack to be able to implement the GSM-R communication protocols, including voice and data services	Network Management Systems such IT tools for monitoring and managing network traffic and performance (e.g., Cisco Prime)	Communication Protocols - 5G- i.e., include protocol stacks for railway communication	Real-Time Processing Software for applications and middleware that handle data from sensors and communication systems in real-time	Encryption Algorithms implementations of AES (Advanced Encryption Standard) and RSA (Rivest-Shamir-Adleman) for data protection	= Moderate Low	= Low criticality	= Moderate criticality	= High criticality	= High criticality									
																							GSM-R and Future Railway Mobile Communication System (FRMCS) supplement the current GSM-R with FRMCS to reach and provide higher data rates and reliability	FRMCS equipment (yet under development by various rail technology providers)	Metals: Copper (Cu), Aluminum (Al), Gold (Au) Semiconductors: Silicon (Si), Gallium Nitride (GaN) for high frequency components Plastics and Polymers: For housing and insulation Ceramics: For capacitors and insulators	= stable as all materials usage consistent with older technology			= Moderate Low	= High criticality	
																							Real-Time Data Processing for ensuring timely processing and transmission of data from various sensors and systems	High-performance Servers and Data Centers	Metals: Copper (Cu), Aluminum (Al), Steel (Fe), Gold (Au) Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) Plastics and Polymers: For casing and insulation Ceramics: For capacitors and insulators	= stable as all materials usage consistent with older technology			= High	= High criticality	
																							Encryption and Authentication Protocols for protecting data integrity and ensuring only authorized access	Cryptographic Modules as hardware security modules (HSM) (e.g. Thales iChivo or Gemalto SafeNet for secure key management and encryption)	Metals: Copper (Cu), Aluminum (Al), Gold (Au) Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) Plastics and Polymers: For housing and insulation Ceramics: For capacitors and insulators	= stable as all materials usage consistent with older technology			= Moderate High (if autonomous Train)	= High criticality	
																							Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) for monitoring the network in case of unauthorized access or threats	Network Sensors (e.g. devices from Snort or Suricata for network monitoring)	Metals: Copper (Cu), Aluminum (Al), Gold (Au) Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) Plastics and Polymers: For casing and protective covers Ceramics: For capacitors and insulators	= stable as all materials usage consistent with older technology			= Moderate High (if autonomous Train)	= High criticality	

FA 5

Sustainable Competitive Digital Green Rail Freight Services

FP5

TRANSFORM & TRANSITION TO DIGITAL GREEN RAIL FREIGHT

Intelligent Train (incl. Digital Automatic Coupler (DAC))

LEADER 2030 Task 2.1 & 2.2 & 2.3 - Desk Search for 'Map of Railway Needs 2030'																					
FLAGSHIP AREA (FA) (according to ERIU MAWP)	FA TITLE (according to ERIU MAWP)	FLAGSHIP PROJECT (FP) (according to ERIU FP respective website)	FP TITLE (according to ERIU FP respective website)	MAIN CONCERNED TECHNOLOGY (based on ERIU MAWP, FP website)	FUNCTIONALITIES (based on ERIU MAWP, FP website)	SUB-FUNCTIONALITIES (according to ERIU FP website)	SUB-FUNCTIONALITIES DEFINING SUB-ASSEMBLIES (detailed technologies) (Full desk search, i.e. beyond ERIU FP website and Public Deliverables + SERA + Interviews FPS Project Coordinator, Operator & Head of EU DAC Migration)	(Main) COMPONENTS TO INTRODUCE (including various documents and interview of Infineon semiconductor product specialist engineer)	(Main) RAW MATERIALS (including various documents and interview of Infineon semiconductor product specialist engineer)	NEW COMPONENTS / RAW MATERIALS USAGE Old vs. New technology adoption in 2030 (i.e. vs. ERTMS 2, ERTMS 1, or none): usage variation levels ↗ Increased usage ↘ stable usage	OLD COMPONENTS / RAW MATERIALS USAGE Old vs. New technology adoption in 2030: usage variation levels = stable usage ↘ decreased usage	(Striking) ELEMENTS TO INTRODUCE (including various documents and interview of Infineon semiconductor product specialist engineer)	Likelihood of technology (H/W/S/V) implementation in 2030 ↗ High likelyhood = Moderate likelyhood ↘ Low likelyhood	Foreseen criticalities in 2030 (Crossing info from I & P column + CMAA list + LEADER 2030 DL 3)	IMPACT ON OEMs/ SUPPLIERS (with special attention to SMEs) supplying/working in the relevant segment (s) ?						
Full Digital Freight Train Operations	Energy and Communication (including Train Integrity)	DAC	Energy and Communication (including Train Integrity)	Automatic Coupler Systems with mechanized components for coupling/uncoupling trains	Mechanical Coupler Components	Metals: Steel (Fe) for durability and strength, Aluminum (Al) for lightweight sections Plastics and Polymers: Nylon or Polyurethane for bushings and wear-resistant surfaces Metals: Stainless Steel (Fe) for corrosion resistance, Aluminum (Al) for lightweight components Plastics and Polymers: Polyethylene (PE) for seals, Rubber for gaskets	- HARDWARE - (According to various documents and interview of Infineon semiconductor product specialist engineer)	- HARDWARE - (According to various documents and interview of Infineon semiconductor product specialist engineer)	High-strength steel (Fe) and aluminum (Al) for lightweight coupling systems	Traditional steel (Fe) used in manual coupling systems may be reduced due to the shift toward automated systems requiring more advanced materials	Coupling Control Algorithms: Software that manages and monitors coupling processes	Moderate No ↗ High (TRL 6/7 targeted for most DAC elements for 2027 - see ERIU MAWP)	Steel - High criticality ↗ Silicon - Very High criticality ↗ Adv. polymers - High criticality	Develop digital customer platforms to offer new services to all Freight customers, allowing real-time management of the logistics chain Identify and design multimodal solutions to improve multimodality and thus facilitate transportation Create digitalised and automated rail freight operations tools to allow seamless operations between all players in the rail freight sector (boosting transport service for the customer, planning and dispatching trains, smoothing train functions monitoring) Design and produce multi-functional and modular wagon							
															Hydraulic or Pneumatic Actuators	Metals: Stainless Steel (Fe) for corrosion resistance, Aluminum (Al) for lightweight components Plastics and Polymers: Polyethylene (PE) for seals, Rubber for gaskets	High-performance plastics for cable insulation and protective housings	Energy Management Systems: Software for optimizing energy use and distribution.	High criticality	SMEs can focus on niche areas like sensors, actuators, communication modules, or specific types of coupler materials	
															Electronic Control Units (ECUs)	Metals: Copper (Cu) for circuit pathways, Gold (Au) for connectors Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for microprocessors and processing chips Plastics and Polymers: Polycarbonate for housing, Epoxy resin for PCB insulation	High-performance plastics for cable insulation and protective housings	Communication Protocols: Software that ensures reliable data exchange.	High criticality	SMEs can focus on Upgrading Production Capabilities as there will be a need to produce more sophisticated and reliable components for DAC systems may require SMEs to invest in new manufacturing technologies and processes, such as precision machining, advanced electronics assembly, and high-quality materials	
															Sensors and Actuators for detecting coupling conditions and actuating the process	Proximity Sensors	Metals: Copper (Cu) for wiring, Aluminum (Al) for sensor housings Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for sensor chips Plastics and Polymers: Polyethylene (PE) for sensor casing	High-performance plastics for cable insulation and protective housings	Communication Protocols: Software that ensures reliable data exchange.	High criticality	SMEs can focus on offering specialized aftermarket services as DAC technology will require ongoing maintenance, diagnostics, and software updates.
															Force Sensors	Metals: Stainless Steel (Fe) for sensor elements Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for sensor chips Plastics and Polymers: Polyurethane for contact and housing	High-performance plastics for cable insulation and protective housings	Communication Protocols: Software that ensures reliable data exchange.	High criticality	SMEs can focus on offering specialized aftermarket services as DAC technology will require ongoing maintenance, diagnostics, and software updates.	
															Electric Actuators	Metals: Steel (Fe) for gears, Aluminum (Al) for housings Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for control electronics Plastics and Polymers: Polycarbonate for casing, Polyethylene Chloride (PVC) for insulation	High-performance plastics for cable insulation and protective housings	Communication Protocols: Software that ensures reliable data exchange.	High criticality	SMEs can focus on offering specialized aftermarket services as DAC technology will require ongoing maintenance, diagnostics, and software updates.	
															Power Supply Systems that include transformers and converters for 400V operations	Transformers	Metals: Copper (Cu) for windings, Silicon Steel (Fe) for the core Plastics and Polymers: Polyethylene (PE) for insulation, Epoxy resin for the coating	High-performance plastics for cable insulation and protective housings	Communication Protocols: Software that ensures reliable data exchange.	High criticality	SMEs can focus on offering specialized aftermarket services as DAC technology will require ongoing maintenance, diagnostics, and software updates.
															Voltage Converters	Metals: Copper (Cu) for coils, Aluminum (Al) for heatinks Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for power transistors and diodes Plastics and Polymers: Polypropylene for capacitor housings, Nylon for connectors	High-performance plastics for cable insulation and protective housings	Communication Protocols: Software that ensures reliable data exchange.	High criticality	SMEs can focus on offering specialized aftermarket services as DAC technology will require ongoing maintenance, diagnostics, and software updates.	
															Circuit Breakers	Metals: Copper (Cu) for contacts, Steel (Fe) for mechanical parts Plastics and Polymers: Bakelite or Phenolic resin for insulation, PVC for internal casing	High-performance plastics for cable insulation and protective housings	Communication Protocols: Software that ensures reliable data exchange.	High criticality	SMEs can focus on offering specialized aftermarket services as DAC technology will require ongoing maintenance, diagnostics, and software updates.	
															Communication Modules with devices that secure data transmission across the train	Transceivers	Metals: Copper (Cu) for antenna connections, Gold (Au) for high-quality connectors Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for radio frequency (RF) chips Plastics and Polymers: Polyurethane for housing	High-performance plastics for cable insulation and protective housings	Communication Protocols: Software that ensures reliable data exchange.	High criticality	SMEs can focus on offering specialized aftermarket services as DAC technology will require ongoing maintenance, diagnostics, and software updates.
															Antennas	Metals: Copper (Cu) or Aluminum (Al) for conductive elements Plastics and Polymers: Polyethylene (PE) for insulation	High-performance plastics for cable insulation and protective housings	Communication Protocols: Software that ensures reliable data exchange.	High criticality	SMEs can focus on offering specialized aftermarket services as DAC technology will require ongoing maintenance, diagnostics, and software updates.	
															Data Processors	Metals: Copper (Cu) for circuit pathways, Tin (Sn) for soldering Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for processors and memory chips Plastics and Polymers: Polycarbonate for casing, Epoxy for PCB insulation	High-performance plastics for cable insulation and protective housings	Communication Protocols: Software that ensures reliable data exchange.	High criticality	SMEs can focus on offering specialized aftermarket services as DAC technology will require ongoing maintenance, diagnostics, and software updates.	
Integrity Monitoring Sensors with devices that ensure the train's physical integrity	Strain Gauges	Metals: Constantan (Ni-Cu alloy) for the sensing element Plastics and Polymers: Polyimide film for insulation	High-performance plastics for cable insulation and protective housings	Communication Protocols: Software that ensures reliable data exchange.	High criticality	SMEs can focus on offering specialized aftermarket services as DAC technology will require ongoing maintenance, diagnostics, and software updates.															
Accelerometers	Metals: Copper (Cu) for wiring Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for microelectromechanical systems (MEMS)	High-performance plastics for cable insulation and protective housings	Communication Protocols: Software that ensures reliable data exchange.	High criticality	SMEs can focus on offering specialized aftermarket services as DAC technology will require ongoing maintenance, diagnostics, and software updates.																
Data Loggers	Metals: Aluminum (Al) for housing, Copper (Cu) for wiring Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for memory and processing chips Plastics and Polymers: Polycarbonate for casing, Epoxy for PCB insulation	High-performance plastics for cable insulation and protective housings	Communication Protocols: Software that ensures reliable data exchange.	High criticality	SMEs can focus on offering specialized aftermarket services as DAC technology will require ongoing maintenance, diagnostics, and software updates.																
Train Functions (e.g. Automated Brake, Test)	Train Functions (e.g. Automated Brake, Test)	Brake Actuators and Sensors for automatic brake testing and monitoring	Brake Actuators	Metals: Steel (Fe) for mechanical components, Aluminum (Al) for actuator housings Plastics and Polymers: Polyurethane for seals, Polycarbonate for housing Metals: Stainless Steel (Fe) for the pressure-sensitive diaphragm Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for sensing elements Plastics and Polymers: Polyethylene (PE) for casing	High-grade steel (Fe) for brake actuators and components ↗ Silicon (Si) for sensors and diagnostic modules ↗ Advanced polymers for housing and protective covers	Traditional manual brake systems that rely on less sophisticated materials might be phased out	Brake Control Systems: Software that automates and monitors brake testing	High (TRL 6/7 targeted for most functions for 2027 if not already for 2025 - see ERIU MAWP)	High-grade Steel - High criticality ↗ Silicon - Very High criticality ↗ Adv. polymers - High criticality	Diagnostic Analytics: Algorithms that assess brake function and report issues	High criticality	SMEs can focus on offering specialized aftermarket services as DAC technology will require ongoing maintenance, diagnostics, and software updates.									
													Pressure Sensors	Metals: Stainless Steel (Fe) for the pressure-sensitive diaphragm Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for sensing elements Plastics and Polymers: Polyethylene (PE) for casing	High-grade steel (Fe) for brake actuators and components ↗ Silicon (Si) for sensors and diagnostic modules ↗ Advanced polymers for housing and protective covers	Traditional manual brake systems that rely on less sophisticated materials might be phased out	Brake Control Systems: Software that automates and monitors brake testing	High criticality	SMEs can focus on offering specialized aftermarket services as DAC technology will require ongoing maintenance, diagnostics, and software updates.		
													Position Sensors	Metals: Copper (Cu) for wiring, Aluminum (Al) for sensor housings Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for sensing elements Plastics and Polymers: Polycarbonate for casing	High-grade steel (Fe) for brake actuators and components ↗ Silicon (Si) for sensors and diagnostic modules ↗ Advanced polymers for housing and protective covers	Traditional manual brake systems that rely on less sophisticated materials might be phased out	Brake Control Systems: Software that automates and monitors brake testing	High criticality	SMEs can focus on offering specialized aftermarket services as DAC technology will require ongoing maintenance, diagnostics, and software updates.		
													Data Acquisition Systems	Metals: Copper (Cu) for wiring, Aluminum (Al) for sensor housings Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for data processing and storage Plastics and Polymers: Polycarbonate for casing	High-grade steel (Fe) for brake actuators and components ↗ Silicon (Si) for sensors and diagnostic modules ↗ Advanced polymers for housing and protective covers	Traditional manual brake systems that rely on less sophisticated materials might be phased out	Brake Control Systems: Software that automates and monitors brake testing	High criticality	SMEs can focus on offering specialized aftermarket services as DAC technology will require ongoing maintenance, diagnostics, and software updates.		
Automated Yard Operations	Automated Yard Operations	Automated Shunting Locomotives, i.e. locomotives equipped with automation for yard operations	Propulsion System	Metals: Steel (Fe) for chassis and motor components, Aluminum (Al) for lightweight parts Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for power electronics and control systems Plastics and Polymers: Polycarbonate for electrical insulation, Rubber for gaskets	Aluminum (Al) for lightweight structures, Steel (Fe) for robust locomotive components ↗ Silicon (Si) for AI and control systems ↗ High-performance polymers for sensor casings and cable insulation	Older mechanical control systems might use less advanced metals and fewer semiconductors	Yard Management Systems: Software to control and automate yard operations	Moderate (Some TRL 6/7 targeted for some Advanced Yard Operations for 2025 - see ERIU MAWP)	Aluminum - Moderate criticality ↗ Silicon - High criticality	AI and Machine Learning Algorithms: For optimizing yard processes and managing logistics.	Moderate	SMEs can focus on offering specialized aftermarket services as DAC technology will require ongoing maintenance, diagnostics, and software updates.									
													Control Systems	Metals: Copper (Cu) for wiring, Gold (Au) for connectors Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for microprocessors and sensors Plastics and Polymers: Polycarbonate for housing, Polyurethane for connector covers	Aluminum (Al) for lightweight structures, Steel (Fe) for robust locomotive components ↗ Silicon (Si) for AI and control systems ↗ High-performance polymers for sensor casings and cable insulation	Older mechanical control systems might use less advanced metals and fewer semiconductors	Yard Management Systems: Software to control and automate yard operations	Moderate	SMEs can focus on offering specialized aftermarket services as DAC technology will require ongoing maintenance, diagnostics, and software updates.		
													Cameras	Metals: Aluminum (Al) for housings, Copper (Cu) for wiring Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for sensors Plastics and Polymers: Polycarbonate for lens casing	Aluminum (Al) for lightweight structures, Steel (Fe) for robust locomotive components ↗ Silicon (Si) for AI and control systems ↗ High-performance polymers for sensor casings and cable insulation	Older mechanical control systems might use less advanced metals and fewer semiconductors	Yard Management Systems: Software to control and automate yard operations	Moderate	SMEs can focus on offering specialized aftermarket services as DAC technology will require ongoing maintenance, diagnostics, and software updates.		
													Monitoring Displays	Metals: Copper (Cu) for internal wiring Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for display drivers Plastics and Polymers: Liquid Crystal Display (LCD) panels, Polycarbonate for casing	Aluminum (Al) for lightweight structures, Steel (Fe) for robust locomotive components ↗ Silicon (Si) for AI and control systems ↗ High-performance polymers for sensor casings and cable insulation	Older mechanical control systems might use less advanced metals and fewer semiconductors	Yard Management Systems: Software to control and automate yard operations	Moderate	SMEs can focus on offering specialized aftermarket services as DAC technology will require ongoing maintenance, diagnostics, and software updates.		
Seamless Planning and Dispatching	Seamless Planning and Dispatching	Servers and Data Centers to host planning and dispatching software	Server Racks	Metals: Fe for structural components, Aluminum (Al) for lightweight frames Plastics and Polymers: Polycarbonate for housing and insulation	Aluminum (Al) for server racks, Copper (Cu) for wiring ↗ Silicon (Si) for processors and memory modules ↗ Epoxy and polycarbonate for insulation and housing	Paper-based or manual dispatch systems with minimal use of metals and semiconductors	Logistics Planning Software: Platforms that optimize train scheduling and routing.	Moderate (TRL 6/7 targeted for some seamless functions for 2025 - see ERIU MAWP)	Real-Time Dispatching Tools: Software that manages the real-time allocation of resources.	Moderate	Aluminum - Moderate criticality ↗ Silicon - High criticality = Epoxy - Moderate criticality	SMEs can focus on offering specialized aftermarket services as DAC technology will require ongoing maintenance, diagnostics, and software updates.									
													Processors	Metals: Copper (Cu) for interconnects, Gold (Au) for high-performance connectors Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for CPUs and GPUs Plastics and Polymers: Epoxy for PCB insulation	Aluminum (Al) for server racks, Copper (Cu) for wiring ↗ Silicon (Si) for processors and memory modules ↗ Epoxy and polycarbonate for insulation and housing	Paper-based or manual dispatch systems with minimal use of metals and semiconductors	Logistics Planning Software: Platforms that optimize train scheduling and routing.	Moderate	SMEs can focus on offering specialized aftermarket services as DAC technology will require ongoing maintenance, diagnostics, and software updates.		
													Cooling Systems	Metals: Fe for structural components, Aluminum (Al) for lightweight frames Plastics and Polymers: Polycarbonate for housing and insulation	Aluminum (Al) for server racks, Copper (Cu) for wiring ↗ Silicon (Si) for processors and memory modules ↗ Epoxy and polycarbonate for insulation and housing	Paper-based or manual dispatch systems with minimal use of metals and semiconductors	Logistics Planning Software: Platforms that optimize train scheduling and routing.	Moderate	SMEs can focus on offering specialized aftermarket services as DAC technology will require ongoing maintenance, diagnostics, and software updates.		
													Communication Networks for real-time data exchange between systems	Routers & Switches	Metals: Copper (Cu) for wiring, Gold (Au) for connectors Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for network processors Plastics and Polymers: Polycarbonate for housing, Polyethylene Chloride (PVC) for insulation	Aluminum (Al) for server racks, Copper (Cu) for wiring ↗ Silicon (Si) for processors and memory modules ↗ Epoxy and polycarbonate for insulation and housing	Paper-based or manual dispatch systems with minimal use of metals and semiconductors	Logistics Planning Software: Platforms that optimize train scheduling and routing.	Moderate	SMEs can focus on offering specialized aftermarket services as DAC technology will require ongoing maintenance, diagnostics, and software updates.	
Intermodal Integration and Prediction	Intermodal Integration and Prediction	Intermodal Transfer Equipment with cranes and automated systems for moving freight between transport modes	Components for Hydraulic Systems	Metals: Steel (Fe) for structural components, Aluminum (Al) for lightweight frames Metals: Stainless Steel (Fe) for cylinders and pistons, Copper (Cu) for fluid pathways Plastics and Polymers: Polyurethane for seals andaskets	Steel (Fe) for mechanical structures in transfer equipment, Copper (Cu) for IoT device wiring ↗ Silicon (Si) for GPUs and RFID chips ↗ Polycarbonate and polyethylene for housing and tags	Traditional mechanical tracking systems that don't utilize modern semiconductors and plastics	Intermodal Logistics Platforms: Software that integrates and optimizes the flow of goods across transport modes.	Moderate (TRL 6/7 targeted for some seamless intermodality for 2027 - see ERIU MAWP)	Predictive Analytics Tools: Software for predicting and optimizing intermodal connections and schedules.	Moderate	Steel - Moderate criticality ↗ Silicon - High criticality	SMEs can focus on offering specialized aftermarket services as DAC technology will require ongoing maintenance, diagnostics, and software updates.									
													Control Systems	Metals: Copper (Cu) for wiring, Gold (Au) for connectors Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for control electronics Plastics and Polymers: Polycarbonate for casings	Steel (Fe) for mechanical structures in transfer equipment, Copper (Cu) for IoT device wiring ↗ Silicon (Si) for GPUs and RFID chips ↗ Polycarbonate and polyethylene for housing and tags	Traditional mechanical tracking systems that don't utilize modern semiconductors and plastics	Intermodal Logistics Platforms: Software that integrates and optimizes the flow of goods across transport modes.	Moderate	SMEs can focus on offering specialized aftermarket services as DAC technology will require ongoing maintenance, diagnostics, and software updates.		
													Tracking and Monitoring Devices such as IoT devices to track cargo across different modes of transport	GPS Modules	Metals: Copper (Cu) for antenna wiring Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for GPS chips Plastics and Polymers: Polyurethane for radomes	Steel (Fe) for mechanical structures in transfer equipment, Copper (Cu) for IoT device wiring ↗ Silicon (Si) for GPUs and RFID chips ↗ Polycarbonate and polyethylene for housing and tags	Traditional mechanical tracking systems that don't utilize modern semiconductors and plastics	Intermodal Logistics Platforms: Software that integrates and optimizes the flow of goods across transport modes.	Moderate	SMEs can focus on offering specialized aftermarket services as DAC technology will require ongoing maintenance, diagnostics, and software updates.	
													RFID Tags	Metals: Copper (Cu) for antenna, Aluminum (Al) for tag frames Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for RFID chips	Steel (Fe) for mechanical structures in transfer equipment, Copper (Cu) for IoT device wiring ↗ Silicon (Si) for GPUs and RFID chips ↗ Polycarbonate and polyethylene for housing and tags	Traditional mechanical tracking systems that don't utilize modern semiconductors and plastics	Intermodal Logistics Platforms: Software that integrates and optimizes the flow of goods across transport modes.	Moderate	SMEs can focus on offering specialized aftermarket services as DAC technology will require ongoing maintenance, diagnostics, and software updates.		
Support new	Support new	Hydrogen Storage Tanks with specialized containers for safe hydrogen transport	Tank Shell	Metals: Aluminum (Al) or Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastics (CFRP) for lightweight, high-strength tanks Plastics and Polymers: Polyethylene (PE) for chemical resistance Plastics and Polymers: Polyurethane foam for thermal insulation	Aluminum (Al) or Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastics (CFRP) for lightweight, high-strength tanks ↗ Silicon (Si) for safety sensors	Heavier metals like traditional steel may be less favored due to weight considerations in hydrogen transport	Containment Monitoring Systems: Software that tracks hydrogen levels, pressure, and safety conditions.	Moderate No ↘ Low	Aluminum - Moderate criticality ↗ Silicon - High criticality	SMEs can focus on offering specialized aftermarket services as DAC technology will require ongoing maintenance, diagnostics, and software updates.											
											Linners	Metals: Aluminum (Al) or Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastics (CFRP) for lightweight, high-strength tanks Plastics and Polymers: Polyethylene (PE) for chemical resistance Plastics and Polymers: Polyurethane foam for thermal insulation	Aluminum (Al) or Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastics (CFRP) for lightweight, high-strength tanks ↗ Silicon (Si) for safety sensors	Heavier metals like traditional steel may be less favored due to weight considerations in hydrogen transport	Containment Monitoring Systems: Software that tracks hydrogen levels, pressure, and safety conditions.	Moderate	SMEs can focus on offering specialized aftermarket services as DAC technology will require ongoing maintenance, diagnostics, and software updates.				
Insulation	Metals: Aluminum (Al) or Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastics (CFRP) for lightweight, high-strength tanks Plastics and Polymers: Polyethylene (PE) for chemical resistance Plastics and Polymers: Polyurethane foam for thermal insulation	Aluminum (Al) or Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastics (CFRP) for lightweight, high-strength tanks ↗ Silicon (Si) for safety sensors	Heavier metals like traditional steel may be less favored due to weight considerations in hydrogen transport	Containment Monitoring Systems: Software that tracks hydrogen levels, pressure, and safety conditions.	Moderate	SMEs can focus on offering specialized aftermarket services as DAC technology will require ongoing maintenance, diagnostics, and software updates.															

Innovative Freight Assets	Hydrogen Fuel Cells	Safety Valves and Sensors. I.e. components for monitoring and ensuring the safe containment of hydrogen	Valves Sensors	Metals: Stainless Steel (Fe) for valve bodies, Brass (Cu-Zn alloy) for fittings. Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for pressure and hydrogen detection sensors. Plastics and Polymers: Polyethylene for sensor housings. Metals: Copper (Cu) for wiring, Aluminum (Al) for housings.	➔ Polyethylene and polyurethane for tank liners and insulation			(Cluster created after the ERUJ-MAWP + Likelihood of FAA)	
	Self-Propelled Wagon	Onboard Propulsion Systems fitted with electric or hybrid engines for self-propulsion	Electric Motors Gear Systems Battery Storage	Metals: Copper (Cu) for windings, Steel (Fe) for the motor core Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for control electronics. Metals: Steel (Fe) for gears, Aluminum (Al) for housings. Metals: Lithium (Li) for batteries, Copper (Cu) for electrical connections. Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for battery management systems. Plastics and Polymers: Polypropylene for battery casing, Polyethylene for insulation	➔ Copper (Cu) for electrical systems, Lithium (Li) for batteries. ➔ Silicon (Si) for propulsion control and navigation systems	➔ Internal combustion engine components with materials like cast iron and basic steel might be reduced in favor of electric or hybrid systems	Autonomous Navigation Software: Systems that manage the movement and routing of the wagon. Energy Management Software: To optimize battery usage and propulsion efficiency.	= Moderate to ➔ Low (Cluster created after the ERUJ-MAWP + Likelihood of FAA)	= Copper - Moderate criticality ➔ Silicon - High criticality = Polypropylene and polyethylene - Moderate criticality
		Battery Storage. I.e. high-capacity batteries for powering the wagon	Battery cells Battery Management System	Metals: Lithium (Li) for lithium-ion cells, Nickel (Ni) for cathodes, Copper (Cu) for anodes. Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for battery management systems. Plastics and Polymers: Polypropylene for battery cell casings. Metals: Copper (Cu) for electrical connections. Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for battery management systems. Plastics and Polymers: Polypropylene for battery casing, Polyethylene for insulation.					
		Sensors for Navigation and Control with devices for managing wagon movement autonomously	Inertial Measurement Units (IMUs) GPS Modules	Metals: Copper (Cu) for wiring, Aluminum (Al) for casing Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for MEMS gyroscopes and accelerometers Plastics and Polymers: Polycarbonate for housing Metals: Copper (Cu) for antenna wiring Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for GPS chips Plastics and Polymers: Polycarbonate for casings					
	Energy Efficiency Strategy for Freight	Energy Recovery Systems thanks to devices like regenerative braking systems to capture and reuse energy	Regenerative Braking Units	Metals: Lithium (Li) for lithium-ion cells, Nickel (Ni) for cathodes, Copper (Cu) for anodes. Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for battery management systems. Plastics and Polymers: Polypropylene for battery cell casings. Metals: Copper (Cu) for electrical connections. Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for battery management systems. Plastics and Polymers: Polypropylene for battery casing, Polyethylene for insulation.	➔ Lithium (Li) for batteries, Copper (Cu) for regenerative braking systems and wiring. ➔ Silicon (Si) for energy management systems	➔ Conventional braking materials that do not support energy recovery, such as certain grades of steel and other composites.	Predictive Maintenance Tools: Software that uses energy data to predict and optimize maintenance needs.	= Moderate to ➔ Low (Cluster created after the ERUJ-MAWP + Likelihood of FAA)	➔ Lithium - High criticality ➔ Silicon - High criticality = Adv. Polymers - Moderate criticality
		Energy Storage Units using batteries or capacitors to store recovered energy	Battery Cells Capacitors (if used) Battery Management System (BMS)	Metals: Lithium (Li) for lithium-ion cells, Nickel (Ni) for cathodes, Copper (Cu) for anodes. Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for battery management systems. Plastics and Polymers: Polypropylene for battery cell casings. Metals: Aluminum (Al) for capacitor plates, Copper (Cu) for terminals. Plastics and Polymers: Polypropylene for dielectric material, Polycarbonate for casing Metals: Copper (Cu) for wiring, Gold (Au) for high-reliability connections Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for microcontrollers and sensors. Plastics and Polymers: Polycarbonate for housing, Epoxy for PCB insulation	➔ Advanced polymers for battery casing, insulation, and energy recovery system housing		Energy Optimization Algorithms: Software that optimizes energy use across the train's systems		
Cooling System (for high-capacity storage)			Metals: Aluminum (Al) for heat sinks, Copper (Cu) for coolant pathways. Plastics and Polymers: Polycarbonate for fan housing, PVC for insulation.						

Intelligent Tra

Innovative Freight Assets

Self-Propelled Wagons

Energy Efficiency Strategy for Freight

<p>Battery Storage</p> <p>Battery Storage, i.e. High-capacity batteries for powering the wagon</p>	<p>Battery Storage</p> <p>Metal: Lithium (Li) for batteries, Copper (Cu) for electrical connections. Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for battery management systems. Plastics and Polymers: Polypropylene for battery casing, Polyethylene for insulation.</p>	<p>➔ Polypropylene and polyethylene for battery casing and insulation</p>
<p>Battery Cells</p>	<p>Metal: Lithium (Li) for lithium-ion cells, Nickel (Ni) for cathodes, Copper (Cu) for anodes. Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for battery management systems. Plastics and Polymers: Polypropylene for battery cell casings.</p>	
<p>Battery Management System</p>	<p>Metal: Copper (Cu) for electrical connections. Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for battery management systems. Plastics and Polymers: Polypropylene for battery casing, Polyethylene for insulation.</p>	
<p>Sensors for Navigation and Control with devices for managing wagon movement autonomously</p>	<p>Inertial Measurement Units (IMUs)</p> <p>Metal: Copper (Cu) for wiring, Aluminum (Al) for casing. Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for MEMS gyroscopes and accelerometers. Plastics and Polymers: Polycarbonate for housing.</p>	
	<p>GPS Modules</p> <p>Metal: Copper (Cu) for antenna wiring. Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for GPS chips. Plastics and Polymers: Polycarbonate for casing.</p>	
<p>Regenerative Braking Units</p>	<p>Metal: Lithium (Li) for lithium-ion cells, Nickel (Ni) for cathodes, Copper (Cu) for anodes. Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for battery management systems. Plastics and Polymers: Polypropylene for battery cell casings, Polycarbonate for insulation.</p>	<p>➔ Lithium (Li) for batteries, Copper (Cu) for regenerative braking systems and wiring.</p> <p>➔ Silicon (Si) for energy management systems</p>
<p>Energy Storage Units using batteries or capacitors to store recovered energy</p>	<p>Battery Cells</p> <p>Metal: Lithium (Li) for lithium-ion cells, Nickel (Ni) for cathodes, Copper (Cu) for anodes. Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for battery management systems. Plastics and Polymers: Polypropylene for battery cell casings, Polycarbonate for insulation.</p>	<p>➔ Conventional braking materials that do not support energy recovery, such as certain grades of steel and older composites.</p>
	<p>Capacitors (if used)</p> <p>Metal: Aluminum (Al) for capacitor plates, Copper (Cu) for terminals. Plastics and Polymers: Polypropylene for dielectric material, Polycarbonate for casing.</p>	<p>Predictive Maintenance Tools: Software that uses energy data to predict and optimize maintenance needs.</p>
	<p>Battery Management System (BMS)</p> <p>Metal: Copper (Cu) for wiring, Gold (Au) for high-reliability connectors. Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for microcontrollers and sensors. Plastics and Polymers: Polycarbonate for housing, Epoxy for PCB insulation.</p>	<p>Energy Optimization Algorithms: Software that optimizes energy use across the train's systems.</p>
<p>Cooling System (for high-capacity storage)</p>	<p>Metal: Aluminum (Al) for heat sinks, Copper (Cu) for coolant pathways. Plastics and Polymers: Polycarbonate for fan housing, PVC for insulation.</p>	

Energy Management Software: To optimize battery usage and propulsion efficiency.

Cluster created after the ERJ-149MP + overhaul of FA4

➔ Silicon - High criticality
= Polypropylene and polyethylene - Moderate criticality

Moderate to Low
Cluster created after the ERJ-149MP + overhaul of FA4

➔ Lithium - High criticality
➔ Silicon - High criticality
= Adv. Polymers - Moderate criticality

FA 7

Innovation on new approaches for guided transport modes

FP7

Integrated Asset Management

maint

Energy Saving & Green technologies - (same as FA4) -

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	Strategic Objectives	Enabling Technologies	Key Challenges	Timeline	Criticality	
<p>Renewable Energy Source (RES) Increase for both infrastructure and Rolling Stock (Same as FA4) -</p> <p>Energy storage systems (ESS)</p> <p>Green Electrification</p>	<p>Smart, Renewable Energy-powered Stations</p>	<p>Use Renewable Energy Generation and generate grid independence by generating energy on-site or near rail stations and tracks, particularly in remote areas.</p>	<p>Solar Panels Metallic Silicon (cell), aluminum (frames), silver (contacts) Semiconductors: Silicon (photovoltaic cells) Plastic and Polymers: Encapsulation layers, backsheet</p>	<p>Low efficiency in remote areas High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>	
		<p>Optimize the energy usage within the rail system by managing the integration of various energy sources by relying on real-time monitoring and control.</p>	<p>Energy management systems (EMS) to provide analytics and reporting on energy usage</p>	<p>Copper for electrical wiring systems Semiconductors: Enclosures, insulation materials</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>
		<p>Energy Storage (Store excess energy generated from renewables) or during off-peak times for later use, ensuring a reliable supply during high-demand periods.</p>	<p>Grid integration and storage solutions to provide fast response to changes in energy demand</p>	<p>Metallic: Lithium (batteries), copper (wiring) Semiconductors: Power converters, inverters Plastic and Polymers: Battery housing, insulation materials</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>
		<p>Grid Stability: Provide grid support functions like frequency regulation and load balancing to maintain stability when integrating renewable energy into the rail power system.</p>	<p>Advanced supercapacitor in fact complement batteries in managing short-term power fluctuations thus ensuring long cycle life</p>	<p>Metallic: Aluminum (electrodes), carbon (anodes) Semiconductors: Power control systems Plastic and Polymers: Enclosures, insulation layers</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>
		<p>Efficient Energy Conversion (e.g., AC to DC), Voltage Regulation (correct voltage levels for different rail subsystems) and Harmonics Reduction (reduce power quality issues)</p>	<p>Power conversion systems to offer real-time control and adaptability</p>	<p>Metallic: Copper (wiring, aluminum (heat sinks)) Semiconductors: Silicon carbide (SiC) devices Plastic and Polymers: Enclosures, insulation materials</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>
		<p>Provide a modular approach to electrification that can be scaled up or down depending on the specific needs of different rail segments</p>	<p>Electrification infrastructure using green energy sources offer scalability for future network expansion</p>	<p>Metallic: Copper (system systems), steel (tracks), aluminum (conductor) Semiconductors: Power electronics for managing grid integration Plastic and Polymers: Insulation for cables, protective coatings</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>
		<p>Smart Grid Integration to manage and distribute energy efficiently across the rail network, adapting to demand changes and supply in real-time (incl. Energy Loss Reduction, Fault Detection Management)</p>	<p>Advanced energy distribution systems to offer real-time monitoring and control</p>	<p>Metallic: Copper (wiring, aluminum (transformers)) Semiconductors: smart grid components, inverters Plastic and Polymers: Cable insulation, housing for electronics</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>
		<p>Proactive Equipment Maintenance to predict and prevent equipment failure before it occurs, reducing downtime and extending the lifespan of rail components</p>	<p>Predictive maintenance systems</p>	<p>Metallic: Steel (copper for sensor housings and wiring) Semiconductors: Sensor components, chips Plastic and Polymers: Enclosures, insulation materials</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>
		<p>Optimize the whole energy and operations needs</p>	<p>AI</p>	<p>AI</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>
		<p>Optimize the whole energy and operations needs</p>	<p>AI</p>	<p>AI</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>
<p>Renewable Energy Source (RES) Increase for both infrastructure and Rolling Stock (Same as FA4) -</p> <p>Energy storage systems (ESS)</p> <p>Green Electrification</p>	<p>Smart, Renewable Energy-powered Stations</p>	<p>Integrate multiple energy sources in rail systems, combining both the efficiency and flexibility of train operations while reducing environmental impact</p>	<p>Metallic: Steel (drive shafts), aluminum (engine components), copper (wiring) Semiconductors: Power inverters, converters Plastic and Polymers: Encapsulation materials, lightweight composite components</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>	
		<p>Maximize the amount of hydrogen that can be stored in a given volume to extend the operational range of the train between refueling stops</p>	<p>Hydrogen storage tanks to ensure compatibility with refueling infrastructure</p>	<p>Metallic: Aluminum, carbon fiber (composite materials for lightweight tanks) Plastic and Polymers: Liners for tanks, pressure containment materials</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>
		<p>Provide quick and efficient refuel hydrogen storage tanks at stations, to minimize downtime and keep trains in operation</p>	<p>Hydrogen refueling infrastructure to integrate with green hydrogen production sources and ensure high reliability and minimal downtime</p>	<p>Metallic: Stainless steel (pipes and valves), aluminum (storage tanks) Semiconductors: Control systems for pressure and flow regulation Plastic and Polymers: Piping insulation, safety coatings</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>
		<p>Streamline Energy Management i.e., coordinate the use of energy from batteries, hydrogen fuel cells, and conventional power sources and enable regenerative braking systems</p>	<p>Integrated powertrains combining battery, hydrogen, and conventional systems versus hybrid braking recovery systems</p>	<p>Metallic: Steel (drive shafts), aluminum (engine components), copper (wiring) Semiconductors: Silicon carbide (SiC) power devices, gallium nitride (GaN) transistors Plastic and Polymers: Encapsulation materials for semiconductor devices</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>
		<p>Integrate multiple energy sources in rail systems, combining both the efficiency and flexibility of train operations while reducing environmental impact</p>	<p>Power electronics for efficient energy conversion</p>	<p>Metallic: Copper (wiring, busbars), aluminum (heat sinks) Semiconductors: Silicon carbide (SiC) power devices, gallium nitride (GaN) transistors Plastic and Polymers: Encapsulation materials for semiconductor devices</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>
		<p>Real-time control systems for seamless transition between power sources</p>	<p>Real-time control systems for seamless transition between power sources</p>	<p>Semiconductors with Silicon Carbide (SiC) for high efficiency in power electronics Copper for wiring and electrical components</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>
		<p>AI algorithms and ML models for monitoring smart aging</p>	<p>AI algorithms and ML models for monitoring smart aging</p>	<p>Semiconductors with Gallium Nitride (GaN) as emerging in power systems</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>
		<p>Energy management systems for optimizing the hybrid powertrain</p>	<p>Energy management systems for optimizing the hybrid powertrain</p>	<p>Semiconductors with Silicon Carbide (SiC) for high efficiency in power systems Copper for wiring and electrical components</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>
		<p>Energy management systems for optimizing the hybrid powertrain</p>	<p>Energy management systems for optimizing the hybrid powertrain</p>	<p>Semiconductors with Gallium Nitride (GaN) as emerging in power systems</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>
		<p>Energy management systems for optimizing the hybrid powertrain</p>	<p>Energy management systems for optimizing the hybrid powertrain</p>	<p>Semiconductors with Silicon Carbide (SiC) for high efficiency in power systems Copper for wiring and electrical components</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>
<p>Renewable Energy Source (RES) Increase for both infrastructure and Rolling Stock (Same as FA4) -</p> <p>Energy storage systems (ESS)</p> <p>Green Electrification</p>	<p>Smart, Renewable Energy-powered Stations</p>	<p>Use Renewable Energy Generation and generate grid independence by generating energy on-site or near rail stations and tracks, particularly in remote areas.</p>	<p>Solar Panels Metallic: Silicon (cell), aluminum (frames), silver (contacts) Semiconductors: Silicon (photovoltaic cells) Plastic and Polymers: Encapsulation layers, backsheet</p>	<p>Low efficiency in remote areas High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>	
		<p>Optimize the energy usage within the rail system by managing the integration of various energy sources by relying on real-time monitoring and control.</p>	<p>Energy management systems (EMS) to provide analytics and reporting on energy usage</p>	<p>Copper for electrical wiring systems Semiconductors: Enclosures, insulation materials</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>
		<p>Energy Storage (Store excess energy generated from renewables) or during off-peak times for later use, ensuring a reliable supply during high-demand periods.</p>	<p>Grid integration and storage solutions to provide fast response to changes in energy demand</p>	<p>Metallic: Lithium (batteries), copper (wiring) Semiconductors: Power converters, inverters Plastic and Polymers: Battery housing, insulation materials</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>
		<p>Grid Stability: Provide grid support functions like frequency regulation and load balancing to maintain stability when integrating renewable energy into the rail power system.</p>	<p>Advanced supercapacitor in fact complement batteries in managing short-term power fluctuations thus ensuring long cycle life</p>	<p>Metallic: Aluminum (electrodes), carbon (anodes) Semiconductors: Power control systems Plastic and Polymers: Enclosures, insulation layers</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>
		<p>Efficient Energy Conversion (e.g., AC to DC), Voltage Regulation (correct voltage levels for different rail subsystems) and Harmonics Reduction (reduce power quality issues)</p>	<p>Power conversion systems to offer real-time control and adaptability</p>	<p>Metallic: Copper (wiring, aluminum (heat sinks)) Semiconductors: Silicon carbide (SiC) devices Plastic and Polymers: Enclosures, insulation materials</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>
		<p>Provide a modular approach to electrification that can be scaled up or down depending on the specific needs of different rail segments</p>	<p>Electrification infrastructure using green energy sources offer scalability for future network expansion</p>	<p>Metallic: Copper (system systems), steel (tracks), aluminum (conductor) Semiconductors: Power electronics for managing grid integration Plastic and Polymers: Insulation for cables, protective coatings</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>
		<p>Smart Grid Integration to manage and distribute energy efficiently across the rail network, adapting to demand changes and supply in real-time (incl. Energy Loss Reduction, Fault Detection Management)</p>	<p>Advanced energy distribution systems to offer real-time monitoring and control</p>	<p>Metallic: Copper (wiring, aluminum (transformers)) Semiconductors: smart grid components, inverters Plastic and Polymers: Cable insulation, housing for electronics</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>
		<p>Proactive Equipment Maintenance to predict and prevent equipment failure before it occurs, reducing downtime and extending the lifespan of rail components</p>	<p>Predictive maintenance systems</p>	<p>Metallic: Steel (copper for sensor housings and wiring) Semiconductors: Sensor components, chips Plastic and Polymers: Enclosures, insulation materials</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>
		<p>Optimize the whole energy and operations needs</p>	<p>AI</p>	<p>AI</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>
		<p>Optimize the whole energy and operations needs</p>	<p>AI</p>	<p>AI</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>	<p>High (existing, need for adaptation)</p>

VERY LOW CRITICALITY (TRL 5-6 by 2030)

<p>Develop an innovative type of on-board energy storage - solid-state battery technology</p>	<p>High (Autonomous Train)</p>	<p>High (Autonomous Train)</p>	<p>High (Autonomous Train)</p>
<p>Develop systems with holistic energy management - considering specific use cases (freight, passenger, terminals), infrastructure components, energy storage, etc.</p>	<p>Moderate</p>	<p>High (Autonomous Train)</p>	<p>High (Autonomous Train)</p>
<p>Design and improve the capacity of the vehicles to be attractive/accessible to various stakeholders</p>	<p>Moderate</p>	<p>Moderate</p>	<p>Moderate</p>
<p>Design of Energy Harvesting systems to optimize sensor autonomy</p>	<p>Moderate</p>	<p>Moderate</p>	<p>Moderate</p>
<p>EMEs can contribute to systems improvement by focusing on electro-mechanical components for low-consumption, low-emission, low-volatility, low-variation loads</p>	<p>Moderate</p>	<p>Moderate</p>	<p>Moderate</p>

cl. Digital Automatic Coupler - DAC-) Full Digital Freight Train Operations

Smart and Efficient Operation for Reduced Consumption, Reduced Emission, Enhanced Safety	Operational Efficiency	Continuous Monitoring to capture and transmit data on train and off-structure performance.	Real-time data collection sensors to monitor route analysis and generate an informed decision.	Metals: Copper (wiring, steel structural components), Sensor chips, microcontrollers, Plastics and Polymers: Flexible sensor components, insulation.	High-strength steel (HS) for structural components.	Control algorithms for energy management.	Moderate to Low (TRL 6 by 2027 only)	Moderate to Low (TRL 6 by 2027 only)				
		Reduce & optimize onboard passenger ride quality and passenger comfort (noise, vibration, acceleration, etc.).	Active noise and vibration control systems.	Metals: Steel (structure), Aluminum (interior), Semiconductors: DSP, Digital Signal Processing (DSP) chips, Plastics and Polymers: Acoustic insulation, vibration damping materials.	Acoustic insulation with Sound Mass (SM) for high-frequency noise control systems.	Metals: Steel (structure), Aluminum (interior), Semiconductors: DSP, Digital Signal Processing (DSP) chips, Plastics and Polymers: Acoustic insulation, vibration damping materials.	Control algorithms for noise and vibration management.	Moderate to Low (TRL 6 by 2027 only)	Moderate to Low (TRL 6 by 2027 only)			
		Minimize the noise reduction at source (e.g., generated by train movements, handling both passenger and commodities near rail lines).	Low-noise track and wheel designs.	Metals: High-grade steel (wheels, axles), Aluminum (housings), Semiconductors: Sensor chips, microcontrollers, Plastics and Polymers: Composite materials for noise reduction.	Acoustic insulation with Sound Mass (SM) for high-frequency noise control systems.	Metals: Steel (structure), Aluminum (interior), Semiconductors: DSP, Digital Signal Processing (DSP) chips, Plastics and Polymers: Acoustic insulation, vibration damping materials.	Simulation software for optimizing track and wheel design.	Moderate to Low (TRL 6 by 2027 only)	Moderate to Low (TRL 6 by 2027 only)			
		Develop powerful and efficient propulsion, reducing energy consumption and operational costs.	High-efficiency traction systems.	Metals: Copper (wiring and stator), steel (motor casing), Semiconductors: Silicon carbide (SiC) or gallium nitride (GaN) power systems, Plastics and Polymers: Insulation for motor windings, enclosures.	Acoustic insulation with Sound Mass (SM) for high-frequency noise control systems.	Metals: Steel (structure), Aluminum (interior), Semiconductors: DSP, Digital Signal Processing (DSP) chips, Plastics and Polymers: Acoustic insulation, vibration damping materials.	Control systems for optimizing energy used in traction and HVAC systems.	Moderate to Low (TRL 6 by 2027 only)	Moderate to Low (TRL 6 by 2027 only)			
		Climate control optimized to save space temperature and air quality inside trains, enhancing passenger comfort.	Advanced HVAC (Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning) systems.	Metals: Aluminum (heat exchangers), copper (wiring), Semiconductors: Temperature sensors, control electronics, Plastics and Polymers: Ductwork, insulation, fan housings.	Acoustic insulation with Sound Mass (SM) for high-frequency noise control systems.	Metals: Steel (structure), Aluminum (interior), Semiconductors: DSP, Digital Signal Processing (DSP) chips, Plastics and Polymers: Acoustic insulation, vibration damping materials.	Proactive algorithms for adaptive energy management.	Moderate to Low (TRL 6 by 2027 only)	Moderate to Low (TRL 6 by 2027 only)			
		Rail Usage Attraction/enhancement through Passenger XP and Accessibility innovative solutions	Operational Efficiency	Seamless payment systems (i.e. Semiconductor Substrate/Wafer, Transistors, Integrated Circuits, Co-Integrators for RFID Chips, Tower Management Circuits, and Memory Cells).	Contactless payment systems (i.e. Semiconductor Substrate/Wafer, Transistors, Integrated Circuits, Co-Integrators for RFID Chips, Tower Management Circuits, and Memory Cells).	Metals: Copper (interconnect), aluminum (housing), Semiconductors: RFID chips, microprocessors, Plastics and Polymers: Card reader casing, RFID tag.	High-strength steel (HS) and aluminum (AL) for lightweight coupling systems.	Payment processing systems for digital transactions.	Moderate to Low (TRL 6 by 2027 only)	Moderate to Low (TRL 6 by 2027 only)		
				Passenger information to provide up-to-date travel information (e.g. schedules and delays) to improve the passenger experience.	Integrated real-time information display (i.e. LEDs and display panel technology (combination of LEDs and LCDs)).	Metals: Aluminum (frames), rare earth metals (LEDs), Semiconductors: LED drivers, microcontrollers, Plastics and Polymers: Display screen casing, protective layers.	High-strength steel (HS) and aluminum (AL) for lightweight coupling systems.	Metals: Steel (structure), Aluminum (interior), Semiconductors: DSP, Digital Signal Processing (DSP) chips, Plastics and Polymers: Acoustic insulation, vibration damping materials.	Real-time data management for passenger information systems.	Moderate to Low (TRL 6 by 2027 only)	Moderate to Low (TRL 6 by 2027 only)	
				Easy and safe accessibility access for passengers with reduced mobility using the rail system more inclusive.	Step-free access aids.	Metals: Aluminum (frames), steel (fill and support structure), Semiconductors: Control system sensors, motor Plastics and Polymers: Non-slip surface, safety barriers.	High-strength steel (HS) and aluminum (AL) for lightweight coupling systems.	Metals: Steel (structure), Aluminum (interior), Semiconductors: DSP, Digital Signal Processing (DSP) chips, Plastics and Polymers: Acoustic insulation, vibration damping materials.	User interface software for accessibility features (e.g., tactile buttons and lifts).	Moderate to Low (TRL not communicated)	Moderate to Low (TRL not communicated)	
				Assist visually and hearing-impaired passengers with navigation and travel through clear audio, visual, and tactile cues.	Audio-visual aids and tactile guidance systems (i.e. Microprocessors, Memory Chips and Sensors).	Metals: Copper (wiring, steel mounting), Semiconductors: Microprocessors, LED drivers, Plastics and Polymers: Speaker housing, display enclosures.	High-strength steel (HS) and aluminum (AL) for lightweight coupling systems.	Metals: Steel (structure), Aluminum (interior), Semiconductors: DSP, Digital Signal Processing (DSP) chips, Plastics and Polymers: Acoustic insulation, vibration damping materials.	Integrated systems for managing audio-visual aids.	Moderate to Low (TRL 6 by 2027 only)	Moderate to Low (TRL 6 by 2027 only)	
				Offer ergonomic and adaptable seating options for passenger comfort.	Advanced seating solutions, e.g. Anti-theft protection, Materials for interiors (and exteriors).	Metals: Aluminum (frames), steel (mountings), Plastics and Polymers: Cushions (foam), fabric coverings.	High-strength steel (HS) and aluminum (AL) for lightweight coupling systems.	Metals: Steel (structure), Aluminum (interior), Semiconductors: DSP, Digital Signal Processing (DSP) chips, Plastics and Polymers: Acoustic insulation, vibration damping materials.	Control systems for adaptive climate control and lighting (e.g., software to adjust lighting, acoustic and air conditioning level to passenger).	Moderate to High (TRL potentially at 8/9 by 2031)	High (TRL potentially at 8/9 by 2031)	
Create an adaptive Environment through automatically adjusted lighting and climate settings (based on passenger density and external conditions).	Intelligent climate control and lighting systems (LEDs and electronic drivers) enhancing comfort and energy efficiency, e.g. Sensors to detect light and acoustics levels.			Metals: Aluminum (frames), steel (mountings), Plastics and Polymers: LED drivers, microcontrollers, Lighting Systems: Metal: Aluminum (housing), rare earth metals (LEDs), Semiconductors: LED drivers, microcontrollers.	High-strength steel (HS) and aluminum (AL) for lightweight coupling systems.	Metals: Steel (structure), Aluminum (interior), Semiconductors: DSP, Digital Signal Processing (DSP) chips, Plastics and Polymers: Acoustic insulation, vibration damping materials.	User interfaces for passenger comfort customization.	Moderate to High (TRL potentially at 8/9 by 2027)	High (TRL potentially at 8/9 by 2027)			
DAC	Operational Efficiency			Automatic Coupler Systems with mechanized components for coupling/uncoupling trains.	Mechanical Coupler Components	Metals: Steel (HS) for durability and strength, Aluminum (AL) for lightweight parts, Plastics and Polymers: Nylon or Polyurethane for bushings and wear-resistant surfaces.	High-strength steel (HS) and aluminum (AL) for lightweight coupling systems.	Coupling Control Algorithms: Software that manages and monitors coupling processes.	Moderate to High (TRL 8/9 targeted for most DAC elements for 2027 - see ERU MAWP)	Steel - High criticality		
Full Digital Freight Train Operations	Operational Efficiency	Power Supply Systems that include transformers and converters for 400V operations.	Transformers	Metals: Copper (Co) for windings, Silicon Steel (Si-Fe) for the core, Plastics and Polymers: Polyethylene (PE) for insulation, Epoxy resin for the coating.	Copper (Co) for high-capacity electrical wiring, Gold (Au) for high-performance connectors.	Energy Management Systems: Software for optimizing energy use and distribution.	Moderate to High (TRL 8/9 targeted for most communication elements for 2027 - see ERU MAWP)	Copper - High criticality				
Train Function (e.g., Automated Brake Test)	Operational Efficiency	Communication Modules with devices that secure data transmission across the train.	Transceivers	Metals: Copper (Co) for antenna connections, Gold (Au) for high-quality connectors, Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for radio frequency (RF) chips, Plastics and Polymers: Dielectric materials for housing.	Silicon (Si) for power modules and communication chips.	Communication Protocols: Software that ensures reliable data exchange.	Moderate to High (TRL 8/9 targeted for most communication elements for 2027 - see ERU MAWP)	Silicon - Very High criticality				
Automated Yard Operations	Operational Efficiency	Integrity Monitoring Sensors with devices that ensure the train's physical integrity.	Strain Gauges	Metals: Invarium (In-Co alloy) for the sensing element, Plastics and Polymers: Enclosures for protection.	Aluminum (AL) for lightweight structures, Steel (St) for robust sensitive components.	Yard Management Systems: Software to control and automate yard operations.	Moderate to High (TRL 8/9 targeted for some Advanced Yard Operations for 2031 - see ERU MAWP)	Aluminum - Moderate criticality				

* Develop digital customer platforms to offer new services to all freight customers, allowing real-time management of the logistics chain.

* Identify and design multimodal solutions to improve multimodality and thus facilitate transportation.

* Create digitalized and automated rail freight operations tools to allow seamless operations between all players in the rail freight sector (boosting transport service for the customer, planning and dispatching trains, smoothing train functions monitoring).

* Design and produce multi-functional and modular wagon.

* SMEs can focus on niche areas like sensors, actuators, communication modules, or specific types of coupler materials.

* SMEs can focus on upgrading Production Capabilities as there will be a need to produce more sophisticated and reliable components for DAC systems may require SMEs to invest in new manufacturing technologies and processes, such as precision machining, advanced electronics assembly, and high-quality materials.

* SMEs can focus on offering specialized aftermarket services as DAC technology will require ongoing maintenance, diagnostics, and software updates.

Intelligent Train (in)		Seamless Rail Freight		Innovative Freight Assets			
Seamless Rail Freight	Seamless Planning and Dispatching	Communication Networks for continuous exchange between systems	Routers & Switches	Metals: Copper (Cu) for wiring, Gold (Au) for connectors Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for network components Plastics and Polymers: Polyethylene for housing, Polyvinyl Chloride (PVC) for insulation	Real-Time Dispatching Tools: Software that manages the real-time allocation of resources.	Function for 2021 - see ERU MAWP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High Criticality - High criticality Medium Criticality - Moderate criticality
		Intermodal Transfer Equipment with cranes and automated systems for moving freight between transport modes	Components	Metals: Steel (Fe) for structural components, Aluminum (Al) for lightweight sections Metals: Stainless Steel (Fe) for rollers and pistons, Copper (Cu) for shafts Plastics and Polymers: Polyethylene for seals and gaskets Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for control electronics Plastics and Polymers: Polypropylene for casings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Steel (Fe) for mechanical structures in transfer equipment, Copper (Cu) for IoT device wiring Silicon (Si) for GPS and RFID chips Polypropylene and polyethylene for housing and taps 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Traditional mechanical tracking systems that don't utilize modern communication and sensors Intermodal Logistics Platforms: Software that integrates and optimizes the flow of goods across transport modes. Predictive Analytics Tools: Software for predicting and optimizing intermodal connections and schedules. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Moderate (TIL 8/9 targeted for some seamless intermodality for 2027 - see ERU MAWP) Steel - Moderate criticality Silicon - High criticality
Innovative Freight Assets	Intermodal Integrations and Production	Tracking and Monitoring Devices such as IoT devices to track cargo across different modes of transport	Control Systems	Metals: Copper (Cu) for wiring, Gold (Au) for connectors Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for network components Plastics and Polymers: Polyethylene for casings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Internal combustion engine components with materials like cast iron and basic steel might be reduced in favor of electric or hybrid systems Containerment Monitoring Systems: Software that tracks hydrogen levels, pressure, and safety conditions. Autonomous Navigation Software: Systems that manage the movement and routing of the wagon. Energy Management Software: To optimize battery usage and propulsion efficiency. Predictive Maintenance Tools: Software that uses energy data to predict and optimize maintenance needs. Energy Optimization Algorithms: Software that optimizes energy use across the train's systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Moderate (Cluster created after the ERU MAWP - likelihood of FAA) Low (Cluster created after the ERU MAWP - likelihood of FAA) Moderate (Cluster created after the ERU MAWP - likelihood of FAA) Low (Cluster created after the ERU MAWP - likelihood of FAA) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Aluminum - Moderate criticality Silicon - High criticality Copper - Moderate criticality High Criticality - High criticality Adv. Polymers - Moderate criticality
		Hydrogen Transport Container	RFID Tags	Metals: Copper (Cu) for antenna, Aluminum (Al) for tag frames Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for RFID chips Metals and Polymers: Composites for tag housing			
Innovative Freight Assets	Hydrogen Transport Container	Safety Valves and Sensors, i.e. components for monitoring and ensuring the safe containment of hydrogen	Valves	Metals: Stainless Steel (Fe) for valve bodies, Brass (Cu-Zn alloy) for fittings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Internal combustion engine components with materials like cast iron and basic steel might be reduced in favor of electric or hybrid systems Containerment Monitoring Systems: Software that tracks hydrogen levels, pressure, and safety conditions. Autonomous Navigation Software: Systems that manage the movement and routing of the wagon. Energy Management Software: To optimize battery usage and propulsion efficiency. Predictive Maintenance Tools: Software that uses energy data to predict and optimize maintenance needs. Energy Optimization Algorithms: Software that optimizes energy use across the train's systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Moderate (Cluster created after the ERU MAWP - likelihood of FAA) Low (Cluster created after the ERU MAWP - likelihood of FAA) Moderate (Cluster created after the ERU MAWP - likelihood of FAA) Low (Cluster created after the ERU MAWP - likelihood of FAA) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Aluminum - Moderate criticality Silicon - High criticality Copper - Moderate criticality High Criticality - High criticality Adv. Polymers - Moderate criticality
		Onboard Propulsion Systems Fit for electric or hybrid engines for self-propulsion	Electric Motors	Metals: Aluminum (Al) for motor core, Steel (Fe) for windings Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for control electronics Metals: Steel (Fe) for gears, Aluminum (Al) for housings			
Innovative Freight Assets	Self-Propelled Wagon	Battery Storage, i.e. high-capacity batteries for powering the wagon	Battery Storage	Metals: Lithium (Li) for battery casing, Copper (Cu) for electrical connections Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for battery management systems Plastics and Polymers: Polyethylene for insulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conventional braking materials that do not support energy recovery, such as certain grades of steel and older composites Predictive Maintenance Tools: Software that uses energy data to predict and optimize maintenance needs. Energy Optimization Algorithms: Software that optimizes energy use across the train's systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Moderate (Cluster created after the ERU MAWP - likelihood of FAA) Low (Cluster created after the ERU MAWP - likelihood of FAA) Moderate (Cluster created after the ERU MAWP - likelihood of FAA) Low (Cluster created after the ERU MAWP - likelihood of FAA) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Aluminum - Moderate criticality Silicon - High criticality Copper - Moderate criticality High Criticality - High criticality Adv. Polymers - Moderate criticality
		Sensors for Navigation and Control with devices for managing wagon movement autonomously	Inertial Measurement Units (IMUs)	Metals: Copper (Cu) for casing Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for MEMS gyroscopes and accelerometers Plastics and Polymers: Polyethylene for housing			
Innovative Freight Assets	Energy Efficiency Strategy for Freight	Energy Recovery Systems Thanks to devices like regenerative braking systems to capture and reuse energy	Regenerative Braking Units	Metals: Lithium (Li) for lithium-ion cells, Nickel (Ni) for cathodes, Copper (Cu) for anodes Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for battery management systems Plastics and Polymers: Polypropylene for battery cell casings, Polyethylene for casings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conventional braking materials that do not support energy recovery, such as certain grades of steel and older composites Predictive Maintenance Tools: Software that uses energy data to predict and optimize maintenance needs. Energy Optimization Algorithms: Software that optimizes energy use across the train's systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Moderate (Cluster created after the ERU MAWP - likelihood of FAA) Low (Cluster created after the ERU MAWP - likelihood of FAA) Moderate (Cluster created after the ERU MAWP - likelihood of FAA) Low (Cluster created after the ERU MAWP - likelihood of FAA) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Aluminum - Moderate criticality Silicon - High criticality Copper - Moderate criticality High Criticality - High criticality Adv. Polymers - Moderate criticality
		Energy Storage Units using batteries or capacitors to store recovered energy	Battery Cells	Metals: Lithium (Li) for lithium-ion cells, Nickel (Ni) for cathodes, Copper (Cu) for anodes Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for battery management systems Plastics and Polymers: Polypropylene for battery cell casings, Polyethylene for casings			
Innovative Freight Assets	Energy Efficiency Strategy for Freight	Capacitors (if used)	Capacitors (if used)	Metals: Aluminum (Al) for capacitor plates, Copper (Cu) for terminals, Polyethylene for casing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conventional braking materials that do not support energy recovery, such as certain grades of steel and older composites Predictive Maintenance Tools: Software that uses energy data to predict and optimize maintenance needs. Energy Optimization Algorithms: Software that optimizes energy use across the train's systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Moderate (Cluster created after the ERU MAWP - likelihood of FAA) Low (Cluster created after the ERU MAWP - likelihood of FAA) Moderate (Cluster created after the ERU MAWP - likelihood of FAA) Low (Cluster created after the ERU MAWP - likelihood of FAA) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Aluminum - Moderate criticality Silicon - High criticality Copper - Moderate criticality High Criticality - High criticality Adv. Polymers - Moderate criticality
		Battery Management System (BMS)	Battery Management System (BMS)	Metals: Copper (Cu) for wiring, Gold (Au) for high-reliability connectors Semiconductors: Silicon (Si) for microcontrollers and sensors Plastics and Polymers: Polyethylene for housing, Epoxy for PCB insulation			
Innovative Freight Assets	Energy Efficiency Strategy for Freight	Cooling System (for high-capacity storage)	Cooling System (for high-capacity storage)	Metals: Aluminum (Al) for heat sinks, Copper (Cu) for coolant pathways Plastics and Polymers: Polyethylene for fan housing, PVC for insulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conventional braking materials that do not support energy recovery, such as certain grades of steel and older composites Predictive Maintenance Tools: Software that uses energy data to predict and optimize maintenance needs. Energy Optimization Algorithms: Software that optimizes energy use across the train's systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Moderate (Cluster created after the ERU MAWP - likelihood of FAA) Low (Cluster created after the ERU MAWP - likelihood of FAA) Moderate (Cluster created after the ERU MAWP - likelihood of FAA) Low (Cluster created after the ERU MAWP - likelihood of FAA) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Aluminum - Moderate criticality Silicon - High criticality Copper - Moderate criticality High Criticality - High criticality Adv. Polymers - Moderate criticality
		Capacitors (if used)	Capacitors (if used)	Metals: Aluminum (Al) for capacitor plates, Copper (Cu) for terminals, Polyethylene for casing			